

VALKYRIES

D2.7 Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases M12

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Main Contributor: INDRA

**Other Contributors: SERMAS, TAS, ISEMI, SSSA, KEMEA, HESE,
USN, AREU, NOVOTEC, PARTICLE, BDI, HRT**

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Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Daniel Pablo Alonso	dpablo@indra.es	IND
Guillem Puntí Sadurní	gpunti@indra.es	IND
Roumen Daton Medenou Choumanof	rdaton@indra.es	IND

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
INDRA SISTEMAS S.A.	IND	Definition of requirements, demonstration scenarios and CONOPs
SERVICIO DE URGENCIAS Y EMERGENCIAS DE LA COMUNIDAD DE MADRID (SUMMA112)	SERMAS	
TASSICA EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A.	TAS	
INTERNATIONAL SECURITY AND EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT INSTITUTE	ISEMI	
PARTICLE	PARTICLE	
UNIVERSIDAD DE MURCIA	UMU	
SCUOLA SUPERIORE DI STUDI UNIVERSITARI E DI PERFEZIONAMENTO S ANNA	SSSA	
NOVOTEC	NOVOTEC	
BLOCKCHAIN2050 BV	BLC	
BULGARIAN DEFENCE INSTITUTE	BDI	
BULGARIAN RED CROSS	BRC	
KENTRO MELETON ASFALEIAS	KEM	
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO ÉVORA	HESE	
ARATOS.NET LTD	ARA	
UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH-EASTERN NORWAY	USN	
AGENZIA REGIONALE EMERGENZA URGENZA	AREU	
HELLENIC RESCUE TEAM	HRT	

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A/0	27/09/2022	All	Original document
A/1	25/01/2023	7. Annex A CONOPs 7.1. UC#1 CONOPs Annex E Traceability matrix (Chapter added)	<p>Changes were added to be more specific in UC#1 Annex A – CONOPs section based on evaluators' suggestion in the Consolidated Review Report.</p> <p>Certain parts from this section were reduced and words in other languages were removed. The text was shorted after evaluators review to focus on the main subject and not explain every small detail.</p> <p>Comment: This deliverable is the updated version of D2.1. This document contains more than 300 pages, and some parts are just merged from other collaborators without converting text into English. The text is informative, but the beneficiary has to shorten this part and focus on the main subject and not explain every small thing. This text should not represent a grant application but a delivery report.</p> <p>The matrix is included in D2.1 and will be used in the deliverables from this point onwards to ensure requirements' compliance.</p>

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1. Executive Summary

VALKYRIES aims at developing cutting-edge advances to support the standardisation and harmonisation of first aids vehicles deployment, training, maintenance, logistic and remote centralised coordination means for effective deployment of resources during the run-up to a major crisis related to any kind of disaster (natural or intentional) that demands the fast actuation and coordination of health emergency services and the associated response teams, with Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) and volunteering. The project will cover the Disaster Management life cycle with a clear focus on enhancing the capabilities of the EU market and R&D initiatives to bring harmonised mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery advances towards achieving and increasing EU disaster resilience.

The primary objective of the VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate, and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes, and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness, and cross-sector/border cooperation for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

This document **D2.7 Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases M12** defines the final version of technical requirements (Base, Extended and Common requirements), their traceability between objectives, and provided a detailed definition of the Use Cases and their respective CONOPs. They are developed with a higher level of maturity compared to the first delivery in the M6.

The following summarises the main contributions of **D2.7**:

- Identification of the set of Base, Extended and Common requirements.
- Introduction of a set of Use Cases for supporting the verification and demonstration of each VALKYRIES most outstanding block of functionalities.
- Definition of four large-scale demonstration scenarios.

Finally, it should be highlighted that this D2.7 version A/0 presents the VALKYRIES Consortium in terms of Uses Cases and potential Demonstration Scenarios. However, it is expected that these will be reviewed by partners, end-users, and customers as the project progresses. This could lead to future modifications or reconsiderations.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases M12

Deliverable Id: D2.7

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D2.7

Name of lead participant: IND

Name of Contributors: SERMAS, TAS, ISEMI, SSSA, KEMEA, HESE, USN, AREU, NOVOTEC, PARTICLE

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Linked project tasks: T2.1 System Requirements, Concepts of Operation, and demonstrators

Action: Design

Status: **Second Release, version A/1** (Update of D2.1)

Document Layout: Custom layout

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonisation and Pre-Standardisation of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. The document presents the requirements of VALKYRIES and the demonstrations scenarios, covering the conditions associated with each work package.

3. Document and Project Scope

3.1. Requirement's context

3.1.1. Development Methodology

The requirements presented in this document are the result of the revision, analysis, and transposition to the VALKYRIES context of the set of requirements preliminarily agreed with EC and the annexation of subsets of new requirements concerning the functionalities that differentiate the VALKYRIES project, together with the requirements that guarantee the proper integration and deployment of the VALKYRIES results on the committed end user's infrastructure.

Based on this, the subsets of requirement that comprise the VALKYRIES capabilities are divided into Base Requirements, Extended Requirements, and Common Requirements.

- **Base requirements:** Requirements taken from the description of the tasks in the DoW (technical proposal). Paraphrase of the task description.
- **Extended requirements:** Any other needs not explicitly described in the DoW (technical proposal). They can be considered optional, but it is often good to include them, since they support a more concrete and refined outline of the task.
- **Common requirements:** Requirements that are derived from the extended ones after an agreement among all partners. The extended requirements that are not agreed among partners will be excluded from the template and will no longer be part of the common requirements.

Figure 1 - Requirements overview

3.1.2. Timeline

The proposed methodology shall be enforced on the following six phases:

- **Phase 1** As an early step, the D2.1 leader (INDRA) presents the first draft of this document, describing the working methodology and a complete transposition of the Base Requirements inherited from meetings with Use Cases owners. The document is shared with the Consortium looking for feedback and revisions. The updated document is internally referred to as the “First Base Version of the VALKYRIES Requirements”.
- **Phase 2** The consortium provides a first version of new requirements related with VALKYRIES end user rules and the core functionalities they represent. A new documental stable version referred to as “First Extended Version of the VALKYRIES Requirements” is released, which covers the first iteration on new extended requirements, compile, and embrace the revisions off all the partners on the “First Base Version of the VALKYRIES Requirements” create at the previous phase.
- **Phase 3** During this phase all the partners review the “First Extended Version of the VALKYRIES Requirements”, providing comments and recommendations which implementation result in the “Revised Extended Version of the VALKYRIES Requirements”. This iteration also includes new requirements suggested by T2.1 non-contributors, thus refining the coverage of the WP and Task in the VALKYRIES project they lead or in which they participate. At the end of this stage, the resulting requirements and documentation are shared with the EC and committed end users for revision.
- **Phase 4** The fourth step comprises a direct iteration with the end users towards imbuing their vision of the expected VALKYRIES outcomes as principal end-users. Based on the “Revised Extended Version of the VALKYRIES Requirements” shared as an early draft of D2.1, the end users may review, discuss, comment, and resolve any doubt about the proposed requirements. The Consortium will attend their requirements (referred to as Common Requirements) and recommendations, and they will be appended in a new stable version, which pre-releases the final D2.1a.
- **Phase 5** This stage focuses on the definition of the VALKYRIES demonstration Use Cases (UC), thus entailing a direct interaction between the consortium and the committed end users. The result is an agreement of each demonstration UC coverage and expectative, and a clear contextualisation of them regarding the VALKYRIES measurable and qualifiedly outcomes, as is the case of their direct traceability against the preliminarily agreed Extended Requirements released at D2.1a.
- **Phase 6** During this stage, the requirements that guarantee the coverage of the agreed demonstration UCs will be included over D2.1a, which will include a final subset of Common Requirements. This phase will result on the final D21.a, which extends the coverable of D2.1a by providing a comprehensively description of the agreed demonstration UCs and the Common Requirements linked to them.

Figure 2 - Timeline requirements

3.1.3. Requirement Levels

The VALKYRIES verification and validation requirements are defined in compliance with the nomenclature described in IETF RFC 2119 [1], which settles the words commonly harmonised towards describing the signify of the requirements in their specification, as well as how they should be interpreted. These key words are "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL", to be interpreted as described in the Table below.

Word	Alternative	Application in VALKYRIES requirement specifications
MUST	REQUIRED SHALL	This word, or the terms " REQUIRED " or " SHALL ", mean that the definition is an absolute requirement of the specification.
MUST NOT	SHALL NOT	This phrase, or the phrase " SHALL NOT ", mean that the definition is an absolute prohibition of the specification.
SHOULD	RECOMMENDED	This word, or the adjective " RECOMMENDED ", mean that there may exist valid reasons in particular circumstances to ignore a particular item, but the full implications must be understood and carefully weighed before choosing a different course.
SHOULD NOT	NOT RECOMMENDED	This phrase, or the phrase " NOT RECOMMENDED " mean that there may exist valid reasons in particular circumstances when the particular behaviour is acceptable or even useful, but the full implications should be understood, and the case carefully weighed before implementing any behaviour described with this label.
MAY	OPTIONAL	This word, or the adjective " OPTIONAL ", mean that an item is truly optional. One capability may choose to include the item because a particular operational condition requires it or because it may enhance the solution while state of the art solutions may omit the same item. An implementation which does not include a particular option MUST be prepared to interoperate with another implementation which does include the option, though perhaps with reduced functionality. In the same vein an implementation which does include a particular option MUST be prepared to interoperate with another implementation, which does not include the option (except, of course, for the feature the option provides.)

Table 1 - Requirement Levels

3.1.4. Requirement Qualification Methods

The methods to use during verification and validation of the system are Demonstration (D), Analysis (A), Test (T), Inspection (I) and Special Qualification Methods (S). The following describes their scope in the context of the VALKYRIES project.

- **Demonstration:** Verification by Demonstration means that the product or system behaves as it is intended to be, and it will be tested in the demonstration scenarios and evaluated by means of a user questionnaire at the end of the demo. Therefore, evaluators can follow the functional user requirements and check that the product or system does what the user requirements say that it should do.
- **Analysis:** Verification by analysis entails the validation of a product or system by using calculations and models, comparing the results obtained with previous studies in terms of Key Performance Parameters (KPPs), Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), thresholds, etc. VALKYRIES evaluators may also rely on analysis to deduce a prognosis of the product or system's performance based on some representative, actual, test results.

The Analytical verification actions cover indicators for cross-component evaluation that include parameters linked to features like accuracy, performance, response time, updatability/upgradability, scalability, or strengthening against adversarial tactics. They can be assessed separately (i.e., component-to-component, function-to-function, etc.) or assuming an integrated VALKYRIES solution. Analytical actions may include benchmarking and quality assessment-based on comparison driven by statistical indicators (e.g., confidence interval, entropy, likelihood, etc.) and/or direct comparison with existing related solutions.

- **Test:** Verification by Tests entails the most technically precise and controlled form of verifying a capability. Based on this, evaluators can test a product to confirm that it behaves precisely as specified under a set of carefully specified test conditions. These operations are typically repeated using different sets of test conditions, following precisely specified steps to complete the test. Therefore, this is often used to verify performance requirements.

VALKYRIES Tests (T) shall verify the operation of the system, or a part of the system, by using instrumentation or other special test equipment to collect data for later analysis. In the context of project, there will be four main types of testing.

- **Unit Testing** - Automated tests written and run by software developers to ensure that a section of an application (known as the "unit") meets its design and behaves as intended. This methodology assumes that units are the smallest testable part of a VALKYRIES related solution, since they enable discovering early problems thorough the development lifecycle. Moreover, unit testing allows developers and experts of all technical partners and stakeholders to amend, refactor or fix code at a later stage, and make sure the module still works correctly.
- **Integration Testing** - During integration testing individual software modules are combined and tested as a group. Integration testing takes as its input the VALKYRIES components that have been unit tested, groups them in larger

aggregates, applies tests defined in an integration test plan to those aggregates, and delivers as its output the integrated system ready for final testing.

The basis behind this type of integration testing is to run user-like workloads in integrated user-like environments. In doing the testing in this manner, the environment is proofed, while the individual components are proofed indirectly through their use.

- **Reliability Testing** - Reliability in statistics and psychometrics is the overall consistency of a measure, which refers to as produces similar results under consistent conditions. In the context of CIS systems (as is the case of the VALKYRIES enablers), software reliability is defined as: the probability of failure-free software operation for a specified period in a concrete environment. Reliability tests shall verify the above by among others, enforcing feature testing, regression testing, or load testing procedures.
- **Security Testing** - Software testing conducted to check whether a software application is secure or not, identifying if the application is vulnerable to attacks. Specifically, 1) It is a process to determine that an information system protects data and maintains functionality as intended; 2) to check how the information flows in a secure environment; 3) to assess how the VALKYRIES capabilities react when being disrupted; and 4) to identify software weaknesses in terms of confidentiality, integrity, authentication, availability, authorisation, and non-repudiation.
- **Inspection:** The verification by inspection is the examination of the product or system using basic senses, so, we would physically examine a product and check all its physical and functional characteristics. It is related to the generation of documentation, and it is the lowest level verification method.
- **Special Qualification Methods:** Any other verification procedure. VALKYRIES Special qualification methods (S) entail any special qualification procedure not covered by conventional inspections, tests, analysis, and demonstration, such as special tools, techniques, procedures, facilities, acceptance limits, and use of standard samples, preproduction or periodic production samples, pilot models, or pilot lots.

3.1.5. Requirement Priorities

VALKYRIES adopts a categorical prioritisation scale for ranking the release date of the functionalities that shall drive the compliance with each targeted requirement. In particular, the following priorities have been considered at requirement definition:

Category	Description	Implications
P1	Critical (Higher Priority)	Priority requirements that must be met for the system not to fail. They shall be partially covered by functionalities to be verified at the earlier verification and validation processes. The fulfilment of the requirement may condition the progress towards meet P2 prioritised conditions.
P2	Medium (Moderate Priority)	P2 requirements should be fulfilled after the P1 requirements are met. The requirements shall be partially covered by functionalities to be verified at the intermediate verification and validation processes.
N/A	Not Applicable	The requirement shall be considered from the very beginning (by design)

Table 2 - Requirements Priorities

3.1.6. Requirement layout

To facilitate the human traceability of both functional and non-functional requirements against the high-level VALKYRIES vision and the project implementation phasing, they have been grouped per WP and tasks. Then each VALKYRIES module is directly linked to a set off Work Packages (WP) and tasks within the implementation plan, which related requirements compliance is mostly affected by the adequate task execution. On these grounds, the Table below depicts the fields that have been considered for requirements gathering.

Requirement	
Editor	Name of the partner that added the requirement.
ID	Identifier depending on the type of requirement, the task, and the requirement number. REQ_[Type]_T[Task number]_[Requirement number] Type: BASE(Base), EXT(Extended) and COM(Common). Task number: From 1.1 to 7.7. Requirement number: From 1 to 100.
Name	Title that captures the general idea of the requirement.
Description	Key insights of the requirement scope framed on the keywords indicated in Section 2.2.3 .
Details	Additional considerations for the requirement fulfilment that extend the overall vision presented in the Description. Details are framed on the keywords indicated in Section 2.2.3 .
Rationale (Optional)	Any consideration that may support the understanding and enforcement of the requirement. If the requirement is inherited from previous related work, the rationale will explicitly indicate and justify its transposition, as well as any potential modification (extension, softening, merge, etc.) concerning the original requirement.
Verification Method	Requirement verification method as detailed in Section 2.2.4 .
Priority	Requirement compliance priority as detailed in Section 2.2.5 .
Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Subset of VALKYRIES objectives Annex F directly linked to the described requirement.

Table 3 - Requirement layout

3.2. Document Structure

This document is organised as follows:

Section 1 Executive Summary provides a summary of the document contents aiming at readers rapidly becoming acquainted with a large body of material without having to read it all.

Section 2 Document and Project Scope identifies the annex, deliverable, and contextualises the motivation and frame for which the document has been created.

Section 3 Key Referent Documents and regulations present the documents considered for requirements gathering.

Section 4 Requirements describe the base, extended and common requirements and its traceability to VALKYRIES objectives.

Section 5 Conclusion remarks the highlights and outcomes of the document.

Annex A The annex introduces a proposal of scenario for the VALKYRIES Use Case Demonstration identified on Use Case #1.

Annex B The annex introduces a proposal of scenario for the VALKYRIES Use Case Demonstration identified on Use Case #2.

Annex C The annex introduces a proposal of scenario for the VALKYRIES Use Case Demonstration identified on Use Case #3.

Annex D The annex introduces a proposal of scenario for the VALKYRIES Use Case Demonstration identified on Use Case #4.

Annex E presents a table with all the identifiers for the challenges described in the call.

4. Key Referent Documents and regulations

The following Table includes the key referent documents and regulations that preliminarily support and guided the D2.7 development assumption.

Document	Title
h2020-wp1820-security_en	Work Programme 2018-2020 14. Secure societies – Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
PROPOSAL_101020676-VALKYRIES-H2020-SU-SEC-2020	Technical Proposal
Grant Agreement-101020676-VALKYRIES	Grant Agreement
H2020 Consortium VALKYRIES Final Version (040521)	Consortium Agreement
101020676_Deliverable_7_(Consultation Strategy)	Consultation Strategy
101020676_Deliverable_8_(Covid-19 Protocol)	Covid-19 Protocol

Table 4 - Key Referent Documents and regulations

5. Requirements

5.1. WP1 - Project Management and Communication

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.1_1	Covid-19 Protocol Plan	Covid-19 protocol SHALL be updated as the project evolves, describing and reporting the effectiveness of the contingencies applied while serving as reference for further related projects.	As the Covid-19 situation evolves, the Consortium MUST look for possible ways to improve the online presence of VALKYRIES and SHOULD ensure the safety of the participants, without disrupting the daily activities of all the committed parties (in particular, emergency responders).	Inspection Demonstration	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.1_2	Periodic Management Report	Project Officer SHALL be informed about the project progress by Periodic Management Report.	They will be submitted at 6-month intervals to regularly inform the Project Officer about the progress of the work and contain an overview of the activities carried out during the reporting period, describes the progress in project objectives, the progress	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				toward the milestones and deliverables set for the period, and any problem found, and corrective actions are taken.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.1_3	Financial Statements & Work Report	Project Officer SHALL be informed about the costs incurred and resources deployed by each contractor by Financial Statements & Work Report.	This deliverable will detail the justification of the costs incurred and of the resources deployed by each contractor, linking them to activities implemented and justifying their necessity, the financial statements from each contractor (which may require an audit certificate) and a summary financial report consolidating the costs of the contractors.	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.1_4	Dashboard VALKYRIES	Dashboard SHOULD allow users and stakeholder's interactions with VALKYRIES applications.	Design and development of a dashboard for allowing users and stakeholders to web-based interact with VALKYRIES applications.	Inspection	P2	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.2_1	Quality Assurance Plan	QRM (Quality Assurance & Risk Manager) SHALL	Quality assurance plan SHALL check any risk assessment	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			develops and supervises a quality plan.	and implementation of mitigation measures ensuring high-quality deliverables and thoroughly tested and reliable solutions. Thus, it SHALL bring an internal FAQ document.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.3_1	Consultation Strategy	It SHALL developed a Consultation Strategy to involve thirds parts as large cluster of External Advisory Boards (EAB), Associated Partners and supportive working groups.	Presentation of the Consortium consultation strategy to getting feedback from stakeholders and establishing a longer-term relationship of mutual benefit and trust.	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_1	Dissemination Strategy	GA - ARTICLE 29_29.1. Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary MUST — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific	Range of activities SHOULD be presented to disseminate VALKYRIES. Among others: 1) At least three VALKYRIES Workshops. 2) At least four VALKYRIES Workshops on Ethical-Legal issues organised in four different countries. 3) At least four VALKYRIES Workshop on Standardisation. 4) Participation in	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			publications (in any medium).	conferences and scientific events. 5) Publication: VALKYRIES partners SHOULD share and select the most appropriate journals and conferences to disseminate the results achieved. Coordination of papers in international journals, workshops, and conferences, in Open Access.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_2	Dissemination Strategy	GA - ARTICLE 29_29.2. Open access to scientific publications	Each beneficiary MUST ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it MUST: as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				<p>Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.</p> <p>(b) Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available free via the publisher, or(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case. <p>(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.</p> <p>The bibliographic metadata MUST be in a standard format and MUST include all</p>			

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				<p>of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and- a persistent identifier.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_3	Dissemination Strategy	GA - ARTICLE 29_29.3. Open access to research data	<p>Regarding the digital research data generated in the action (‘data’), the beneficiaries MUST:</p> <p>(a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">(i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;(ii) not applicable;	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				<p>(iii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (see Annex 1);</p> <p>(b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).</p>			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_4	Communication and Dissemination Strategy	GA - ARTICLE 29_29.4. Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem	<p>Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) MUST:</p> <p>(a) display the EU emblem and</p> <p>(b) include the following text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676".</p> <p>When displayed together</p>	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_5	Communication and Dissemination Strategy	GA - ARTICLE 29_29.5. Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility	Any dissemination of results MUST indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_6	Communication Strategy	VALKYRIES project updates SHOULD be communicated.	Range of activities SHOULD be presented in order to communicate VALKYRIES. Among others: 1) Newsletters to inform stakeholders about project developments (at least five per year) 2) Press releases, SHOULD have to be executed to get the attention of the general public. In this way, we will achieve more public support and awareness. Regular issue of press releases about the	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				project (at least two per year). 3) Fact sheet, poster, brochure, gadget, and flyer to be used during conferences and events to provide easily accessible information about VALKYRIES 4) General public, Industry and other non-scientific conferences, joint events, round tables, show cases and/or exhibitions			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_7	Communication Strategy	VALKYRIES project updates SHOULD be communicated.	Range of activities SHOULD be presented in order to make known VALKYRIES. Among others: 1) Website: Opening, updating, and maintaining a user-friendly public website with general information, news items, event announcements, presentations, a publication list, and our public deliverables. 2) Social networks: Opening,	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				updating, and maintaining social media profiles with general information, news items, event announcements, post, and relevant publications.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_8	Communication Strategy	VALKYRIES project SHOULD have an own identity	Range of activities SHOULD be presented to create the VALKYRIES' identity. Among others: 1) Graphic line: creation of a graphic line according to the project essence Project Logo: a representative logo of the concept and origin of the selected name and topic 2) Documentary templates: A set of PowerPoint and Word templates designed following the graphic line of the project	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_9	Dissemination Strategy	Each partner SHOULD define its individual dissemination strategy	Each partner SHOULD define its individual dissemination strategy, including events, conferences, target magazines, etc	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_10	Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Delivery of deliverable 1.9 Communication and dissemination strategies in M6	Deliverable 1.9 Communication and dissemination strategies MUST be delivered in M6	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_11	Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Delivery of deliverable 1.10 Impact Creation Reports in M12 and M24	Deliverable 1.10 Impact Creation Reports MUST be delivered in M12 and M24	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.4_12	Impact Creation Report	VALKYRIES project SHOULD have an Impact Creation Report	These reports SHOULD outline the VALKYRIES impact created through dissemination and communication activities, including liaison to other activities.	Inspection	N/A	All
IND	REQ_COM_T1.4_1	Dissemination Strategy	A joint dissemination strategy MAY be defined	A joint dissemination strategy MAY be defined which includes dissemination activities performed by two or more partners. The joint dissemination strategy MAY be in line with relevant activities of other (EU-	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				funded) projects closely related with VALKYRIES.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.5_1	Ethical and Legal Compliance Framework	<p>VALKYRIES will analyse and define the legal, societal, and ethical frameworks in which VALKYRIES operates.</p> <p>It will identify and consider legal, ethical, and societal dimensions of the proposed solution that are related to the technology, user processes, behaviours, and decision-making to make sure that the VALKYRIES vision, methodologies and functional and non-functional requirements are compliant with the EU legislation and with ethical norms and practices. This will ensure project compliance with established principles such as privacy by design and privacy by default</p>	<p>The Compliance Framework (CF) SHALL be developed in two versions: 1) initially, it SHALL focus on ensuring the integration of ethics into a daily execution of the project, starting from the design and integration of solutions, and testing in use cases; and 2) an update of the guidelines concerning VALKYRIES' solutions, its use and legality SHALL be provided (feedback and observations from trials, inputs from Ethical Panels). These guidelines are then considered in each WP and deliverables, including verification of the action to the guidelines during tests. The Consortium SHALL opt for Open Research Data Pilot, meaning that except for</p>	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				patent constraints, other IPRs protection, data protection issues, research results MUST follow the FAIR principles. An open repository SHALL be used to Find, Access, Interoperate, and Re-use data. Research publications MUST be in open access.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.5_2	Data Management	Data Management Platform SHALL include the data management life cycle and Data Management Plan (DMP)	Describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated within the project. The plan SHOULD cover methodology and standards, curation, and preservation, but, most importantly, SHOULD specify what data will be shared/made open access and why/why not. Results will be guiding reference for all WPs. It is RECOMMENDED to report on developed guidelines and the VALKYRIES platform that SHOULD be developed by offering a SaaS	Inspection	N/A	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				tool to manage in ethically and legally sustainable way information sharing processes with LEA and the public during prevention and incidents.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T1.5_3	Protocol for Innovators	Guidelines are RECOMMENDED to be extracted to generalise and harmonise applications within similar sectors.	Considering M1.1 and M1.2. Guidelines are RECOMMENDED to be extracted to generalise and harmonise applications within similar sectors.	Inspection	N/A	All

Table 5 - WP1 Requirements

5.2. WP2 - Design Principles and harmonisation Tactics

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_BASE_T2.2_1	Unified glossary and map of Joint terminologies and semantic representations	A common semantic model related to reconnaissance procedures, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters, MUST be produced to facilitate further related standardisation activities.	It at least MUST extend those standardised at ISO 22300 (Security and resilience vocabulary).	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-5
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.2_1	Health and medical unified glossary, terminology and semantic	Support medical data interchange between different applications, so a reference health data structure and model SHALL be established.	Additionally, to the ISO 22300, it shall support EHR (Electronic Health Records) data models. (Candidates standards: ISO 13606-5:2010)	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-3
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.2_2	Extensibility of glossary, semantic and terminology	To be adapted to future evolution of the medical and /or practices, the glossary semantic and terminology may require adaptation while retro-compatibility with legacy,	The solution SHOULD be able to handle evolution of the unified glossary, and support specific countries needs	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			therefore the structure shall support cross reference translation				
TAS	REQ_COM_T2.2_3	Definition of the categories of the glossary	The glossary structure SHALL follow the established structure of work packages and project tasks, to facilitate the inclusion of terms by the partners.	The terms and representation semantic that are incorporated in the glossary SHALL be included in one of these categories: 1) Ethical, Legal & Societal Aspects. 2) Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responders; 3) Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responders. 4) Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responders	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
TAS	REQ_COM_T2.2_4	Collaborative development of the glossary (Glossary web app)	The collaboration of the partners MUST be through a web application developed by TAS	The collaboration of the partners through the web application MUST be carried out with the assigned user. The partners MAY propose, review, or consult the terms throughout the	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				development of the project. They MAY also propose semantic terms or representations to include in the glossary.			
TAS	REQ_COM_T2.2_5	Documentary reference library of the project	The application developed for the elaboration of the glossary MUST allow the management of documentation.	The reference documentation MUST be managed with the web application developed for the elaboration of the glossary. The referenced documents MUST be uploaded to the web. The documentary source MUST be identified and a characterisation of it MUST be uploaded.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
IND	REQ_BASE_T2.3_1	Overarching Architecture (OA), APIS and Interfaces	VALKYRIES execution SHALL guide the reference implementation of the targeted procedures and technologies by developing their Overarching Architecture (OA) in a modular	The architecture SHALL indicate the dependencies traceability between subsystems, and the communication procedures with the external data sources. The architecture SHALL be based on the Platform	Inspection Test	P1	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			approach. The VALKYRIES OA MUST distinguish the main components and subsystems to be integrated through the project life cycle, taking as a technical baseline the system requirements described in task T2.1.	Independent Model (PIM) paradigm, so that stakeholders and project partners SHALL equally understand it. The PIM SHALL be transformed into a Platform Specific Model (PSM) once its subsystems are identified. Bearing in mind the VALKYRIES OA, T2.3 SHALL define the APIs and interfaces needed for communication between the different modules available within the VALKYRIES platform.			
PARTICLE	REQ_BASE_T2.3_2	Overarching Architecture shall be based on the Platform Independent Model	Establishing the model for the VALKYRIES Overarching Architecture (OA): The Overarching Architecture SHALL be based on the NAF Methodology	The VALKYRIES OA shall identify the key Applications that are included in the SIGRUN Solutions; It shall establish a data model for sharing and integration (Interoperability) of the different applications	Inspection Test	P1	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				based on an application-agnostic model, such as Public-subscribe; The VALKYRIES OA SHALL establish the model for applications interface (APIs) to integrate the different block; The VALKYRIES OA shall provide a model for integration of the USER-INTERFACE of the multiple blocks.			
PARTICLE	REQ_BASE_T2.3_3	Legal, ethics, and data privacy regulations	The VALKYRIES OA SHALL include native capability to implement, assess and verify the traceability of the legal, ethics, and data privacy regulations.	The VALKYRIES OA SHALL include native capability to establish the legal ruling aspects applicable through the chain of the data process, according to the different countries Laws. This implies that the legal frame applicable at each step of the data process chain; Likewise, in case of the post situational assessment, it SHALL provide the	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				conditions for a post-event assessment of the compliancy with the valid legal frame.			
PARTICLE	REQ_BASE_T2.3_4	Interoperability with external data sources	The VALKYRIES OA SHALL support interoperability with external data sources; upgradeability with new standards and harmonisation with current processes and with the frameworks of first responders.	The VALKYRIES OA SHALL establish a model enabling an easy transformation of external or new data sources, regarding to its semantics, terminologies and taxonomy thus supporting the scalability and upgradeability of VALKYRIES solution.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-8
PARTICLE	REQ_BASE_T2.3_5	KARA technologies, HERJA procedures and EIR	The VALKYRIES SHALL support the KARA technologies, the HERJA procedures and the EIR Collaboration between entities established in the proposal and in the deliverables from TASK 2.1 AND TASK 2.2 (To be		Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			reviewed and consolidated later)				
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_1	Key System Components	The OA SHALL support the key components and functions provided by the application identified by the VALKYRIES consortium.	A list of applications and its main components and functions SHALL be collected to establish a reference of elements items to develop the OA.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-8
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_2	OA Data security	The OA SHALL support data protection by design	To ensure the security of the data exchanged between different application, the protocols used shall support private-public encryption key.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-4
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_3	OA Data security	The OA MAY support data trust by design	To ensure the security of the data exchanged between different application, and avoid data tampering, the data generated shall be protected based on Blockchain.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_4	OA data Exchange traceability	The OA SHALL provide data traceability by design	Data exchange between systems shall be able to be traced in case of audit, through Blockchain technology.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-2
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_5	OA data Exchange authorisation	The OA MUST provide trace of data exchanged to the country's authority's authorisation.	The OA model must trace data exchanged between countries to the legal authorisations provided by the authorities of the countries.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_6	OA data lifecycle management	The OA MUST provide data lifecycle management, to manage persistent data, temporary data, condition validity data, etc	The OA model must establish the functions to handle data time validity.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-7
BC2050	REQ_COM_T2.3_7	Blockchain component	A Blockchain layer incorporated in SIGRUN in a non-invasive way.	A Blockchain layer that should operate in parallel with the SIGRUN platform and will handle the secure storing of critical	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				data from various sources.			
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_8	OA Communication security	The information exchanged SHALL be protected against unauthorized user	The messages exchanged between the different devices SHALL only be accessible by the data originator and the intended data consumer.	Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_9	OA Communication resilience	The architecture of the communication MUST provide the means to guarantee a very high availability of the communication resources	<p>The architecture SHALL support multiple and different networks interfacing to ensure redundancy of data paths.</p> <p>It SHALL also provide the data exchange redundancy, by using clustering of data services</p> <p>The architecture also RECOMMENDS the use of</p>	Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				networks architecture that provide improved resilience (Ad-hoc network; DTN networks and SDN networks)			
PARTICLE	EQ_COM_T2.3_10	OA Minimum Functions	The architecture SHALL establish the VALKYRIES services	The architecture SHALL establish and defined the VALKYRIES services responsible for three main functions: 1 - Communications Resources Services, that manages the communications and networks within VALKYRIES; 2 -Data exchange Services, which provides the services to establish the data interchange and common standards between the applications; 3- Valkyries Core services responsible	Test	P1	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				for the orchestration, synchronization and interoperability between the entities and applications.			
PARTICLE	REQ_COM_T2.3_11	Data shared	The Valkyries shall provide the mean to share transactional data, video streaming, data streaming, audio streaming, and files.	The architecture SHALL establish the mean and functions that allows the VALKYRIES applications to share the streaming of data to multiple consumers (video, data stream, etc) as well as other data sources and formats as documents, or files.	Test	P2	all
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T2.4_1	Map of Standards and joint roadmap.	The Map of Standards and joint roadmap SHALL present the analysis and map of the planned and ongoing VALKYRIES related standardisation actions, depicting a joint roadmap of them.	The different steps of the standardisation processes SHOULD be defined to develop a tailored roadmap for VALKYRIES, this SHOULD be an extended action plan, with the necessary details	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				to follow, to develop the VALKYRIES standardisation tasks. A first roadmap draft SHOULD be produced and sent to the partners for consultation. The final document reviewed by Valkyries partners SHOULD be shared internally with all partners and uploaded as Deliverable 2.4.			
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T2.4_2	Pre-definition the improvements to apply in this project	Pre-definition the improvements to apply in this project and SHALL identify opportunities and priorities.	Pre-determine the improvements to apply them in this project. Schedule and prioritise the identified standardisation opportunities. Workshops with partners and the External Advisory Board (EAB) SHOULD be undertaken to prioritise the needs and identified opportunities	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T2.4_3	Develop a sustainable process to improve future standardisation	VALKYRIES SHOULD develop a sustainable process to improve future standardisation	Based on identified needs, gaps and opportunities VALKYRIES SHOULD develop a sustainable process to improve future standardisation. That process provides a common reference point for discussion, evaluate the document specifications, improve interoperability and formalise certification.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.4_1	Identify opportunities for standardisation and implement them	VALKYRIES SHALL identify opportunities for standardisation and will try to implement them	Examine the current state of standardisation VALKYRIES SHALL Identify opportunities for standardisation and implement beyond the work programs of the European, international, and military organisations dedicated to this purpose	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.4_2	Certification about interoperability	VALKYRIES MAY design a possible certification scheme about interoperability	Design a possible future certification, which ensures an agreed cross-border emergency standard, continuous performance, and quality control This certification MAY ensure the interoperability between organisations	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.4_3	Collect and evaluate relevant documentation	Collection and evaluation of legal requirements, protocols, standards. It SHOULD compare the different countries' requirements, standards, and protocols	All partners SHOULD be required to identify every relevant documents, protocols, and legislation that applies to their UC. Evaluation and comparison of the state of the current European's references and documents MUST be undertaken for every use case to identify issues, handicaps, and gaps.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.4_4	Provide a common reference point for discussion	VALKYRIES SHALL provide a common reference point for discussion	A common reference point for discussions between parties about	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				communication, equipment, and resources SHALL be provided to extend the evaluation of the procedures with the integration of the EAB expertise. For this purpose, standardised and tested methods will be used.			VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.4_5	Common guidance for certification and quality control	VALKYRIES MAY create a common guidance for certification and quality control and continuing performance	At the end of the project, VALKYRIES MAY provide a common guidance for certification and quality control and continuing performance SHOULD be formalise d (as evaluation of Indicators, KPI...)	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T2.5_1	Identify and evaluate relevant documentation	VALKYRIES SHOULD define and enforce the harmonisation framework and define of common certification schemes	All partners SHOULD be required to identify all the relevant standards, including requirements, recommendations, and guidelines for interoperable operation, education, technology,	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				and equipment. This set of prioritized standards MUST be evaluated.			
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T2.5_2	Suggest or propose standards	VALKYRIES SHALL explore the feasibility of proposing/recommending legal amendments or new requirements.	Amendments or new developed standards SHALL be made or propose for filling the gaps identified at previous stages. Common procedures and guidelines MUST be developed for interoperable operation, education, technology, and equipment.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T2.5_3	Produce a certification scheme	VALKYRIES SHALL produce a certification scheme in base of the gaps found and embed in the legal framework.	The project MUST produce a certification scheme/s ranging from technologies and procedures up to personnel-related aspects (e.g., competence or accreditations). The definition of common	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				certification schemes MUST be embedded in the existing legal framework and will explore the feasibility of proposing/recommending legal amendments or new requirements.			
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.5_1	Suggest a new standard with common procedures and guidelines	VALKYRIES SHALL suggest a new standard with common procedures and guidelines	VALKYRIES SHALL suggest a new standard with common procedures and guidelines based on: The result of compiling pre-existing standard, identified gaps and UCs evaluation report.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.5_2	Establish new requirements for needs	VALKYRIES MAY establish new requirements for needs	Identify needs in certification schemes (e.g., competence or accreditations) and SUGGEST new requirements for these needs for European level.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.5_3	Gaps and improvements for UC	VALKYRIES SHOULD define gaps and improvements for UC and test them Establish which procedures will be standardised	A tailored Use Cases procedure SHOULD be defined to identify gaps and improvements (from current requirements), all the improvements suggested SHOULD be tested in every use case. Detect needs and establish which procedures will be standardised and by which method. Gaps and improvements for UC	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T2.5_4	Provide a common reference point for discussion	VALKYRIES SHALL provide a common reference point to explore amendments or new requirements	A common reference point for discussions between parties (partners and External Advisory Board (EAB)) about communication, equipment, and resources SHALL be provided to explore a common guidance for proposing/recommending legal amendments or new requirements.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				For this purpose, standardised and tested methods will be used.			

Table 6 - WP2 Requirements

5.3. WP3 - Responsible innovation, certification and exploitation

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.1_1	Identification of relevant ethical, legal, and societal aspects between hard law and soft law	VALKYRIES SHALL aim to identify the hard and soft law regulatory framework relevant to the development of innovative standardisation and certification solutions in the context of the crisis management scenarios addressed by VALKYRIES.	The analysis SHALL cover the current legislative background and security standards landscape in Europe, covering the most relevant EU and national standards, as well as ISO and IEC. This analysis SHALL be conducted through a literature review, including policy documents and reports, along with stakeholders' involvement initiatives.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.2_1	Technical hints based on the existing standards	Standardisation SHALL be implemented to enhance interoperability in the context of the specific crisis management	Based on the existing international standards (e.g., ISO, IEC, OASIS) and European Standards produced by CEN, CENELEC and ETSI. 1. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS to specifically assess the limits and the opportunities	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			scenarios addressed by VALKYRIES.	<p>to the achievement of technical interoperability provided by the EU data protection and intellectual property framework.</p> <p>2. VALKYRIES SHALL provide a common certification scheme and harmonisation framework to improve interoperability among the different cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical stakeholders. This will bring together and enhance existing ones and propose novel solutions to bring up.</p> <p>3. VALKYRIES SHALL study and improve the ability of two or more information and communication technology applications, to accept data from each other and perform a given task in an appropriate and satisfactory manner without</p>			

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				the need for extra operator intervention.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.2_2	Networking, communication, and digital transformation interoperability	Crisis management SHALL imply networking and communication with all the stakeholders and the general public. The interoperability SHALL depict a key factor in making a digital transformation possible.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Digital solutions SHALL be incremental, in a step-by-step approach, as enablers of communication needs, and require training and experiment.2. Legal, organisational, data/semantic, and technical aspects of communication MUST be covered, which only is possible with the active involvement of all actors through the whole capacitation life cycle. [ECC17]	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.2_3	Digital information interoperability and normalisation	The deployment of first aid units SHALL demand specific standardisation actions towards acquiring digital information from victims/public and sending it to the whole C&C system.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. VALKYRIES SHALL cover the gap of standards for patient-management in mass casualty incidents, which shall incorporate new digital opportunities.2. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS studying ways to enhance the ability of digital content to perform all its	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				functionalities in interaction with a concrete digital environment".			
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.2_4	Ethical interoperability	All actions MUST be carried out in compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, national, or local laws. Knowledge and review of the applicable ethical regulations.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. VALKYRIES MUST maintain a constant attitude of respect for the ethical principles that protect people in emergency situations, regarding the request and treatment of necessary and relevant data. VALKYRIES MUST offer a solution that integrates this respect and follows the regulation on the matter.2. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS to specifically assess the limits and the opportunities to the achievement of ethical interoperability provided by the EU data protection and intellectual property framework.3. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS a minimal dataset for patient-management in mass casualty incidents,	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				management of data of affected persons, which shall duly consider privacy issues and personal data equipment.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.2_5	Legal interoperability	Knowledge and review of the applicable legal regulations in cases of disasters or mass casualty incident. All procedures and proceedings MUST be under the regulatory framework of norms and laws of Civil Protection.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. VALKYRIES MUST ensure that all action and carried out under the regulatory frameworks of Civil Protection and its mechanisms in case of disasters or mass casualty incident in cross border frontier.2. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS to specifically assess the limits and the opportunities to the achievement of legal interoperability provided by the EU data protection and intellectual property framework.	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.2_6	Report on the technical, legal, and ethical profiles related to the interoperability of first response capabilities	VALKYRIES project MUST deliver a technical, legal, and ethical interoperability report of the profiles participating in the project.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. VALKYRIES MUST ensure that all the profiles that participate on the project are covered by a report of the technical, legal, and ethical aspects that searches for gaps and opportunities.2. VALKYRIES SHALL cover the gaps regarding interoperability, offer adequate solutions and promote the opportunities encountered.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3
IND	REQ_COM_T3.1_1	Semantic interoperability	VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS promoting the ability to ensure that the precise meaning of exchanged information is unambiguously interpretable by any other system, service, or user.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS ensuring that every situation and its characteristics and effects are given a common semantic designation, as is of great importance for smooth communication.	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T3.2_2	Organisational interoperability	VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS studying the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities, and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals.	1. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS documenting and integrating or aligning business processes and relevant information exchanged. Organisational interoperability also aims to meet the requirements of the user community by making services available, easily identifiable, accessible and user focused.	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8
IND	REQ_COM_T3.3_3	Budgetary interoperability	Due to the budgetary differences of emergency responders VALKYRIES MUST explore ways to ensure that the budget does not block adequate emergency response.	1. VALKYRIES RECOMMENDS documenting and aligning methods to promote a comprehensive emergency response that complies with the budget balance of the intervening actors	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.3_1	Data protection and IP boundaries to improve interoperability and deployment	Taking also into consideration the technical hints from T3.1-2 and inputs emerging, especially	The constraints given by data protection principles on the protection of data subjects SHALL be evaluated in the context of the specific	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			from WPs 4-5, VALKYRIES execution SHALL evaluate the limits and opportunities to achieve in the technical interoperability provided by the European data protection and intellectual property framework.	crisis management scenarios addressed by VALKYRIES. In the same perspective, the barriers under intellectual property law, as the eventual existence of technical protection measures and proprietary formats SHALL be required. Against this backdrop, combined schemes enabling interoperability objectives SHALL be developed, in the form of “fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory” terms, grant back clauses and standards of openness designed explicitly for crisis management technologies, and directly resulting from the combination of traditional IP schemes and data protection principles, in particular the principle of fairness and transparency.			

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T3.4_1	Collection of current standards (ISO, EN)	VALKYRIES MUST collect, analyse current standards (ISO, EN), and identify gaps	VALKYRIES MUST Collect standards related to emergency management (ISO, EN) to produce a map of ISO or EN standards that may be related to emergency management. Those documents MUST be analysed, identifying the gaps and the opportunities, regarding the comprehensive management of actions in the event of a cross-border emergency.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T3.4_2	Collection of current procedures (SOP)	VALKYRIES SHALL aims to identify, collect, and evaluate current procedures (SOP) and produce a map of the operational procedures or every UC.	Standards Operating Procedures (SOP), voluntarily implemented at countries and organisations, MUST be collected and evaluated for the 4 use cases (end users) and produce a map of the operational processes for each of the participants in the 4 use cases, with assigned tasks,	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				the resources used, and the results to be obtained.			
NOVOTEC	REQ_BASE_T3.4_3	Detect harmonisations needs for the SOPs	VALKYRIES SHALL detect harmonisations need for the SOPs and setting up the action criteria and minimum common information necessary.	From the analysis of the gaps and the differences in these processes, the harmonisation needs for the SOPs MUST be detected, setting up the action criteria and the minimum common information necessary to carry out a unified SOP.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_1	Standard of minimum common	VALKYRIES SHALL Build a standard of minimum common to carry out the SOPs.	Build a standard with the minimum common information necessary to carry out the SOPs. Identify gaps with data corrected by organisations to suggest recommendations	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_2	Gaps between standards and partners SOPs	VALKYRIES SHALL identify gaps between standards and partners SOPs	Identify gaps between ISO and EN standard and partners procedures to suggest improvements.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_3	Minimum Common Data (MCD)	Minimum Common Data (MCD) operation phases	The project SHALL provide the minimum data to carry out the operation beyond: (MCDI) and RECOMMENDS (MCDT1), (MCDT2) for example pre-emergency, post emergency and report data.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_4	Workshops with partners and the External Advisory Board (EAB)	Workshops with partners and the External Advisory Board (EAB) to analyse SOPs.	Workshops with partners and the External Advisory Board (EAB) SHOULD be undertaken to analyse the certification and SOPs gaps, opportunities, minimum common information, and opportunities.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_5	Provide a common reference point for discussion	Provide a common reference point for discussion with standardised and test methods	A common reference point for discussions between parties about minimum common information MUST be provided. For this purpose, standardised and tested methods will be used. To define the minimum data necessary to carry out a unified SOP with the	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				integration of the EAB expertise.			
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_6	Explore amendments for harmonisation needs	Explore amendments for harmonisation needs based on previous stages of the project	Based on harmonisation needs identified for the SOPs (evaluation of the operational processes that each of the participants in the Use Cases), and considering existing standards (ISO, EN) SHOULD be explored amendments within a common frame of reference	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
NOVOTEC	REQ_COM_T3.4_7	Minimum Common Data (MCD)	Minimum Common Data (MCD) Incident and Triage	The project MUST provide the minimum data to carry out the operation in relation to: Minimum Incident Data Set (MCDI) And RECOMMENDS MCD Primary Triage (MCDT1) MCD Secondary Triage (MCDT2)	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.5_1	Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse different national European certification initiatives as well as international efforts to identify commonalities and differences.	The analysis SHALL include national, European, and international initiatives, centralized in the EU Certification Frameworks, and highlighting future certification actions derived from the impacts for the digitalisation of the EMS sectors (technologies, procedures, collaboration). The task also covers the accreditations and related attestations, deepening into the gaps on the existing evaluation facilities and tests, as well as their federation and information sharing procedures, aiming to help to plan how they may evolve so the support the latest and forthcoming advances and certification schemes. A specific aim in the evolution plan is to reduce the time from research to certification, as	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				well as enhancing their sustainability (energy efficiency, safety, etc.). Indeed, when developing critical products that have to be certified, this takes a long time and is thus costly. A study on the impact of research and innovation activities on certification SHALL be carried out and SHALL provide recommendations on how the connection could be improved.			
USN	REQ_BASE_T3.5_2	Map of certification initiatives	Certification initiatives SHOULD be mapped for technology, procedures and collaboration in SAR and Emergency Response which is impacted by digitalisation.	Identify certification and standardisation initiatives for mobile systems for SAR and emergency response. Standards of interest are both technical standards regarding products (safety, physical and functional requirements, data transmission and security) and more operational standards of how and what	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				information is presented to different users.			
USN	REQ_BASE_T3.5_3	Map testing procedures and test facilities	VALKYRIES SHALL mapping of testing procedures and test facilities for the products and system groups relevant for the Valkyries project	Define "test procedure" and "test facility" relevant for the different types of emergencies. Practical approach: How and where is new equipment solutions tested (e.g., Oil spill is tested in closed basin). How to test and facilitate localizing, communicating, recovery in disasters. - List testing procedures. - List Test facilities - Map to the product and system groups	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-4
USN	REQ_BASE_T3.5_4	Analyse certification, testing procedures and test facilities	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse certification requirements, test procedures and test facilities to identify gaps and opportunities to reduce time and cost.	List of identified gaps and opportunities. Describe connection between research and innovation activities on certification. Suggestion for how this knowledge can be exploited	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				in the Valkyries user cases and for future development of products and systems.			
USN	REQ_COM_T3.5_1	Arrange meeting with SAR and ER technology users	VALKYRIES SHALL schedule meeting with organisations experienced with testing, qualifying and using new technology for SAR and ER.	This task is part of mapping how new technological solutions are adopted by SAR and ER organisations.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.6_1	Intellectual property rights (IPR) management	The management of IPR topics between the VALKYRIES Consortium SHALL be tracked by the Innovation & IPR Manager (IM).	The respective partners SHALL establish intellectual property at Work Package level. To ensure smooth project execution, partners agree to grant each other royalty-free access rights to their background and foreground IP for executing the project. The Consortium Agreement will define details concerning these rights after the project to background/foreground IP. IPR ownership. Foreground IP shall be owned by the	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				respective Consortium's partners whose employee(s) generated it, or on whose behalf it was generated. Details of the project's legal framework related to the work, IP ownership, access rights for the project duration and other matters of the Consortium's interest will be defined in the Consortium Agreement to be signed by all partners before the project start. In some cases, where joint IPR ownership is envisaged, partners involved will explore the potential for a joint venture.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.6_2	Exploitation Models	The VALKYRIES Consortium SHALL identify any potential exploitation options for consideration thorough the project life cycle	For the possible exploitation of the VALKYRIES project solutions, it is RECOMMENDED to analyse the following exploitation options and models: 1. Open-source licence of complete or partial project	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> results 2. Transaction based charges 3. Mixed models 4. Direct sale of licences 5. User types of models 6. "Give and Take" models 7. Subscription model 8. Pay on deploy model 9. Open Source with ring-fencing 			
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.6_3	Shared Commercialisation Strategy and Plan	That SHALL include a detailed analysis of each customer segment, the specific problem being addressed for each segment, and the quantifiable business value that VALKYRIES will deliver.	A comprehensive go-to-market and financial plan MUST provide confidence for external investors to support VALKYRIES outcomes as suitable for scaling as a standalone commercial venture. It SHALL define a plan for the commercial deployment of the results: which service models will be delivered first, which target end-users will be addressed during the initial stage of the project, which technical parts will be	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				prepared first, etc. Different scenarios will be drafted depending on the amount of investment potentially obtained.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T3.6_4	Novel technologies/equipment to Education/training and new certification opportunities	The key exploitable results of VALKYRIES are standards and the Commercialisation of most of the reference harmonized and integrated solutions, which is RECOMMENDED to be commercialized by some of the exploitation models.	They SHALL range for novel technologies/equipment to Education/training and new certification opportunities. The Consortium will also focus on the exploitation of the key elements of IP that are deemed to have commercial value.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1
IND	REQ_COM_T3.6_1	Innovation meetings	The innovator & IPR Manager SHALL organize emerging opportunities meetings.	The idea consists in project meetings including sessions on emerging technologies/approaches to generate novel ideas for research and to ensure applied knowledge transfer to our industrial partners,	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				and inform future research decisions			
IND	REQ_COM_T3.6_2	IPR validation by EAB	The EAB SHALL be responsible for continuous review of the research progress	The EAB SHALL being provide with reports at 6-month intervals from the CoP, to identify new opportunities for innovation, grow the engagement with our industrial partners, and seek opportunities for new collaborations.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2
IND	REQ_COM_T3.6_3	Commercialisation culture	Commercialisation culture for new opportunities	Commercialisation culture SHALL be worked to maximise the identification, assessment, and execution of opportunities to deliver impact from research outputs.	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2
IND	REQ_COM_T3.6_4	IPR Helpdesk European Commission	It is RECOMMEND in case of any doubt about IPR to use IPR Helpdesk European Commission	The use of the IPR Helpdesk (www.ipr-helpdesk.org) is RECOMMENDED be promoted to help individual participants and partners with questions related to the protection of IPR.	Inspection	N/A	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2

Table 7 - WP3 Requirements

5.4. WP4 - Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.1_1	First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse the technological opportunities for first aid response on self-driving and unmanned vehicles, then revise their related regulatory and normalisation gaps.	Race a roadmap towards an adoption of such technological opportunities, by EU first aid responders SHALL be proposed. A subset of the investigated opportunities SHALL be selected for fitting the end-user requirements of the VALKYRIES reference integration (SIGRUN). Land-based drones (rover) SHALL also be exercised to put into operation in the demonstration use cases (tasks T7.5, T7.6, T7.7 and T7.8), to prove how in disaster scenarios we MAY leverage the exploitation of autonomous units to cover the tasks usually conducted by first aid responder (human) staff. In this context, drones MAY also be used to collect	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				information in all areas included in VALKYRIES.			
USN	REQ_BASE_T4.1_2	Self-driving and unmanned vehicles	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse the technological opportunities for first aid response on self-driving and unmanned vehicles.	Unmanned vehicles can deliver a variety of services to first and responders, the importance is to map what services is wanted by the responders and what services the vehicle systems can provide. And by this make a gap analysis	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
USN	REQ_BASE_T4.1_3	Categorisation of the different systems	VALKYRIES SHALL categorize the different system in accordance with proposed plan for environment	Unmanned vehicles have a primary environment they are designed to operate in (e.g., Air, ground, surface, subsurface.) This Categorisation will be used to compare the systems possibilities with the different regulations in force throughout Europe	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
USN	REQ_BASE_T4.1_4	Type of assistance	VALKYRIES SHALL categorize the different system in accordance with category	All rescue operations consist of several different phases some in sequence and some parallel (surveillance and area clearance, first-responder assistance, command control	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				assistance etc.). The task is to map what type of assistance different unmanned vehicles can give to the different phases and compare this with the regulations in force for rescue operation. The aim is to find gaps between today's regulations and new regulations where unmanned vehicles is a part of it			
USN	REQ_BASE_T4.1_5	Information gathering	VALKYRIES SHALL map the end-users requirements and needs for information, data, and communication in a rescue situation	The first responders have a variety of needs and requirements when it comes to information gathering, - interpretation and - distribution. The end-users' needs will be mapped and compared with the systems possibilities and limitations	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T4.1_6	Information presentation	VALKYRIES SHALL present the information to end-users.	Regardless of the systems services, complexity and use a low-tech flow of information to end-users is of paramount importance. The task will look into the design of decision support system and suggest a	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				common standard for how end-users will send and receive data regardless of language, technological systems available, skills and the environment the first responders are a part of.			
UMU	REQ_BASE_T4.2_1	Trusted communication of end-user terminals with the infrastructure	The growing landscape of trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals to enhance existing EU capabilities for first aid responses MUST be analysed looking for technological opportunities.	The main gaps, challenges and regulatory barriers for their adoption MUST be reviewed, resulting in a set of harmonisation opportunities and a roadmap for integration into the EU Security Market. A subset of the identified technological opportunities SHALL be selected and harmonized to meet requirements of the VALKYRIES reference integration.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T4.2_2	Framework for secure and trusted communications	The framework MUST be capable of communicating in a secure and trusted fashion based on	The designed framework SHOULD consider regulatory gaps, challenges and opportunities aiming to harmonize communication capabilities. It SHOULD	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7,

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			current harmonisation opportunities.	consider currently used communication technologies (e.g., TETRA) and prospecting ones (such as Bluetooth/Wi-Fi/4G/5G) to evaluate harmonisation opportunities.			VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_1	Sufficient communication capabilities between devices	The devices intervening in the solution MUST allow the communication between them to enable operational information sharing.	All devices used REQUIRED have sufficient communication capabilities to share data between them, being able to transmit information to SIGRUN, as well as receiving relevant data from the platform.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_2	Integration with existing communication technologies	The solution MUST be compatible with existing communication technologies widely used in emergency scenarios.	Valkyries SHALL make use of communication technologies commonly used in emergency scenarios to implement the transfer of relevant data.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_3	Optimal network technology selection	The network MUST escalate according to the requirements and technological restrictions in each location.	The network MUST use the best communication technology available, when possible, adapted to the particularities of the data that need to be sent.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_4	Communication availability between devices	The communication systems between devices MUST guarantee the availability of the service for an acceptable percentage of time.	It is RECOMMENDED to use redundant links in the SIGRUN core system. Moreover, it is RECOMMENDED to have access to equipment able to create ad hoc access points in disasters.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_5	Information confidentiality	The information exchanged MUST be confidential between the devices involved in the communication.	The messages exchanged between the different devices SHALL only be accessible by the sender and receiver. For this, it is necessary to cypher these messages.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_6	Ensure data integrity	The integrity of the data exchanged between the various devices MUST be guaranteed.	It is necessary to guarantee the integrity of the data transmitted since a modification of the data could lead the system to make erroneous decisions. It is RECOMMENDED to use hashing techniques with the purpose of detecting alterations in the data.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_7	Data availability	Access to the data obtained MUST be available during most of the time.	It is necessary the accessibility and continuity of data exchange between different devices. The deployed system MAY use backups to store critical data to prevent loss or corruption.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_8	Authentication mechanisms for network access	Each participant and device MUST be authenticated in the system.	All intervening actors deployed MUST be authenticated in the system to access the network and send or receive data. There are different possibilities, such as using a password, a token, or a private key.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_9	Role-based authorisation	Roles MUST be assigned to each of the network actors with certain permissions.	It is necessary to create different roles for each of the network users and devices.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_10	Resources priority based on roles	Resources MUST be prioritized based on the role assigned to each actor.	The system MUST implement optimisation mechanisms and assignation of resources depending on the role of each actor.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_11	Deployment of redundant systems	The platform MUST be resilient when facing a wide variety of issues.	It is essential to deploy redundant systems that can ensure the availability of the system if there is an error. Particularly, it is RECOMMENDED the deployment of backup servers, services, and communication links.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_12	Secure data storage	Data MUST BE stored in the database using cryptographic mechanisms.	Use of encryption techniques to guarantee that the information cannot be accessed by non-authorized parties. Additionally, it is RECOMMENDED the use of techniques to securely store and access the data.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.2_13	Trust scores	The relationship between parties MUST be based on trust scores.	The system MUST implement different trust scores, such as the underlying technology in communications being used or the type of assets.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.2_14	Bridge between different communication technologies	The communication system SHALL provide gateways and connectivity between different communications technologies (5G / Wi-Fi / Bluetooth)	End-User terminals and devices may use local connectivity technologies, like Bluetooth, without network capability. Data channel cross communication technologies shall be supported to enable data integration end-to-end.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.2_15	Manage data priority	Communications layer SHALL enable the definition and use of different priority communications channels	In a congestion and critical scenario, managing the data to be transferred in due time and needed, is a key success for operations. Not all data holds the same criticality level and, therefore, its priority for delivered. to respond to the potential of communications overload and ensure high priority data is delivered, the communications system and networks SHALL provide means to establish data priority communications, levels of services, etc.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.2_16	FAST Deployable networks	The network and communication infrastructure that support the operations SHALL be fast and easily deployable	Short time deployability of the communications and infrastructure is critical for a quick response. The System MUST be able to deploy and initiate critical services in a short time. (Time tbd). If needed the communication services capability are becoming online by phases.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BC2050	REQ_COM_T4.2_17	Data sharing robustness	The integrity of the data exchanged and shared between the various actors MUST be guaranteed.	Blockchain technology SHALL be utilized as a tool to prove the integrity of securely stored critical information.	Test Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.3_1	Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technology improvements	A map of related harmonisation opportunities SHALL be generated and a roadmap for their technological adoption and normalisation SHALL be suggested.	Roadmap SHALL suggest a subset of harmonisation technical opportunities to serve to the VALKYRIES reference integration (SIGRUN).	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.3_2	Preliminary C3ISR analysis	State of the art analysis SHALL be done about the current Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR)	An improvement study SHALL be carried out to find technological improvements to the support systems for the first responders.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.3_3	Recognition of Technological gaps	Main barriers and challenges in the incorporation of these technologies SHALL be detected	It SHALL be identifying the pros and cons about future implementation issues as a part of the reference integration for the adoption and subsequent standardized and harmonic implementation for first responders. Effective Communication Technology	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.3_4	Related harmonisation opportunities Map	Map of related harmonisation opportunities are RECOMMENDED to be generated resulting in guidelines and field notes for supporting further associated actions.	As a preliminary stage of the VALKYRIES project, the large ecosystem of emerging opportunities for enhancing the first aid actuation in disaster situations will be surveyed, analysed and categorized resulting in an ontological map of the existing state-of-the-art and beyond enablers, and the pros/cons of their adoption.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.3_5	Roadmap for their technological adoption and normalisation	Roadmap SHOULD be created to define their technological adoptions to get the major VALKYRIES milestones. Roadmap	VALKYRIES SHOULD bring roadmaps for their mitigation and prompting the adoption of the disruptive solutions on the first aid response markets. VALKYRIES will also bring a	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	roadmap of expertise landscaping and actual trends in the employment of advanced technologies, procedures, and tactics.			
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_1	Real time updating	For mobile Command and Control Applications SHALL updated according to the database.	To avoid logistical faults and optimize the evacuation routes, the application has to update the cartography, assistant vehicles, logistics, alerts status, reporting, etc. Timetable of arrival resources to the incident. Update the current status (latest version)	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_2	Multiplatform	The Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR) platform SHALL run on different operating systems and any type of device.	Linux, MacOS, Windows and Android SHALL run the Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR) platform. Added to the platform layout is desired to be kind of responsive design.	Inspection Test	P2	IVALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_3	Optimisation the electrical and telecommunication resources	The Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR) platform MAY optimize the electrical and telecommunications consumption resources according to the deployment in the advanced control command centre.	Via satellite communication for SOC network coverage	Inspection	P3	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_4	User-friendly C&C app	The Command-and-Control Application SHALL be used by multiple career profiles. The C&C app SHALL easy-to-use software application and MAY provide a user-friendly platform.	With the aim to help first responders accurately input info. Also, to confirm the concluded of any specific step. For example, Decontamination line ready, measurements done, zones established etc.).	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_5	Data synchronisation	Data synchronisation SHALL be possible between the advanced control command centre and the central control command centre.	Mobile Command and Control Application SHALL work autonomously offline in case of losing the communications with the C4 (Main Command and Control Centre Operation).	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_6	Audio Record	The Command-and-Control Application MAY allow record the incidents audios.	To keep the traceability about the incident, the Command-and-Control Application MAY record the audios.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_7	Automatic refresh	The Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR) platform SHALL refresh the system with no need to do manually.	To prevent some information losses, the system SHALL be refresh automatically. Conflict resolution engine (categorize by priorities).	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_8	Agile intercommunication between wearables and C&C	To establish a range of communications the Command-and-Control Application SHALL link with external systems.	Communication between wearables and the Management app to make more effective work with wearables distributed to victims and 1st Interveners.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_9	Sensitive data encryption	To guarantee the security of sensitive data, the Command-and-Control Application SHALL have a data encryption system.	The C&C system SHALL be blockchain-supported, to provide proof of data validity and traceability of information, thus promoting trust and transparency between actors.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_10	Agile intercommunication between C&C units	The Command-and-Control Application MAY communicate over third Command and Control Applications	In terms of communications the Command-and-Control Application it MAY be able to link along third Command and Control additional Applications with another countries.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_11	Sensoristic integration	To manage the catastrophes interventions, first responders MAY take in consideration connect different	Kind of information like hazard materials, gas pollution, temperature, meteorological data, etc. MAY be displayed. To detect and identify the threat in detail.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			sensors and share the measurement results	What is the substance, what is its properties and effects?			
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_12	Confirmation (states)	To guarantee the operational securities, the ACM (Advanced Command Post) SHALL suggest confirmation of all the intervening teams	To confirm the completion of specific states like decontamination line ready, measurements done, zones established, etc.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_13	Search engine (GIS)	To get access into the GIS as fast as possible Search engine MAY be implemented.		Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_14	Historical Data (training)	Storage capacity to record the most relevant information of the incident.	The information stored MAY be used to improve training services, procedures, response time, ... In future catastrophes with multiple casualties	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_15	Automatic translator	The Command-and-Control Application MAY be automatically translated by external translator services		Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_16	Web resources	The Command-and-Control Application MAY connect between external network resources.	The Command-and-Control Application MAY consume network resources such as traffic, weather information, etc.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_17	Critical structures	Critical structures that may be affected by the original causes of major disasters (fire, gases, toxic spills, etc.) MAY be identified.	Oil rigs, Gas platforms, hazard materials warehouses MAY be some of the examples of critical structures	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.3_18	Data analysis	The command & control application SHALL process the data collected.	The data collected SHALL be deployed on dashboards, tables, reports, etc.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.3_19	First Aid Vehicles data	Data originated from First Aid Vehicles, (position, operational status, etc.) SHALL be reported in a continuous basis to	First Aid Vehicles data SHALL be displayed in a dashboard with its status, positions, ETA, etc.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			the multiple actors (Command centre, medical centre, hospitals, etc.)				
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.3_20	Offline data recover	In the absence of critical data freeze due to momentaneous communication fail, the system SHALL support offline storage and automatic resync when connectivity so recovered.	When moving in harsh terrain environment, connectivity may be lost or intermittent. Critical data may still be locally gathered and transmitted automatically when connectivity is re-established.	Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.3_21	Medical Data requests	System SHALL Access to victims electronic Health Records (EHR)	Victims in critical condition may not be able to provide their health information (allergies, blood type, pacemaker, etc.). Therefore, access to existing EHR may be critical to a proper medical assistance; careful attention to privacy data access and usage, and recording.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.3_22	Cross border information sharing	System MUST allow for data originated by one country to be classified, by the originator, as shareable or not shareable.	Due to national constraints and political sensitivity of critical events, national law, etc, it may happen that some of the data generated by one country cannot be freely shared. Therefore, the system MUST provide means to establish which data is shareable or not. And implement the procedures that may require authorisation prior to being shared.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.4_1	Technological timelines	Potential improvements MAY be incorporated considering new technological opportunities for digitisation	In this line, VALKIRYES MAY apply technologies such as modelling and simulation aggregation, BIM modelling and static digitisation, Digital Twin Instance (DTI) and their interrelationship as Digital Twins Aggregated (DTA) and Portable Digital Twins (EDT). In this context, potential contributions of novel technological approaches like introducing social media	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				intelligence to improve the EMS preparedness, taking advantage of AI-based predictive Big Data analytics for guiding anticipatory actions, bringing auxiliary unmanned vehicles and autonomous driving capabilities to the conventional first aid scenarios, exploring the potential of the emerging communication paradigms, digitalisation/virtualisation; inherently demand a review of their linked operational procedures, education, training and cross-sectional collaboration.			
IND	REQ_BASE_T4.4_2	Technological harmonisation opportunities	MUST be identified and assess of the regulatory, certification and standardisation needs and gaps on the existing and emerging technologies for	The requirement SHALL covers the analyses of their technological regulatory and harmonisation gaps, the definition of a potential roadmap for adoption/normalisation, and the application of the VALKYRIES	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			supporting first aid responses.	harmonisation in a subset of them resulting in guidelines for later related actions.			
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_1	Use of AI to suggest evacuation routes	AI MAY suggest evacuation routes to hospitals, approach routes of different devices, lane enabling and adjoining traffic management.	The technological solution may use AI to provide first responders with assistance in finding alternative evacuation routes to hospitals.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
TAS	REQ_COM_T4.4_2	Use of AI to suggest priority of evacuation of victims.	AI MAY suggest, according to the characteristics of the patient, their clinical status, the availability of ambulances and hospital capacities at any time, which patient to evacuate at what time, with which ambulance and to which hospital.		Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_3	Use of AI to provide assistance to the fire fighters.	AI MAY provide assistance to the command by proposing an increase in endowments, change or releases of them, potential affected populations.	Operational capabilities of each fire station in the area for first interventions giving suggestions for intervention (such as nearby air units and their response times to the point).	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
TAS	REQ_COM_T4.4_4	Use of AI to suggest number of EMS vehicles / First responders mobilized.	AI MAY suggest, according to the characteristics of the incident and the impact zone, the available EMS resources, and their distance from the focus, which vehicles / first responders to mobilize.	Additionally, the technology solution MAY use AI to suggest which roles each vehicle/rescuer should assume upon arrival on scene to optimize the chain of care.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_5	BIM modelling and static digitalisation	Graphical tool MAY be added to the final integration. Appropriate processing of the data received MAY improve the existing graphical procedures.	Geographic extension layer Mountain Road plans Covers to paint the relevant information view (Air water discharge points, Situational control of the different endowments, Information about the components of the	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				dots through various sensors, Fire Layer, Multi-screen work capability, Health Posts, Access Control Points, PMA (Advanced Command Post)			
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_6	Digital Twins Instance (DTI)	Digitalisation experts MAY review the technological opportunities for incorporating DTI	A DTI (created from the DTP) is the twin of a physical asset. The DTI stays linked to the physical asset through its lifecycle. The DTI, typically, contains data relating to in-use conditions as captured through the sensors, historical state, predicted state, asset and warranty information, service records, etc.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_7	Digital Twins Aggregated (DTA)	Digitalisation experts MAY review the technological opportunities for incorporating DTA	A DTA is an aggregate of many DTIs. The DTIs may be co-located within one entity. It is well-established a group behaviour is not the sum of individual behaviour.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_8	Portable Digital Twins (EDT)	Digitalisation experts MAY review the technological opportunities for incorporating EDT	Embedded in Virtual Testbeds the Digital Twin becomes an “Experientable Digital Twin” (EDT), in which experiments can be performed and the different outcomes can be compared or evaluated.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_9	Augmented Reality Visualisation	Regarding first aid interventions it MAY be added an Augmented Reality Visualisation Technologies to achieve best results on critical events assisting first responders	Augmented Reality Glasses it MAY provide an extra technological wizard in terms of triage.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_10	VCMS (Victim Case Management System)	Mobile application for triage MAY be able to communicate with Command-and-Control application supporting first responders	To digitalize all the information collected by the wearables, their location, and their current clinical situation	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_11	Wireless communication	It SHALL communicated the data from the VCMS to Command-and-Control Application.	Wireless connection between sensors, wearables devices, VCMS and C&C application.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T4.4_12	Hands free technology	To facilitate the tasks of first responders, it SHALL provide hands free technology.	With the increasing needs for frequent instant communications for first aid, it becomes attractive to create an assistive device to facilitate software interaction. In this paper, we introduce a wearable communicating device featuring hands-free interaction technologies.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6
UMU	REQ_BASE_T4.5_1	Study of opportunities for wearables technologies	Analysis of the state of the art in a categorized manner among the most promising technological alternatives. The analysis SHALL ensure compatibility with the operational environment.	The work to be undertaken in this task MUST be the study and identification of technologies that MAY have a positive impact on this type of device, and which contribute to mapping the operational environment and improve the efficiency of response logistics while supporting the operation of the equipment,	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				aiming to improve human-computer interaction.			
UMU	REQ_BASE_T4.5_2	Analysis of legal terms	Review the legal terms based on the communications and information transmitted between the different technologies. The review SHALL indicate the legal impact at the European level that may occur.	Identification of legal barriers and challenges for the definition of a common and standard adoption framework at the European level.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T4.5_3	Categorisation, selection, and applicability of technologies within the framework	The selection of the most promising technologies SHOULD have a high possibility of applicability in the project and adapting them to the requirements of the deployed environment.	Among all the technologies studied (spatial planning, infrastructure and deployed unit location, logistic planning, search, and rescue, etc.) those that meet the criteria defined in the standardisation framework MUST be selected and adapted as part of the VALKYRIES reference integration, resulting in guidelines and fieldnotes for	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				supporting further harmonisation.			
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_1	Use of wearable devices	The use of portable devices SHALL offer relevant data from their users.	These wearable devices MUST offer relevant biometric information from their users, such as heart rate. These devices MAY locally store the data acquired, transmitted when they have proper connectivity to communicate with the SIGRUN core. Additionally, they MAY also offer geo location of the device to know where their users are.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_2	Data transmission to SIGRUN	The wearable devices MUST be able to send the acquired data to the platform.	The wearables MUST be capable of sending the data acquired from their users to SIGRUN, either stored offline until their have connection or transmitted in real time.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_3	Resistant and portable devices	The devices MUST be portable with reduced weight, while being resistant to the adverse effects of the environment.	The devices SHALL be lightweight so that they are not uncomfortable for patients, as well as resistant to water, shocks, and high and low temperatures. Additionally, it is RECOMMENDED that they are adaptable to all wrist sizes.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_4	Wearables with sufficient autonomy	The wearables MUST have a good battery to support the requirements of an emergency.	These devices MUST operate in adverse scenarios where they cannot be continuously close to an electrical power source. Because of that, they REQUIRE to be autonomous for an adequate amount of time.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_5	Adaptative capabilities	The wearable MUST easily support its change between patients or responders.	After the usage of the device by a patient or first responder, the wearable must be easily restored to start gathering information from a different subject.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_6	Communication range	Devices MUST have sufficient communication range to interconnect with other devices in the environment.	The devices MUST have a comprehensive communication range to interconnect to other nodes that allow sending or receiving information.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_7	Compatibility with different communication technologies	The devices SHALL incorporate several communication interfaces to select the optimal one at any given time.	Devices SHALL incorporate various interfaces with different communication technologies that allow exchanging them depending on the environment.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_8	Easy integration of new functions in the firmware	Device hardware MAY be easily upgradable to add new capabilities or improve the existing ones.	It is RECOMMENDED that the firmware of the device can be easily designed. Furthermore, the application of updates SHOULD be simple.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_9	Geolocation capability	The wearables SHALL obtain their geographical position in short time intervals and transmit it to the receiving node of the network.	The geographic position SHALL be acquired by means of terrestrial positioning technologies such as GNSS or using beacons transmitted over a sufficient distance range to locate the users in	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				emergency areas, among other methods.			VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T4.5_10	Easy configuration of the wearables	The wearables MUST be easy to configure in emergency environments.	The setup of the devices MUST be simple, where first responders should have to include the minimum amount of data possible, implementing most of the configuration in a transparent way.	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T4.5_11	Easy usability of the wearables	The wearables MUST be easy to use in emergency environments (for example, wearing sanitary or safety gloves, in very extreme lighting conditions, etc.)	Viewing, navigating, and entering data through the devices MUST be feasible under the conditions in which the first responder works, easily adaptable to those conditions, and easy to use by first responders easy to use.	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T4.5_12	Monitoring first responders' fatigue	VALKYRIES SHOULD include a tool that monitors first responders' fatigue.	Monitor and alarm in the event of high levels of fatigue so that the practitioner can be changed.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.5_13	Monitor Victims signals	VALKYRIES SHALL include a tool that monitors Victim's signal during the transportation to Hospitals.	Victims' health signals shall be collected by wearables. Also, First Aid Vehicles are equipped with additional victims monitoring tools. The System MAY gather health these signals and, in real-time, share them with the medical coordination and with the assigned Hospital	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.5_14	Wearables automatic connection with First Aid Vehicles	Wearables and First Aid Vehicles SHALL automatically establish a data sharing mechanism when the victims enter the First Aid Vehicle.	When a victim is transported, the wearable shall automatically connect to the First Aid Vehicle and is ready to share the victims' signals once it is authorized to.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
PAR	REQ_COM_T4.5_15	Easy registration of victims	VALKYRIES MAY include a tool for an easy registration of victims' bio data (face / fingerprint, etc.) to a unique identification device, which allows to be tracked and	When victims are in an unconscious state, its identification may not be possible. Nevertheless, it must be registered in the system and followed to ensure it is not loss and, when identification is obtained, it	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			followed, even if the identity is unknown.	can be filled-in into the system			

Table 8 - WP4 Requirements

5.5. WP5 - Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_1	EU operational mass casualty incidents (MCI) procedures analysis	EU operational MCI procedures MUST be analysed	The participants of the consortium, supported by the stakeholders and by the External Advisory Board, MUST research, identify and analyse all common EU operating procedures related to recognition, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters. The analysis of these documents SHOULD be carried out following a previously determined common methodology, based on the outputs of the initial WPs of the project, and focused on favouring the processes of comparison, detection of gaps, harmonisation, and pre-standardisation.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_2	Gaps and opportunities identification	The regulatory and harmonisation Gaps and opportunities SHOULD be identified	The regulatory and harmonisation gaps and the related procedural opportunities for facilitating, guiding, and enhancing the cooperation between actors in the reconnaissance, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disaster, SHOULD be identified, with special focus in the cross-sectorial, cross-hierarchical, and cross-border collaboration.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_3	MCI procedures harmonisation guidelines and recommendations	Harmonisation guidelines and recommendations for MCI procedures MUST be produced.	After analysing EU procedures and identifying gaps and opportunities, project partners MUST elaborate harmonisation guidelines and recommendations for reconnaissance procedures, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_4	MCI Procedures harmonisation	Harmonisation of a subset of MCI procedures MUST be performed.	A harmonisation of a subset of the procedures for reconnaissance, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters MUST be performed, applying the VALKYRIES harmonisation tactics	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_5	Roadmap for EU-level capacitation	A roadmap to harmonize and enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters SHOULD be suggested.	After carrying out the analysis, prioritisation and scheduling of the evolution and adoption of new common practices and procedures for first aid responses on the EU Security Market, a tentative roadmap for the EU-level capacitation regarding harmonisation of the procedures for reconnaissance, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters SOULD be proposed,	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_6	Further related actions proposal	Further related actions for harmonisation SHOULD be recommended.	At the end of task T5.1, recommendation for further related actions related to harmonisation of the procedures for reconnaissance, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters SHOULD be noted.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.1_7	Needs analysis	Collection and analysis of needs related to C2 from the perspective of responders.	Status of methods, procedures, technology, and equipment of selected end-users (project partners) will be described and needs for improvements will be identified.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_1	Crisis management plans	Crisis management plans at the local, regional, or national level, coordination and support plans at the international level MUST be studied and analysed.	The consortium partners MUST research the existence of crisis management plans at the different levels of civil protection authority to analyse the degree of existing planning in response to crisis situations.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_2	Specific emergency services procedures	Emergency services SHOULD have specific action procedures to deal with incidents with multiple victims (disaster medical management plan)	The existence of specific action procedures for the health management of incidents with multiple victims is considered necessary for the response to an emergency to be carried out efficiently. It SHOULD be analysed whether the emergency services at European level and, mainly, those of the countries involved in the uses case have these action procedures.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_3	Health system	Organisational capacities of health systems	The health systems of European countries SHOULD be analysed and studied, emphasizing the Organisational capacities to respond to an incident with multiple victims.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_4	Event notification	Analysis of the event notification process that entails the activation of a response plan to a health crisis	The data of the event necessary to discriminate about the magnitude of the event and the repercussion that it SHALL have at the health level could be studied and analysed	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_5	Criteria for activation of the disaster medical management plan	The criteria that are established for a health management plan to be activated SHOULD be studied and analysed.	The activation of the DMMP and the subsequent notification of the appropriate medical functions should occur almost simultaneously. Notification consists of any process in which the appropriate medical functions and services are informed of a disaster situation that MAY require a response from those notified.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_6	Operational structure in emergency services	The operational structure SHOULD involve the division of tasks, including roles, responsibilities, and authorities, as well as	Coordination SHOULD be guaranteed in the tasks carried out by the emergency services to minimize the mortality and morbidity of the survivors of the disaster.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			the coordination of various medical and non-medical operational assets	The rescue, decontamination, triage, stabilisation, evacuation, and definitive treatment of disaster survivors, carried out by all the operational assets involved, require integration through individual, mono and/or multidisciplinary management or coordination systems. of disasters			
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_7	Response data	Data SHOULD be collected and analysed continuously	Continuous data collection and analysis SHOULD relate to the impact of the disaster and the needs for its management.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_8	Communications	Medical communications and information management	There SHOULD be communication channels that allow the exchange of information between the coordinating bodies and the operational organisations involved in the response. In addition, progress reports should be published at regular intervals, broadcasting appropriate	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				information to the media and the population			
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_9	Health resource management	Inventory of available health resources (human and material)	It SHALL be possible to have an inventory that is updated as incident management progresses, so that resources can be acquired and assigned based on the evaluation of the response to the emergency. It should include personnel, supplies and equipment as well as technical support.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_10	Triage	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse and identify the use of triage for the management of incidents with multiple victims and, if so, the triage method used.	Triage is a management tool meant to achieve the primary objectives of disaster medical management. It seeks to rapidly provide the greatest benefit for the largest number of casualties to minimize mortality, morbidity, and indirect effects within the affected population and to re-establish as soon as possible the routine level of medical care. It also renders the	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				delivery of medical care to an overwhelmed health system into a manageable task.			
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_11	Victim information management	Information collected on the victims treated.	The standardized collection of data on the victims makes it SHOULD analyse the health consequences of a disaster and its management once resolved. Data such as the total number, age group, identification and affiliation of the victim, gender, location, etc.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_12	On-site medical care	Study and analysis of medical care provided to victims of a disaster	Activities at the disaster site include the collection, medical treatment, and transportation of sick/injured survivors. The collection process includes casualty location, primary triage, and retrieval of ill/injured survivors from hazard direct impact areas and transfer to the formal system for evacuation to definitive care. This transfer SHALL involve keeping victims in one or	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				more areas for on-site medical care or direct transfer to health facilities. The medical treatment and transportation process is comprised of: Secondary triage, On-scene treatment and release of minimally ill/injured persons, Advanced stabilisation, distribution, and transportation to health facilities of the most seriously ill/injured survivors			
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_13	Distribution of ill/injured survivors	Effective coordination and communications MUST be critical importance in the distribution of disaster victims.	The distribution of ill/injured survivors MUST be adequate to avoid saturating hospital emergency services and ensure that victims are transferred to the hospital where they can receive definitive treatment for their injuries.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

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TAS	REQ_COM_T5.1_14	Hospital resources utilisation	Use of operating rooms for patients requiring immediate surgery	Current protocols RECOMMEND that only those patients with life-threatening pathology be transferred for surgery. Procedures for managing incidents with multiple victims SHOULD include this nuance in the patient care process	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
AREU	REQ_BASE_T5.2_1	EU logistics and deployment capacities in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters analysis	EU logistics and deployment capacities MUST be analysed.	A study and analysis of existing capacities and lessons learned from pan-European exercises related to first aid and cross-border crises MUST be carried out, to identify gaps and opportunities and in support of preparation of an adequate Organisation of logistics and deployment for the European Emergency Medical Services.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
AREU	REQ_BASE_T5.2_2	Maintenance, logistics and deployment in MCI and disasters guidelines and recommendations	Guidelines and recommendations for maintenance, logistics and deployment in MCI and disasters MUST be produced.	After analysing EU procedures and identifying gaps and opportunities, VALKYRIES MUST develop a tentative roadmap for their fulfilment and advanced recommendations and guidelines in maintenance, logistics and deployment for first aid responders in MCI and disasters.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
AREU	REQ_BASE_T5.2_3	Maintenance, logistics and deployment skills in MCI and disasters	VALKYRIES MAY develop advanced skills in maintenance, logistics and deployment for first aid responders in MCI and disasters.	The skills obtained SHALL be harmonized towards serving the SIGRUN reference integration and tested in multinational, cross-sectorial field and to support the process of harmonisation for first aid responders in case of cross-border and cross-hierarchical disaster situations	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
AREU	REQ_COM_T5.2_1	Realtime Resource	VALKYRIES SHALL develop a web portal (community-share) with the real available response resources on EU.	The skills obtained SHALL be use as a system integration data and testing in multinational, cross-sectoral field and to support the process engagement for first aid responders in case of cross-border and cross-hierarchical disaster situations	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
AREU	REQ_COM_T5.2_2	Typology Categorisation response	Command and Control application SHALL categorize the incidents to deal in agile way the major events.	The skills obtained SHALL be to identify the minimum equipment required and the human resources request	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
AREU	REQ_COM_T5.2_3	Logistics management plans	VALKYRIES SHALL provide a guideline with the logical sequence of activation of resources based on events and dimension event	The guidelines SHALL lead to having an adequate resource management tool for the event to be rescued that is homogeneous and correct	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

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TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_4	Personnel and material for deployment of portable or fixed health posts	In disasters, tents are often needed in which to care for victims. Emergency teams SHALL have the capacity to deploy this type of infrastructure.	The emergency service SHALL have the capacity to deploy portable structures or provide fixed structures in which to assist the victims, guaranteeing their assistance in the appropriate conditions.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_5	First responder relays	It MAY be necessary to relieve the first responders because the emergency drags on over time.	The emergency service SHOULD plan how to relieve their personnel in the event that the emergency continues over time.	Inspection Demonstration	P3	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_6	Extraordinary mobile resource capacity	Capacity of an emergency team to increase its operational resources in case more resources are needed than those available in the ordinary device.	Emergency services SHOULD plan how to increase operational resources if necessary. They may have to replace resources or simply increase them.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_7	Medical material and medicines	It MAY be necessary to supply medical material and medicines to assist victims.	The emergency services SHOULD have planned how they are going to carry out the supply of medical material and medicines that may be necessary to assist the victims of a disaster.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_8	Needs of first responders	It MUST be ensured that the first responders have the basic means necessary to act in the disaster area: fuel, supplies, transportation, rest areas...	Emergency teams MUST plan how to ensure the basic needs of first responders.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_9	Ensure communications	In disasters, a stable communications network may not be possible.	The emergency services MUST have a plan that guarantees the availability of communications at the disaster site. Even establishing temporary networks.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_10	Affiliation of uninjured	Uninjured people affected by a disaster MUST be affiliated and registered.	All the people affected by a disaster MUST be identified, affiliated, and registered, to efficiently manage their needs.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_11	Evacuee assembly points	There MUST be meeting points where people who must be evacuated due to a disaster go.	The meeting points for evacuees MUST be previously established and MUST be known by the possible interested parties.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_12	Shelter for evacuees	Logistical capacity MUST be available to house, if necessary, people affected by the disaster who must be evacuate	MUST be available emergency shelter, necessities and transportation for those affected by evacuation	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

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TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_13	Supply for affected	Those affected by a disaster MAY need essential items	Administrations MUST have the capacity to provide basic needs to people affected by the disaster. For example, clothing, water, basic hygiene products...	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.2_14	Restoration of essential services	Essential services such as electricity, water, telephone... as well as communication routes, can be affected by a disaster.	There MUST be a response plan that allows for the prompt restoration of essential services. This plan must include both the management and the supply of machinery and technical equipment for the rehabilitation and replacement of services.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T5.3_1	Command and Control (C&C) gaps and opportunities identification in mass casualty incidents (MCI) response.	Command and Control (C&C) EU capabilities against mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters MUST be analysed to identify gaps and opportunities.	VALKYRIES MUST explore existing gaps and emerging enablers towards defining an information network that allows emergency commanders to maintain situational awareness and	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

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				obtain relevant information for decision making.			
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T5.3_2	MCI C&C Recommendations	Recommendations for the development, harmonisation, and integration of C&C solutions regarding the MCI and disasters MUST be produced.	VALKYRIES MUST produce recommendations to develop new capabilities, harmonisation and integration regarding C&C, through the work of the experts of the Consortium and the support of the External Advisory Board.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T5.3_3	C&C Capabilities harmonisation	Harmonisation of a subset of C&C capabilities MUST be performed.	A subset of selected capabilities for C&C will be reference integrated at the SIGRUN platform, serving at the project demonstration	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T5.3_1	SOP (Standard Operation Procedures)	User guide for operational decision making. Standardize activities procedures.	It SHALL be configurable depending on kind of incident.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

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IND	REQ_COM_T5.3_2	Command and Control application assets proposal	Assign resources to the incident.	The systems MAY propose several assistance vehicles. The operator MAY take a decision according to the system proposal.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T5.3_3	Incident's Categorisation	The incident MUST be categorized according to the nature of the causative agent, its intensity, and the consequences, to establish an adequate response.		Inspection Test Analysis	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_4	Incident identification and validation	Incident identification and validation MUST be supported by protocols and MAY be supported by tools that facilitate decision-making.	Early warning systems are very important to minimize the time between the occurrence of the incident and the launch of the response.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

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TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_5	Immediate initial response	The initial contingency response MUST be protocolized to favour immediate intervention in the event of an incident.	This initial response MUST subsequently be adapted to the specific characteristics of the incident and the needs generated.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_6	Operative communications	An effective operational communications network MUST be established within incident response planning to ensure communications with teams deployed on scene.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_7	Chain of command on scene	An Incident Command Post MUST be established to ensure command and control on scene.	The main intervention groups present on the scene MUST be represented in this Incident Command Post.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

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TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_8	Initial security actions	The basic actions for the containment of the damage caused by the incident MUST be initiated from the very first moment, to reduce the added risks for those affected and for the first responders.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_9	Zonation for deployment	The incident scene MUST be organized into homogeneous zones according to the level of risk and the operational objectives pursued in each zone.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_10	Emergency Operations Plan activation	Upon confirmation of an incident, a pre-established Emergency Operations Plan MUST be activated to ensure an adequate response.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_11	Emergency response coordination centre	An Emergency Response Coordination Centre MUST be set up, bringing together all those responsible for the disaster command and control centre. This centre MUST have a unified command.	This Centre MUST have adequate means to perform command and control functions, including communications, hardware, and software to facilitate coordination, decision-making, and communications.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_12	Damage assessment	An exhaustive evaluation of the state of the affected infrastructures, industries, and assets SHALL be carried out.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_13	Action strategy definition and planning	An action strategy MUST be defined and planned, based on the provisions of the Emergency Operations Plan and the specific situation caused by the incident.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_14	Resources mobilisation and deployment	The necessary and appropriate resources MUST be mobilized to respond to the emergency.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_15	Information flow managing	The command and control of the disaster response MUST be based on a communication network and on an adequate, effective, and secure flow of information that facilitates informed decision-making and horizontal and vertical coordination.	Effectiveness of the disaster response depends on effective uses of information and knowledge	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_16	Gather and Analyse Data	Tools SHOULD be made available to facilitate effective data collection and processing, as they are essential to the efficiency and effectiveness of disaster	Data collection and data processing are critical in the disaster response. Artificial intelligence solutions SHOULD be very useful.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			relief and response strategies.				VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_17	Situational awareness	The Incident Command MUST be aware of and attentive to what is happening on scene at a particular time, with particular emphasis on the effect of changes in the incident; in effect, know how the incident is evolving.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_18	Continuous response reevaluation	Decisions MUST be continually reviewed, and the effectiveness of actions MUST be monitored to always ensure an appropriate response to the incident.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_19	Track of resources	The Incident Command MUST track and know where first responders and other personal or resources are deployed at any time.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
							VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_20	Logistical support of resources	There SHOULD be an effective system for detection, communication, and provision of logistical needs, which guarantees adequate support for the efficient operation of the resources deployed on the scene.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_21	Reporting	The Incident Command MUST be able to provide a summary of aggregated incident information in easy-to-issue, to transmit and to understand reports.	Providing updates to emergency services, policy makers, or even the public on incident status and response actions SHOULD be regular.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.3_22	Demobilisation	The decision to terminate the emergency response to an incident MUST be based on protocolized criteria and ensure the		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			orderly, safe, and efficient return of emergency resources to their original location and status.				VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.4_1	Common Operational Picture information	Relevant information for the Common Operational Picture (COP) MUST be identified	After researching and analysing the common EU operational procedures related to reconnaissance, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters, they MUST identify and determine relevant information that facilitates operational coordination between cross-sectorial, cross-hierarchy and even cross-border teams.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.4_2	VALKYRIES Common Operational Picture definition	A Common Operational Picture (COP) generation capability MUST be defined for the VALKYRIES project.	Define a capability for VALKYRIES to present a Common Operational Picture that incorporates and contextualizes, in real-time, the key data points and streams from the VALKYRIES data-sharing framework, to	Inspection Test Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				support to the decision-makers in the disaster management.			
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.4_3	VALKYRIES Common Operational Picture Key data and flows	VALKYRIES COP Key data and flows MUST be defined	Establish the key data points and flows that MUST be incorporated and contextualized in real time in the VALKYRIES data exchange framework to support to the decision-makers in the disaster management.	Inspection Test Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.4_4	Alerting and Warning procedures and enablers	EU Alerting and Warning procedures and enablers MUST be identified and analysed.	The participants of the consortium, supported by the stakeholders and by the External Advisory Board, MUST research, identify and analyse the common EU procedures and the enablers to issue alerts and warnings in mass casualty incidents and disasters.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3
TAS	REQ_BASE_T5.4_5	Alerting and warning recommendations and guidelines	Recommendations and guidelines to issue alerts and warnings in disaster situations MUST be produced.	After analysing EU procedures and identifying gaps and opportunities, project partners MUST elaborate recommendations and guidelines to issue alerts	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				and warnings in disaster situations.			VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_1	COP Standard Terms	The terms used in the COP MUST be defined and standardized	It MUST be supported by the efforts to ensure semantic and terminological interoperability developed in task T2.2 of the project.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_2	Multi language	The COP SHALL allow the multi-language option to favour its effectiveness in cross-border areas.	It SHALL be supported by the efforts to ensure semantic and terminological interoperability developed in task T2.2 of the project.	Inspection. Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_3	COP Normalized graphics	The graphic representations and colour codes used in the COP MUST be defined and standardized	It MAY be supported by the efforts to ensure semantic and terminological interoperability developed in task T2.2 of the project.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_4	COP cartography	The mapping used in the COP MUST be updated, adequate and its Visualisation scalable within the scope of the incident.		Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_5	Communication routes	Communication routes MUST be represented updated at the COP.	It MUST indicate the type of route. I CAN point to traffic status incidences in real time	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_6	Meteorological info	Updated and forecast weather conditions (intensity and direction of the wind in the foci(s), weather conditions) SHALL be represented at the COP.	SHALL include alarms about changes in direction or forecast of rain or about other weather conditions	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_7	COP Selective display (layers)	A display MUST ALLOW to select the layers of information wanted to display at any time in the COP	It MUST allow the selection of layers of information to display, isolated or in combination.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_8	COP data flow	The COP MUST always show the updated information.	All the information shown by the COP MUST correspond to the suitable information, from the different sources of information integrated in SIGRUN, with an efficient and secure connectivity, automatic refreshing, etc.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_9	Risk map	The COP SHALL indicate other possible risks around operations (risk map).	It SHALL indicate other potential risks of relevance previously recorded around operations (risk map of the emergency response plan), and it foreseen evolution, in anticipation of possible complications arising from the original incident. It MAY indicate the type of risk by means of an icon/colour code.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_10	Vulnerability	The COP MAY indicate elements of special vulnerability around operations.	IT MAY indicate elements of special vulnerability around operations (identification, location, type, contact), in anticipation of possible complications derived from the original incident. It MAY	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				indicate the type of element by means of an icon/colour code.			
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_11	Map of logistical resources	The COP SHALL indicate logistics resources of interest previously registered around operations.	It SHALL indicate resources of interest previously registered around operations (resources suitable for developing triage or in situ first health care, water or energy supply points, suitable areas for shelter, etc.). It SHALL indicate its basic elements (identification, location, type, contact), in anticipation of possible logistical reinforcement needs. You CAN point to the resource type using an icon/colour code.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_12	Hospitals	The COP SHOULD locate the hospitals of the health system around operations.	It SHOULD identify the basic elements of the hospital (name, location, contact). It MAY indicate the overall capabilities of each hospital (level, critical services). It MAY indicate the updated capacities of the hospital	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				(emergency room, operating room, ICU)			
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_13	Incident (focus)	The COP MUST indicate the location and extent of the focus (impact zone)	It MUST locate the updated impact area, depending on the evolution of the risk and the dynamic elements that condition it.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_14	Emergency Response Plan	The COP SHALL indicate the emergency response plan that has been activated, as well as the declared activation level.	It SHALL include alarms to suggest activation of a certain emergency plan or activation/activation level review.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_15	Victims	The COP MUST indicate the location of the victims in the scenario of operations.	It MUST include the victim's basic information (location, identification, triage level, status). It MUST indicate by means of colour code the level of triage assigned. It MAY locate the victim by geopositioning. It MAY include predefined alarms related to victims, based on assigned triage, status, and evolution time.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_16	EMS Vehicles	The COP MUST indicate the location of emergency vehicles in the operations scenario.	It MUST include basic vehicle information (location, identification, type, status). It SHOULD indicate by icon the type of vehicle. It MAY indicate by colour code the status of the vehicle. It MAY locate the vehicle by geopositioning.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_17	First Responders	The COP MUST indicate the location of the first responders in the operations scenario.	It MUST include the basic information of the first responder (location, service, status). It MUST indicate by icon / colour the emergency service to which it belongs. It MAY include alarms based on default parameters.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_18	Incident commanders	The COP MUST indicate the location of the incident commanders and chiefs.	It MUST include basic command information (location, service, identification, role, contact). It MAY indicate by icon / colour the emergency service and the role.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_19	Facilities deployment	The COP MUST indicate the location of the resources deployed to support the intervention of the emergency medical service on the scene of operations.	It MUST include the basic information of each resource (location, service, identification, role, contact). It MAY indicate by icon / colour the responsible emergency service and the function.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_20	Alert and warning emission criteria	Recommendations MUST be established regarding the criteria for deciding when to issue alarms and warnings in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include predefined mechanisms that, depending on the characteristics and evolution of the incident, facilitate decisions regarding the issuance of alarms and alerts.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_21	Alert and warning content	Recommendations MUST be established in relation to the contents of alarms and warnings issued in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include aids that facilitate the writing of alarms and alerts.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_22	Recipients of alerts and warnings	Recommendations MUST be established in relation to the recipients of alarms and alerts issued in the context of the response to MCI and disasters,	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include aids that facilitate the identification of recipients of alarms and alerts.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_23	institutional enablers	Recommendations MUST be established in relation to the emission of alarms and warnings through the Administration, institutions, and organisations in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include aids that facilitate the issuance of alarms and alerts through Administrations, institutions, and organisations.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_24	Mobile devices	Recommendations MUST be established regarding the emission of alerts and warning through mobile devices in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include tools that facilitate the issuance of alarms and direct alerts to mobile devices (mobile phones, smartphones, tablets, etc.) in each geographical area.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
							VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_25	Conventional fixed telephone network.	Recommendations MUST be established regarding the emission of alerts and alarms through fine telephone networks in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include tools that facilitate the issuance of alarms and alerts through conventional fixed telephony networks in each geographical area.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_26	Social networks	Recommendations MUST be established regarding the issuance of alerts and alarms through social networks in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	The SIGRUN integration solution MAY include tools that facilitate the issuance of alarms and alerts through social networks in each geographical area.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
TAS	REQ_COM_T5.4_27	Loudspeaker and other elementary means to alert and warning.	Recommendations MUST be established regarding the emission of alerts and alarms through public address systems and other elementary resources in		Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			the context of the response to MCI and disasters.				VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_28	Pictures / Video on site	The Command-and-Control Application MAY allow store pictures / video on-place	In terms of analysis, it is RECOMMENDED the gathering of infographic data places on site	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_29	Dashboards	The Command-and-Control Application SHALL generate on-time dashboards.	The operators from Advanced Command Post can be assist by dashboards.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_30	Customizable maps	The Command-and-Control Application MAY interact with graphical tools	The operators from Advanced Command Post can paint on the maps the strategic situations of the Health Posts, Access Control Points, PMA (Advanced Command Post), etc.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_31	Agencies proposal (incident)	The Command-and-Control Application MAY suggest to the operator most relevant agencies for each incident to keep in touch between them.	The operators of Command-and-Control Application MAY have been suggested which agencies are involved according to the location where they are.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_32	Autocomplete (text)	MAY be included an autocomplete feature in which an application predicts the rest of a word a user is typing	In function of the location of the major event the operator COULD add predefined text regarding the type of incident.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_33	Reports	The command-and-control application MAY create automatic reports at any stage of the incident.	To achieve these following points: Time & cost savings, Accessibility, transparency & productivity, Real-time decision-making, Growth & development the Command-and-Control application MAY generate automatic reports.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6
IND	REQ_COM_T5.4_34	Streaming media	The command-and-control application SHALL play back in real time any media content delivered to computers and mobile devices via the internet	To be able to mitigate as much as possible the negative impacts of the catastrophe the C&C app SHALL stream in real time the situation using drones with cameras. Thus, operators at the advanced control command post will be assisted in making decisions in labour-intensive contexts.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6

Table 9 - WP5 Requirements

5.6. WP6 - Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responders

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_BASE_T6.1_1	Data federation	Opportunities for harmonized resource federation.	Explore emerging collaboration opportunities focalized on resource federation and trusted information sharing, revealing their map, regulatory/normalisation gaps and proposing a roadmap for their mitigation. A subset of the opportunities MUST be reference harmonized towards enabling the project reference integration (SIGRUN).	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T6.1_2	Framework for resource federation	VALKYRIES SHALL design a framework supporting the harmonisation and pre-standardisation of cross-sectorial, cross-border, cross-hierarchical resource federation.	Design a framework able to help in the harmonisation and pre-standardisation of resource federation between multiple parties and stakeholders making up the disaster scenario, enabling their cooperation in a secure and trusted fashion as well as emphasizing the demanded collaborative procedures by following a cross-sectorial,	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				cross-border and cross-hierarchical approach.			
UMU	REQ_BASE_T6.1_3	Management of multi-domain data	VALKYRIES SHALL design a framework to harmoniously manage multi-domain data.	The inter-institutional collaboration requirements will be analysed thoroughly, adapting the resource federation framework with the interoperability harmonized abilities to handle the multi-domain scenario being explored in VALKYRIES.	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T6.1_1	Use of cross-domain data federation protocols	The solution MUST use mechanisms able to share cross-sectorial, cross-border and cross-hierarchical information	Federation of information MUST be considered when sharing information between different domains.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T6.1_2	Single sign-on (SSO)	Authentication processes MUST be easy to manage in emergency scenarios.	To improve the management of authentication, it is RECOMMENDED the use of Single Sign-On (SSO) to log in the system just once, keeping the session active during the emergency.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T6.1_3	Definition and deployment of trust domains	Devices and entities in the communication architecture MUST trust each other.	The endpoints of the architecture MUST rely on a trust relationship.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T6.1_4	Normalisation of data exchanges	The system MUST unify the methods for data exchange in cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical domains.	SIGRUN MUST offer a transparent approach considering the particularities of each country in terms of operational capabilities and regulations.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T6.1_5	Cooperation in secure and trusted environments	The different actors using the platform MUST have mechanisms to communicate in a secure and trusted way.	SIGRUN MUST guarantee a secure communication between domains having a trust relationship, such as countries collaborating in a common emergency.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_BASE_T6.2_1	Education and Training for first aid response	A goal of VALKYRIES is to plan, organize and implement thorough study and analysis of the existing capabilities, debriefing principles for first aid relate to pan-European exercises and cross-border crises supported by recent technological and procedural tools (hyper-realistic simulations, learning analytics, shared lessons learned, etc.) in support of preparation of a framework for joint education and training for the European Emergency Medical Services.	VALKYRIES SHALL develop an advanced education and training kit, including curricula, education methodology and training materials, for first aid responders. The education and training kit SHALL be tested against multinational, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical audience to support the process of interoperability building and capabilities harmonisation for first aid responders in case of cross-border and cross-hierarchical disaster situations. Besides these reference harmonized solutions, the conducted research SHALL deliver a map of the related opportunities, the analysis of their regulatory/normalisation gaps, and a roadmap for their mitigation.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BDI	REQ_BASE_T6.2_2	Study and analysis of the existing capabilities.	A study and analysis of the existing capabilities regarding education and training for first aid response in the EU MUST be performed.	It MAY be focused on the countries involved in the use cases, the research will deliver a map of the related opportunities, the analysis of their regulatory/normalisation gaps, and a roadmap for their mitigation.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
BDI	REQ_BASE_T6.2_3	Developing of an advanced education and training kit.	An advanced education and training kit SHOULD be developed, including curricula, education methodology and training materials for first aid responders.	To facilitate the preparation of a framework for joint education and training for the European Emergency Medical Services. It SHOULD be supported by recent technological and procedural tools (hyper-realistic simulations, learning analytics, shared lessons learned, etc.)	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
BDI	REQ_BASE_T6.2_4	Testing of a subset of proposed recommendations against multinational, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical use cases.	A subset of proposed recommendations MUST be tested against multinational, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical use cases.	To test the effectiveness of the proposed recommendations applied to specific aspects of the fist responders' tasks.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BDI	REQ_COM_T6.2_1	Education and Training for first aid response	VALKYTIES SHALL define the levels of needed education and training for first aid responders according to the emergency situations described in the use cases.		Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7
BDI	REQ_COM_T6.2_2	Study and analysis of the existing capabilities	The VALKYRIES team MUST study existing education and training (E&T) programmes such as the programmes of the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy, the Bulgarian Red Cross, as well as the E&T programmes of the partners in the consortium.		Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7
BDI	REQ_COM_T6.2_3	Developing of an advanced education and training kit	Based on the analysis of the existing E&T programmes and the requirements, the VALKYRIES team MUST suggest education and training kit to be used by		Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			the first aid responders. The E&T kit MAY cover knowledge and skills for measurement and registration of physiological indicators; performing medical manipulations; assessment of the condition and vital functions of the patients and victims; emergencies requiring immediate first aid and behavioural algorithms; evacuation of a victim from a dangerous area or place of an accident; behaviour and activities in crisis and disaster situations.				
BDI	REQ_COM_T6.2_4	Testing of a subset of proposed recommendations against multinational, cross-sectorial and	The developed under WP6 education and training kit for the first aid responders MAY be tested during the WP7		Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
		cross-hierarchical use cases	international and multiagency exercises.				
IND	REQ_COM_T6.2_5	Theoretical and practical course on triage application (VCMS)	Training courses MAY be developed to familiarize first aid responders with the triage tool (VCMS).		Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T6.3_1	Map of opportunities for raising the public and practitioner awareness at disaster management situations	Aim: develop a model for social awareness and public consciousness and responsibility for getting actives in the event of a disaster and share the responsibility for recovery of public order and providing support to most affected from the extraordinary event	Draft a list of events and actions for raising practitioner awareness resulting on list of suitable ones. Study models for social awareness and public consciousness and responsibility for getting activities in the event of a disaster and share the responsibility for recovery of public order and providing support to most affected from the extraordinary event	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.3_1	Working framework scaling the targeted group	VALKYRIES SHALL define a working framework scaling the targeted groups, interests, preparedness, communication models, etc.	Make a list of target groups, define roles of the target groups, competences profiles, define roles in the cycle of DRM	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.3_2	Attract public awareness	VALKYRIES SHALL develop a framework on how to attract public awareness	Develop a communication framework however make to know what exactly will be promoted to the general public. ISEMI proposes to develop two types of communication frameworks for actors addressed / outreached and for the general public.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.3_3	Attract first responders	VALKYRIES SHALL develop a roadmap how to attract first responders, DRM policymakers and experts	Develop a roadmap for involvement of the policymakers and first responders. Draft a list of basic activities, including information and topics for facilitating of the target groups	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.3_4	Models and measures for leadership crisis communication	VALKYRIES SHALL propose models and measures for leadership crisis communication in the phase of prevention, preparedness, reaction, and recovery	leadership crisis communication: Our understanding is that the awareness about crisis communication shall focus on the crisis managers is crucial to understanding crisis communication strategies, as they are responsible for most preparatory, mitigation, response and recovery	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				activities and are considered experts from their communities. Although some question their role in crisis communication and their decision-making power at the local level, their expertise is crucial to understanding the use of crisis communication strategies and integrating the knowledge and needs of the local community and extraordinary events-based adaptation. In addition, crisis managers are encouraged to work to ensure that the collection, organisation, and dissemination of information leads to open, honest, accurate, tailored, two-way and knowledgeable information.			

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.3_5	Analyse the gaps in crisis communication	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse the gaps in crisis communication and propose a list of best practices	Define type of communication - communication to the public/media or communication during or during the disaster development. One SHALL be linked to leadership crisis communication and the other to the standard operational procedures.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.3_6	Distribute good practices into groups	VALKYRIES SHALL distribute good practices into groups – use of technology, use of crowdsourcing, use of crowd-mapping, use of tactical communication, use of volunteers, etc.	Draft a compendium of good practices, distribution, newsletter, short video material to outline critical and essential good practices	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-7
BDI	REQ_BASE_T6.4_1	Civil-Military Cooperation	VALKYRIES SHALL explore the role of CIMIC (civil-military cooperation), particularly in the case of large-scale cross-border disasters with mass casualties as a key	The Consortium SHALL analyse lessons learned from previous operations and SHALL identify main interoperability gaps among different actors engaged in managing crises. Besides, as a result of this VALKYRIES requirement implementation (REQ-BASE-	Inspection	P1	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			factor for successful crisis management.	T6.4), the Consortium SHALL suggest improvements in doctrinal/procedural, operational and tactical documents, and instruments for civil-military collaboration. State of the art and growing opportunities on CIMIC SHALL be mapped and analysed, revealing regulatory/normalisation needs and suggesting a tentative EU-level roadmap for their mitigation. A subset of the identified opportunities SHALL be selected and harmonized towards serving the SIGRUN reference integration, including doctrinal/protocols amendments, extensions, etc., and/or supportive tools. Their effectiveness on the validations, verifications and demonstrations SHALL result in guidelines and recommendations for further related actions.			

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BDI	REQ_COM_T6.4_1	Civil-Military Cooperation	VALKYRIES SHALL define the role, tasks and supporting capacity of CIMIC personnel in case of catastrophic and complex emergency situations.	CIMIC personnel have a crucial role and can work effectively in a field of catastrophic and complex emergencies enhancing the cooperation between different first aid responders. CIMIC specialists and teams will support local authorities, public safety services and volunteers for relief work in case of disaster and events or series of events caused by natural phenomena, incidents, accidents, or other extraordinary circumstances. Military and especially CIMIC teams can enhanced and supplement the efforts of the firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection authorities, NGOs, and others to use special forces and special resources	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BDI	REQ_COM_T6.4_2	Civil-Military Cooperation	VALKYRIES SHALL identify areas of mutual interest between military and other participants around disasters and to define some steps, procedures, and requirements to achieve in a better way goal in case of such complex situation	The CIMIC personnel have to concentrate and perform: Overview of the contingency planning process; Joint Emergency Planning of CIMIC activities together with civil representatives; Some requirements for Interaction of the efforts and coordination of the activities with civilian participants and local authorities during the operation in the emergency zone; Joint military-civilian teams can respond effectively in such events or series of events if some procedures and doctrinal documents are available; Joint TTPs should be developed and validated for the operation and interaction between military and civilian response teams at the operational and tactical levels; A list of proposals for doctrinal amendments, operational manuals and TTPs shall be	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				development, as a supportive tool for harmonizing the efforts, mechanisms, procedures and recourses by all EU countries in order to minimize damages and increasing resilience In highly dynamic emergencies.			
TAS	REQ_COM_T6.4_3	Synergies in training	Opportunities for cross-training between professionals from civil and military institutions SHOULD be analysed, for the mutual acquisition or updating of skills.	The daily activity of civil emergency services can provide military personnel with the opportunity to keep their professional skills up to date for their future military operations. Similarly, the complex logistical and operational capabilities and expertise of the armed forces can facilitate high-level training for civilian professionals.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T6.5_1	Map of opportunities for cross-sectorial cooperation. Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism	VALKYRIES SHOULD review of related opportunities	VALKYRIES SHOULD develop a roadmap: list measures and forms of cooperation in the DRR+DRM cycle Gap analyses – develop a framework and identify gaps in each country	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				Develop an ontology of SOP involving volunteers, local multipliers, and policymakers in the reaction phase Propose measures for involvement of local actors			
TAS	REQ_COM_T6.5_1	EU civil protection and aid voluntarism map	Existing national and international organisations in EU countries in the field of civil protection and disaster response SHOULD be studied.	It SHOULD provide a framework for profiling of the NGOS and volunteers' organisations as well as the other institutions involved in the DRM (Public/NGO/private)	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.5_2	Capabilities	VALKYRIES SHOULD deliver of analyses of the capacities and competences.	It SHOULD provide a comprehensive compendium of competences/capacities and skills required by each actor. We will follow the staff division into four categories (basic [support volunteer support units), technical intervention, strategic and leadership actors/staff, and decision-makers. Capacities and competencies will be analysed as per unified competence framework. Further, based on	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				the comparative analyses from various countries, we will establish the minimum requirements in terms of service resources and preparation of the volunteers.			
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.5_3	Operability	Profile the territory and availability of a centralized mechanism for registration and activation of voluntary institutions in the form of a rapid response in the event of a disaster.	VALKYRIES SHOULD develop a roadmap: list measures and forms of cooperation in the DRR+DRM cycle Gap analyses – develop a framework and identify gaps in each country	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T6.5_4	Integrability	VALKYRIES SHOULD analyse the existence of operational procedures that can be integrated with those of the professional emergency services, guaranteeing greater joint efficiency.	Develop an ontology of SOP involving volunteers, local multipliers and policymakers in the reaction phase	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Table 10 - WP6 Requirements

5.7. WP7 - Reference Integration, Evaluation and Demonstration

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
KEM	REQ_BASE_T7.1_1	Use case requirements for testbeds	VALKYRIES SHALL deploy requirements of the demonstration use cases	This subtask aims to identify and further analyse the deployment requirements of all 4 demonstration use cases	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
KEM	REQ_BASE_T7.1_2	Testbed design	VALKYRIES SHALL design of the testbed	Based on the output of subtask T7.1_1, subtask T7.1_2 aims to complete the architecture of the testbed	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-8
KEM	REQ_BASE_T7.1_3	Existing services identification	VALKYRIES SHALL check of already existing relevant services	Checking of already existing services (subsystems, tools, and methods) (such as INDRA's iSAFETY platform, INDRA's Cyber Range, SYECON 3D, INDRA's Tactical Environment etc.) for compliance with pre-defined specifications	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-4,

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				for integration in the testbed			
KEM	REQ_BASE_T7.1_4	Services integration	VALKYRIES SHALL integrate testbed services	Integration of selected existing services in the testbed	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
KEM	REQ_BASE_T7.1_5	Evaluation methodology	VALKYRIES SHALL develop of an evaluation methodology	Development of a methodology for the end-user validation of the effectiveness of the standardized first aid response procedures and actions that will be tested through the testbed and for the technical verification of the modules and services to be integrated in the system.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T7.2_1	Study datasets to create a Valkyries-compatible model	Existing datasets MUST be analysed to create a model to support the implementation of the SIGRUN reference framework.	Study already existing datasets to ease the harmonisation actions that will support the SIGRUN platform.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_BASE_T7.2_2	Generate rich datasets	The datasets studied MUST include relevant data coming from different sources.	Generation of datasets with data from different perspectives serving as a reference for the SIGRUN framework.	Analysis	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T7.2_3	Obtain information from virtual sensors	It is RECOMMENDED that models can be integrated with data from existing virtual simulations.	The system MUST generate observations collected from cyber sensors, physical sensors and operational logs when synthetically injecting on sandboxes kinetic scenarios or simulations variations that MAY lead to conduct operational decisions. The Consortium background RECOMMENDED a set of COTS enablers for their feasible simulation (e.g., Indra's Tactical Environment, SYECON 3D, etc.)	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_BASE_T7.2_4	Inclusion of the minimum data set to the dataset	The dataset MUST include the minimum data set containing data relevant to the scenario.	The dataset MUST contain the minimum data set, which includes relevant information for the training of the models. These generated data serve for the prediction of situations previously unknown to the models.	Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T7.2_5	Analyse the dataset and extract more relevant features	It is REQUIRED to study the most relevant patterns of the captured data to obtain the most relevant characteristics.	Analysis of the gathered dataset, which SHALL serve to extract the most relevant and discriminating features for ML-based techniques.	Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_BASE_T7.2_6	Comparison of the outcomes with the state-of-the-art	It is RECOMMENDABLE to compare the datasets obtained with those already existing in the literature.	It is intended to publish the datasets produced by the project, also conducting a comparison of state-of-the-art solutions based on the developed dataset.	Analysis	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_1	Models integrating data from multiple sources	It is REQUIRED to create models allowing the optimisation of decision based on the data obtained from multiple sources.	The SIGRUN system MUST unify the different data into one or more intelligent models offering support for the decision-making process during an emergency.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_2	Models for optimizing patients care	The models MUST be capable of identifying the best decisions to treat subjects belonging to the multiple-victim emergency.	Use of artificial intelligence techniques to classify and sort subjects according to the health conditions they manifest. In this way, the system MUST guarantee treatment optimisation, increasing efficiency.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_3	Models for recognition of the patients' state	Models MUST be obtained for the detection of patients' status by analysing the various bio signals of the patients.	Models are needed to identify the severity of the state by measuring different bio signals to obtain a label representing a certain state.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_4	Reinforcement learning	The existing models MAY be able to acquire new intelligence from new data coming from past experiences.	The use of reinforcement learning is RECOMMENDED to increase the knowledge and capabilities of the trained models, providing new inputs to improve their predictions. For that, it is essential to provide data from past experiences, such as previous emergency situations or simulations.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_5	Datasets to train the models	Already existing datasets from emergency situations MUST be used to train the intelligent models.	Datasets MUST be obtained from previous simulations, and other relevant data sources to train the different models and improve the existing ones. These datasets SHOULD contain data from heterogeneous sources to generate rich models. The use of Big Data	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				techniques MAY be useful to manage large scale data.			
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_6	Integration with existing software for simulations	The models trained SHOULD allow their integration with external software offering simulations to test and improve their performance.	The integration of these models with external software would allow to test their performance easily and efficiently, and therefore refine them before their application in real-life emergency scenarios.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_7	Obtain the most relevant features	The system MAY identify the most relevant and least correlated features in the acquired data.	The system needs to be able to acquire the most relevant patterns from the data to train the learning models efficiently. This would ensure shorter training times and prevent overfitting and underfitting.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
UMU	REQ_COM_T7.2_8	Efficient labelling	The system MAY guarantee an efficient labelling of the data, adapting itself depending on the objective to be addressed.	The labelling mechanisms have to provide a range of operation depending on the classification process used, differentiating between different approaches such as binary or multi-classification models.	Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_BASE_T7.3_1	Reference Integration and harmonisations	VALKYRIES requirement REQ-BASE-T7.3 includes all the activities and efforts related to the reference integration and harmonisation.	VALKYRIES SHALL achieve a functional framework resulting from the integration of all these elements in an unified SIGRUN interoperable platform able to properly operate on real first-aid response exercises; being deployed at the project demonstration scenarios.	Demonstration	P1	All

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_2	Integration Plan	Audit of the Integration Plan	Check of the simple plan of the foreseen integration activities; it SHALL be consistent, logical, containing no gaps etc.	Inspect	P1	All
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_3	SIGRUN components output format	Audit of the format of the outputs of the SIGRUN components	Detailed testing of the accordance of the outputs of the different SIGRUN components which SHALL comply with the relevant standards, giving countable results in KPIs form.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_4	SIGRUN components input format	Audit of the format of the inputs of the SIGRUN components	Detailed testing of the accordance of the inputs of the different SIGRUN components which SHALL comply with the relevant standards, giving countable results in KPIs form.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_5	Seamless operation of SIGRUN	Audit of the conservation of seamless operation of SIGRUN	Detailed testing of the execution time and synchronisation of the procedures of the different components of SIGRUN which SHALL be found in between acceptable limits for the seamless operation of SIGRUN, giving countable results in KPIs form.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_6	SIGRUN's Layered architecture	Systematic review of SIGRUN's Layered architecture	Level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the envisioned Layered architecture.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_7	SIGRUN's Extensibility	Systematic review of SIGRUN'S Extensibility	Level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the envisioned Extensibility.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_8	SIGRUN'S Expandability	Systematic review of SIGRUN'S Expandability	Level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the envisioned Expandability	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_9	SIGRUN's Interoperability	Systematic review of SIGRUN's Interoperability	Level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the envisioned Interoperability	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_10	SIGRUN's Multi-level scalability	Systematic review of SIGRUN's Multi-level scalability	Level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the envisioned multi-level scalability.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_11	SIGRUN's privacy & data protection	Systematic review of privacy and data protection	Level of accordance of the integrated system (SIGRUN) which SHALL comply with the EU privacy and data protection standards.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_12	SIGRUN's cybersecurity framework	Systematic review of SIGRUN's cybersecurity framework	Level of robustness of SIGRUN in terms of (cyber)security against threats which SHALL comply with the relevant EU standards like Cybersecurity Act etc.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
ARA	REQ_BASE_T7.3_13	Overall Reference Integration and harmonisation evaluation	This task SHALL contain a collection of previous outcomes of the above activities of T7.3 towards the final evaluation of the integration	This task SHALL contain a collection of previous outcomes of the above activities of T7.3 towards the final evaluation of the integration.	Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
IND	REQ_BASE_T7.4_1	Reference evaluation and demonstration framework	This task SHOULD enclose all the activities related to testing the components, modules, interfaces, procedures, etc., reference integrated as well as their interoperability, normalisation, and harmonisation to support first aid responses on disaster scenarios.	It SHOULD covers the evaluation of the VALKYRIES reference architecture, with integration tests and system validations. Functional, modular, inter-modular, scalability and security tests SHALL be executed on the testbed developed and	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				integrated in the adapted virtual labs and testbeds (T7.1).			
IND	REQ_BASE_T7.4_2	System Validation and Evaluation	It SHALL describes the effectiveness of the VALKYRIES outcomes according to the validation and evaluation methodology	The validation and evaluation of integrations for use case demonstration and their outcomes SHALL be performed, including a broad study based on the expectations and null/alternative hypothesis, and the impact of the massive cross-border demonstrations in both the attending stakeholders	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T7.4_1	Preliminary drills	Set KPIs for small-scale test trials. To gathered as much information as possible it MAY be useful test VALKYRIES by Preliminary drills.	Before the final pilot run, a series of smaller scale evaluation and validation tests will be carried out to validate the KPIs.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T7.4_2	Evaluation and Verification of the drill's organisation	It is RECOMMENDED to evaluate the Organisation of the drill to capture lessons for futures exercises and the performance of specific operation or functions being tested.	The evaluation of the drill SHOULD broadly addresses the aspect of the overall respond system or capacities being tested.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T7.4_3	C&C App Evaluation and Validation	It SHALL be executed Evaluation and Verification tests for proving the correct operation of the Command-and-Control Application.	The application SHALL be guaranteed by Evaluation and Verification tests. The C&C App SHALL works uninterruptedly.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T7.4_4	VCMS (Victim Case Management System) Evaluation and Validation	It MAY be executed Evaluation and Verification tests for proving the correct operation of the VCMS (Victim Case Management System)	The application MAY be guaranteed by Evaluation and Verification tests. It MAY be proven that the first aid team can work at any time, achieving technological independence even in the presence of adverse situations.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
IND	REQ_COM_T7.4_5	Agile system of communications between the different stakeholders	It is RECOMMENDED execute Evaluation and Verification tests for proving the agile communications between the different stakeholders.	The communication systems between participants are RECOMMENDED to be evaluated and validated by means of quantitative identifiers.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-9
IND	REQ_COM_T7.4_6	Evaluation and Verifications of the activities from the Action plan	The performance of the activities described in the action plan SHOULD be evaluated and validated.	We SHOULD ensure that all the activities described in the action plan will be completed.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-9
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_1	Minimum operation of the operating system in adverse situations	The basic operation of the system MUST be guaranteed regardless of the geographical or technological characteristics of the incident site.	It is RECOMMENDED to agree on the minimum data set to be collected according to the capacity of the operating system and the capacity to transmit data in adverse scenarios such as high mountains, sea, or places of scarce mobile coverage such as Subway, caves, etc. It is RECOMMENDED to establish different levels	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				of data collection according to the technological possibilities existing due to the nature of the incident or the terrain.			
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_2	Agreements signed between the countries involved	All actions and procedures MUST consider current legislation and respect the agreements signed between the countries.	<p>The planning and management of the drills SHOULD consider all the agreements signed between the countries involved including the action protocols of civil protection, local emergency services and the legislation in force in the management of mass casualty incident.</p> <p>It is RECOMMENDED to review the legislative framework governing actions of mass casualty incident that includes, among others, the agreements signed</p>	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				between countries, agreements, and protocols of action of European Civil Protection and current legislation. In this way, each action and procedure of the project MUST respect these regulations			
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_3	Ethical principles and standards of good practice	It MUST consider, like other research projects, the standards of good practices in research such as Reliability, Honesty, Respect, Accessibility and Ethics among other items.	VALKYRIES like any other research project MUST respect the basic research standards agreed at European level. These standards will be integrated, from the beginning, in every step and process of data collection, deposit, analysis.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-8
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_4	Minimum legal and safety requirements for the planning, management,	The planning, management and execution of drills MUST consider the various legal and safety aspects of each phase of the process.	It SHOULD consider the different legal and security aspects such as securing people and property, obtaining	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
		and execution of the drills		permits and licenses among others. It is RECOMMENDED to create a list with the minimum legal and safety requirements for the planning, management, and execution of the drills. The planning of the drill MUST consider the deadlines for obtaining the permits and other items included in the minimum legal and safety list.			
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_5	Evaluation of the Organisation of the drill	It is RECOMMENDED to evaluate the drill. Evaluation is a key part of the pre-exercise planning phase.	The evaluation of the drill broadly addresses the aspect of the overall respond system or capacities being tested. We SHOULD define our strategy for reporting or measuring achievement of each of the exercise's	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-10

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				objectives according to guidelines and recommendation.			
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_6	Efficient management of economic and financial resources.	Adequate funding SHOULD be provided for the provision and supply of all the necessary elements for the execution of the drill.	The evaluation, approval, and acquisition of different services, supplies and materials necessary for the execution of the drill are fundamental aspects when optimizing the financial management of the drill between Spain and Portugal. Different aspects of financial management of the drill should be considered. Aspects such as the total budget of the drill and the approval and acquisition of services, supplies and materials necessary to ensure proper planning, management, and execution of the exercise.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
SERMAS	REQ_BASE_T7.5_7	Action plan	An action plan is RECOMMENDED for each of the stakeholders involved in the planning, management, and execution of the drill.	<p>An action plan is RECOMMENDED for each stakeholder group in the drill to serve as an executive frame of reference for their entrusted tasks.</p> <p>It is RECOMMENDED to consider the international guidelines for drill management to plan, manage and execute the drill between Spain and Portugal. An action plan based on the WHO guide is RECOMMENDED as an executive framework for the actions and evaluations of the drill between Spain and Portugal</p>	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_1	Testing on a smaller scale	It would be RECOMMENDED that the operating system has been tested, in small drills, prior to the drill between Spain and Portugal to check and test its operation.	It would be ADVISABLE to use the VALKYRIA operating system in the usual drills carried out by the first participants involved in the Spain and Portugal drill. The objective of these drills, on a smaller scale, would be to check the suitability of the training, usefulness, and usability of the system among other parameters, to improve the system before the drill.	Inspection Test Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-1
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_2	Common system evaluation methodology	The harmonisation and standardisation of the training and simulation of the first responders would be RECOMMENDED.	It is RECOMMENDED to agree on a common style of training and simulation that includes the most important items to consider optimizing the understanding of the tasks assigned to each interest group.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				It is RECOMMENDED to validate its effectiveness in smaller-scale drills before the main drill between Spain and Portugal.			
SESRMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_3	Autonomous work without interruptions	The first responders SHOULD be able to work autonomously and expediently in the first line of multiple incident victims.	The application SHOULD guarantee, always, the technological independence of the first responders in such a way that each team can fluidly collect the essential information for an adequate and agile management of the incident.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_4	Agile system of communications between the different stakeholders	The need to have a telecommunications system that guarantees the correct and agile communication between the different interest groups and the organizers of the drill SHOULD BE considered.	The planning, management and execution of the drill MUST consider the correct and agile communication between the different stakeholders to ensure its correct development.	Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				Different stakeholders such as first responders, directors, coordinators, politicians, and the press among others must receive truthful and agile information in real time.			
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_5	Application for the management of incidents	It is RECOMMENDED to have an app capable of collecting and managing all the data collected from the different means of transmission of information.	The app MUST have the multilayer management capacity to meet the operational needs of the participants, have different management profiles. The app is configured with management alarms for greater effectiveness in decisions such as number of resources, number of optimal resources, fatigue of the interveners, etc. The app can communicate with the different vinculated	Inspection Test Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-5

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				<p>devices for management deployed in the field to collect data for mission management</p> <p>The app can share data through the SIGRUM platform</p> <p>The app has the possibility to receive the information from 112 through an information gateway</p>			
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_6	Consider the previous drills carried out by the first responders of both countries	The planning, management, and execution of the drill between Spain and Portugal SHOULD consider the agreements signed between both countries.	The agreements signed between Spain and Portugal on the management of mass casualty incident in the border area MUST be considered in all aspects of the planning, management, and execution of the drill between the two countries. Early responders from both countries have participated in similar	Inspection	P2	<p>VALK-OBJ-2</p> <p>VALK-OBJ-3</p> <p>VALK-OBJ-4</p> <p>VALK-OBJ-5</p> <p>VALK-OBJ-6</p> <p>VALK-OBJ-8</p> <p>VALK-OBJ-9</p>

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				joint drills in recent years			
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_7	Joint drill implemented with VALKYRIES.	It would be RECOMMENDED that the drill between Spain and Portugal be coordinated and if it's possible will be part of the drills scheduled between both countries.	According to the agreements signed between Spain and Portugal on the management of incidents of mass casualty incident, an annual drill is carried out to implement the joint plans and protocols to optimize the management and assistance in this type of incidents. It would be RECOMMENDED that the drill between Spain and Portugal will be part of this joint drill implemented with VALKYRIES.	Inspection	P2	VALK-Obj-2 VALK-Obj-3 VALK-Obj-4 VALK-Obj-5 VALK-Obj-6 VALK-Obj-8 VALK-Obj-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				<p>The planning, management, and execution of the drill between Spain and Portugal coordinated and integrated into the joint drills of the first responders included in the collaborative framework between the General Directorates of Emergencies and Civil Protection of both countries gives the best support to the VALKYRIES project being able to reach the end users to detect areas of improvement and evaluate items as essential as utility, usability, opportunity among others.</p>			

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_8	Information about the basic characteristics of the drill	It is RECOMMENDED to agree and publish information on the basic characteristics of the drill before its execution.	It is RECOMMENDED to agree and disseminate essential information on the basic characteristics of the drill such as the date, type, area, and magnitude of the incident; Damage to infrastructure and the environment, etc.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_9	Basic information necessary for the coordination of the drill	It is RECOMMENDED to agree and publish basic information necessary for the coordination of the drill before its execution.	It is RECOMMENDED to agree and disseminate information essential for proper coordination in general and between different first responders. Essential data on first responders (total number of resources, type of vehicles, location, etc.); characteristics of the intervention zones (Triage Zone, Access and Evacuation Routes, Communication Channels, Area of	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				Concentration of wounded, etc.); Victims (total number of victims, severity, distribution, etc.); Hospital resources (Number of hospitals, type of hospitals, distribution, number of beds, etc.) among others			
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_10	Basic information needed for drill planning	It is RECOMMENDED to obtain information necessary for an optimal planning of the drill before its execution.	It is recommended to obtain basic information on the population (demographic, economic and development characteristics) and the health system (health resources, hospital, and out-of-hospital health system, model, and protocols for attention to multiple incidents, etc.) for optimal planning of the drill.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_11	Basic information needed for the evaluation of the drill	It is RECOMMENDED to agree and plan the collection of the basic and necessary	It is RECOMMENDED to agree and plan the collection of basic information necessary	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			items for an optimal evaluation of the drill.	to evaluate both the health management of the incident and the deployment of VALKYRIES. Essential data on the management of the incident (time of arrival of resources, intervals of action and activation of protocols, number of resources, etc.); medical transport (time of action, evacuated patients, etc.); Local medical care (time of arrival of patients to local primary or hospital care, time of activation hospital alert, etc.); Logistical problems (communication problems due to infrastructures, language, etc.) and deployment of			VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				VALKYRIES among others.			
SERMAS	REQ_COM_T7.5_12	It would be advisable to implement wearables for the registration, control and monitoring of the victims	The wearables record the triage and priority data of the victims, their assessment and treatment carried out and geolocation	Through certain devices, a link is made with the wearables to register and read the pertinent information to the victim. To improve the speed of data transmission, improve its traceability, and security of accompaniment of this information with the victim	Inspection	P2	OBJ-5 OBJ-6 OBJ-7 OBJ-8
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_1	SELP conformity	Solution MUST comply with related safety, ethical, legal and privacy rules.		Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-4
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_2	Security	Security of the data MUST be ensured in its exchange via the system/platform	Storing of the data, but mainly communication ways (encryption, etc.)	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_3	Interoperable and integrable	For use of different units and actors as well as for cross-border. VALKYRIES SHALL be able to ensure integrations with current/legacy systems.	To enable the ability of computer systems or software of related actors to exchange and make use of information.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_4	Robustness and endurance	VALKYRIES SHALL be operatable in adverse conditions	Water/dust resistance, decontaminable, enable to operate in poor visibility/audibility. Also working time on batteries.	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_5	User-friendly and autonomous use	VALKYRIES SHALL be easy to use - intuitive operations. (Simple and short training should cover the needs for use.)	Control of the system should be rather simple. Responders are under stress during action. What can run autonomously it should run autonomously.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_6	End-user acceptance	Acceptance of lessons learned from previous actions and trainings/exercises. VALKYRIES SHALL consider all end-user comments and recommendations.	Development in close relation with end-users. Solution has to be confirmed and accepted by end-users	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_7	Tested and validated	Outputs SHALL be tested and validated.		Inspection Test (Analysis)	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4
ISEMI	REQ_BASE_T7.6_8	Effective	VALKYRIES SHALL ensure the solutions being value for money	Solution should provide reasonable price-quality ratio.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_1	Accepting readily available technologies	VALKYRIES SHALL reduce necessity to buy new devices.	Based on available devices like smartphones, tablets, PCs/NBs, etc.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_2	Fast and smooth	VALKYRIES SHALL present always up to date situation	On time information. Every fact reported to the system have to be captured and provided to the others immediately.	Inspection Test Analysis	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_3	Independent and stable connection	VALKYRIES SHALL ensure connectivity in all possible (even theoretical) conditions.	What if there is not internet/ mobile signal? What if radio is not possible risk of explosion?	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_4	Integrable with smart/ external devices and sensors	VALKYRIES SHALL have the possibility to connect various devices and sensors	integration with for example: body camera/microphone, detectors, autonomous systems (drones...), body sensors, oxygen level. But also, data from hydrometeorological sensors, etc.	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_5	Automatic features	What can be done automatically - it SHOULD be done this way. With aim to reduce related effort of the actors.	Localisation, navigation, maybe translations, etc. Online displaying who is where (also its capacities). Best route suggesting. Marking important points...	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_6	Manageability	Controllable in difficult conditions (PPE, gloves ...)	HAZMAT units have protecting suits, breathing apparatus, number of gloves, etc.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_7	Multi-displayable ways	VALKYRIES SHALL be able to present data on various ways (PC, tablets, smartphones, maybe also augmented/virtual reality). Earphones as well as the	Different units use different tools, but everybody SHOULD understand the situation	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			involvement of other senses should be considered.				
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_8	Easy to report/ insert data	Easy to upload up to date facts (partially overlapping with REQ_COM_T7.5_5 and REQ_BASE_T7.6_5). Speech to text conversion SHOULD be considered.	The way how to put the data inside the system have to be easy, simple, and quick. It is wanted to use drop down menu, proposals, etc. to enable simple click approach. Respectively voice control (verbal commands).	Inspection Test	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_9	Grouping of information	To group information and its further processes which SHOULD be present on basis of pre-set rules	Police MIGHT have slightly different interests than FRS and ambulances and vice versa. Each actor should receive information which is important for him (cognitive load of the users have to be considered).	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_10	Interconnection of actors/units	VALKYRIES SHALL communicate with C2 and with other units as well as between them at the same time	To ensure such a communication as well as to allow management of these links. (on/off, rules and responsibilities)	Inspection Test	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_11	Health records	VALKYRIES SHALL display of health records of identified persons	Specific need for ambulances. Applicable in countries, where this is possible.	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_12	Sustainable	VALKYRIES SHALL have maintenance and updates	What maintenance will be required. What if some part is damaged? Possible updates due to the technological and technical development...	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
ISEMI	REQ_COM_T7.6_13	Trouble-shooter	VALKYRIES SHALL have technical support (online/offline)	Possible support in case of problems.	Inspection	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7
BDI	REQ_BASE_T7.7_1	Planning of the UC3	The goal of this sub-task SHALL implement the whole planning of the exercise under T7.7	Planning of the UC3 regarding the size, location, and territorial coverage in case of physically implementation of the exercise in the affected	Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				regions on the Bulgarian territory, including exercise security, communications and logistics plans and procedures.			
BDI	REQ_BASE_T7.7_2	Analysis of existing regulatory/standardisation framework	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse is of existing regulatory and standardisation framework and procedures for civil protection.	Analysis of existing regulatory and standardisation framework and procedures for civil protection in Bulgaria and Greece to synchronize the implementation of different emergency rescue and emergency recovery activities.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3
BDI	REQ_BASE_T7.7_3	Development of SOPs	VALKYRIES SHALL develop SOPs regarding coordination between different actors, including volunteers.	The goal of this sub-task is to develop the SOPs to be used during the exercise.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BDI	REQ_BASE_T7.7_4	Coordination with different actors involved in the exercise.	VALKYRIES SHALL coordinate with different actors from Bulgaria and Greece involved in the exercise regarding their roles and responsibilities, as well as with the responsible local authorities in Bulgaria.		Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7
BDI	REQ_BASE_T7.7_5	Joint training of First Aid Responders	Joint training of First Aid Responders participating in the exercise	A joint training workshop SHALL be organized for the participants in the exercise based on the results from Task T6.2: Education and Training for first aid responders. This will be an opportunity to practically test the deliverables.	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
BRC	REQ_BASE_T7.7_6	Host nation support	VALKYRIES SHALL provide some definition and development of host support to the "visiting" partners. In general rules how to support partners coming abroad to	The goal of the task is to develop customized common rules on how to coordinate and jointly implement activities during joint UC execution.	Test Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			support disaster response operation.				
BRC	REQ_BASE_T7.7_7	Volunteer support	Definition of common rules to ensure volunteer safety, wellbeing, and successful participation in UC	The goal is to create rules of volunteer participation in the UC SHALL ensure their participation in line with legal and ethics requirements	Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-9
BDI	REQ_COM_T7.7_1	Planning of the UC3	Planning of the UC3 MUST be done in close cooperation between the BDI and the BRC, as well as the partners from Greece - KEMEA and the HRT. Before the start of the exercise, the Bulgarian partners MUST visit the region where the exercise will be implemented and will coordinate with the regional authorities, police, border police and the military units that will be involved. At this point, the plan is to have an exercise in place with physical participation of first aid responders and project		Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
			partners. In case of COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, we will develop a plan to implement the exercise by simulation.				
BDI	REQ_COM_T7.7_2	Analysis of existing regulatory/standardisation framework	The analysis of the existing regulatory and standardisation framework and procedures for civil protection in Bulgaria and Greece MUST be done well in advance before the exercise to provide a good basis for the normal implementation.		Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9
BDI	REQ_COM_T7.7_3	Development of SOPs	The development of the draft SOPs MUST be prepared in advance to guarantee successful implementation of the exercise. The final document will be discussed and approved before the start of the exercise.		Inspection	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BDI	REQ_COM_T7.7_4	Coordination with different actors involved in the exercise.	The coordination with the different actors involved in the exercise MUST be done in advance to guarantee successful cooperation during the exercise. Responsible are BDI, BRC, KEMEA and HRT. A plan for CIMIC MUST be prepared in advance.		Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
BDI	REQ_COM_T7.7_5	Joint training of First Aid Responders	The developed in WP6 E&T kit MAY be tested during the exercise. There MAY be a 4-hours joint multinational workshop to present and test the E&T kit followed by an evaluation of the suggested training. At least one representative from all institutions/organisations involved in the exercise MUST attend.		Inspection Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
BRC	REQ_COM_T7.7_6	Host nation support	In the scope of the project, the minimum requirements shall cover - preparation of country briefings/factsheets for incoming teams; the identification and training of liaison officers to join the incoming teams; to set up and train national host support team/s; coordination on the site; logistics; etc.	For more details see Brussels, 1.6.2012, SWD (2012) 169 final	Test Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
BRC	REQ_COM_T7.7_7	Volunteer support	NHS /see above/ plus qualification requirements of incoming teams, insurance, volunteer management, scope of work - agreement, legal local requirements, comms, etc.		Demonstration	P2	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_1	Familiarisation	To plan the user cases, VALKYRIES SHALL learn how similar exercises are conducted, using todays solutions	Participate in different exercises as an observer	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_2	Harmonisation	With 4 different scenarios as user cases, is it vital to compare the different scenarios to make a common script for how the demonstrations SHALL be planned, conducted, and reported	Participate in exercises like the other exercises, and have common workshops for the planning of the demonstrations	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_3	Testing on a smaller scale	The usability, reliability and usefulness of the system SHOULD have been previously tested in incident simulations of multiple victims with first responders in their usual work activity.	By using systems already in use by first responders, it SHALL be tested if these systems are compatible with the demonstrations the projects will conduct	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_4	Common system evaluation methodology	The use of a common tool agreed in a committee of experts and validated ensures the harmonisation and standardisation of the evaluation methodology.	It is RECOMMENDED to form a committee of experts (UTSTEIN style) to define and agree on a minimum set of items to create a valuation survey of the system and its subsequent validation.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_5	Minimum data set	It is RECOMMENDED to reach an agreement between experts to define the design, collection, analysis and labelling of data related to different areas of learning and teaching methodology for comprehension.	It is RECOMMENDED to form a committee of experts (UTSTEIN style) to define and agree on a teaching model for comprehension and simulation.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_6	Autonomous performance of first responders	The autonomous work of the first responders guarantees fluidity to the management of the incident ensuring, always, truthful, and updated information.	The application MUST guarantee, always, the technological independence of the first responders in such a way that each team can fluidly collect the essential information for an adequate and agile management of the incident	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_7	Basic operation of the technology regardless of the adversities and location of the incident.	The operating system MUST work in adverse geographical and / or technological conditions such as high mountains, sea, or places of scarce mobile coverage such as the Metro, caves, etc.	The minimum technology MUST be established for the proper functioning of the operating system in basic mode. It is necessary to agree,	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				preferably by UTSTEIN style, the minimum data to be collected when the operating system works in basic mode due to the adverse situations of the incident.			
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_8	Legal regulations	Knowledge and review of the applicable legal regulations in cases of disasters or mass casualty incident, including the EU Civil Protection Mechanism. All procedures and proceedings MUST be under the regulatory framework of norms and laws of Civil Protection.	We MUST ensure that all action and carried out under the regulatory frameworks of Civil Protection and its mechanisms in case of disasters or mass casualty incident in cross border frontier.	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-9
USN	REQ_BASE_T7.8_9	Ethical principles	All actions MUST be carried out in compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, national, or local laws. Knowledge and review of the applicable legal regulations.	We MUST ensure that persons carrying out research and activities tasks follow norms and laws, and good research practices. This implies with the following fundamental principles: Reliability, honesty, respect and	Inspection Demonstration	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-9

Editor	ID	Name	Description	Details	Verification Method	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
				accountability. A surveillance system is recommended.			

Table 11 - WP7 Requirements

6. Conclusions

This document reflected the entire consortium's effort to present a final version of the base, extended and common requirements and the description of the four demonstration scenarios. Over the six months since the delivery of D2.1 document, the content has been reviewed and the requirements have been refined. These requirements are essential to achieve the VALKYRIES objectives and the challenges defined in the call.

In this document D2.7 (update of D2.1 document), a broader picture of the project has been considered, resulting in a much clearer idea about potential capabilities/functionalities to be provided by VALKYRIES.

During the following months of the project and as the different work packages progress, new opportunities for harmonisation may arise, new points of interest may emerge, and they should be reflected in the document. In case of modifications or reconsiderations, these would be submitted as annexes, with adequate justification for the changes, and highlighting the decisions taken.

Finally, regarding the proposed Demonstration Scenarios, it is remarkable that the project tasks related to the development of the Use Cases start in month 19 (explicitly T7.5, T7.6, T7.7 and T7.8 of VALKYRIES), which leaves a margin of time from now on, once this final version has been presented, to be able to expose what is presented in this document in the demonstrators. The resources and infrastructures table including the breakdown by actors and split between the planning and execution phases was not added in this version of the document.

7. Annex A – CONOPs

These Concept of Operations Plans (CONOPS) provides guidance to public safety agencies (traditional first responders) and non-traditional responders for developing and employing interoperability during their demo scenarios.

Where incidents either extend beyond a local authority’s boundary or, due to the scale of the emergency response activity, require the support of other local authorities, there should be a working agreement for events that require more than one local authority to invoke its emergency response and recovery arrangements.

7.1. UC#1 CONOPs

SERMAS as leaders of Task 7.5 and UC1 has held several meetings with the authorities of Évora (Portugal) and Extremadura (Spain) and have agreed to participate actively in the review, planning and execution of the drill. To this end, a multidisciplinary team of experts in disaster management has been created to review the planning, management, and execution of the drill.

It is currently being reviewed by the Portuguese and Extremadura authorities and the next meeting of the multidisciplinary team will be 26-27 October where the last details will be defined and agreed. The drill will be brought forward to the first half of May by fire alert.

UC#1 CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE & RECOVERY	
Response mobilisation and sustainability	<p>Both in Extremadura and in the District of Portalegre, the corresponding Civil Protection Emergency Response Plans will be activated.</p> <p>Authorities on the ground:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency Operations Centers (EOC): 112 Extremadura (Integrated/Operational Coordination Centre (CECOP/I), 112 Portugal (Distrital Operational Coordination Centre (CCOD)) • Advanced Command Post • Action groups. Firefighters, EMS, etc • Hospitals: Évora Hospital and potentially other hospitals in Extremadura • Victims. • Other actors: Civil Protection, Red Cross Portugal/Spain, Volunteers, Public Health Services, Politic representators <p>To support the ability for to response to a prolonged emergency, each authority maintains sufficient resources and expertise to maintain its response for 48 hours.</p>
Cross-Border Authority	<p>Emergency response roles</p> <p>The roles more commonly found to exist as a dedicated emergency response roles include:</p>

emergency response staff	<p>(i) First Level – Emergency Operations Centres (EOC)</p> <p>(ii) Second Level – Advanced Command Post</p> <p>(iii) Third Level – Command sections and Action groups</p>
Cross-Border Authority command and control	<p>The Emergency Operations Centres from Extremadura and Portugal will be composed of the following profiles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disaster management political authority • Incident Manager • Incident management support team • Crisis management team <p>The District of Portalegre will establish an Advanced Command Post appropriate to phase IV of the OMS (Operations Management System) and Extremadura will also establish its Advanced Command Post.</p> <p>The Advanced Command Post is composed of all the chiefs of the action groups present in the drill. Each action group chief / director will be present at the post to facilitate tactical decision-making.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Command Post <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Incident Commander o Command staff <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>Logistics</u> ▪ <u>Operations (fire fighting, search & rescue...)</u> ▪ <u>Medical care, evacuation</u> ▪ <u>Safety</u> ▪ <u>Others: Planning, Technical assistance, liason, etc</u> • Action groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <u>Safety: Police, Civil Guard, Portuguese National Guard</u> o <u>Operations: Firefighters, search and rescue</u> o <u>Medical: EMS and ambulances</u> o <u>Logistic</u> o <u>Psychological first aid</u> o <u>Technical assistance</u> o <u>Public information</u>
Cross-Border Authority strategic command	<p>The command-and-control structure is composed by the following entities:</p> <p>EOC: The EOCs of both countries will be in contact with each other to ensure maximum coordination of actions on both sides of the border.</p> <p>Advanced Command Post: The unified command of an AMP, the Incident Commander IC, will be in each case the one determined by the standard in the territory where it is located. When support teams of other nationalities work</p>

	<p>in this AMP, their commands will be integrated into the command staff, but always under the unified command of the IC.</p> <p>Action teams: each action group has a Chief / Director who organise the work of all responders within its unit.</p> <p>Variations in Command and Control (C2) may occur, depending on the severity of the incident and the availability of certain units on the field.</p> <p>Communication between agencies should be continuous through the Incident Commander.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) First Level (Command & Control) – Emergency Operations Centres (EOC) (ii) Second Level – Advanced Command Post (iii) Third level – Action group Chief / Director
Cross-Border Authority tactical command	<p>The affected Local Authority nominates an Action group Chief to act as their Tactical Manager, who has overall responsibility for the Local Authority's response to the emergency. These managers determine the best way to achieve the strategic priorities as determined by the Incident Commander.</p>
Function-specific capabilities	<p>Firefighters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Firefighting, both ground and aerial, is deployed on a cross-border level. <p>Ambulances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic and advanced life support of emergency system, red cross and Civil Protection of both Spain and Portugal are activated. <p>Security forces from both countries are activated.</p> <p>HESE Hospital</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activated and ready to respond to the medical emergencies assigned. <p>Other Spanish and Portuguese health care institutions might/can be included to plan and support assistance resources and decisions.</p> <p>Advanced Command Post</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation close to the emergency scenario that allows decision making and coordination close to the first responders on terrain.
Mutual Aid	<p>Participating authorities shall provide, wherever possible, assistance to another participating authorities in the form of provision of personnel and/or</p>

	<p>equipment in the event of, or in the reasonable anticipation of, an emergency or other disruptive or rising incident when asked to do so.</p> <p>The corresponding Civil Protection plans from Extremadura and from the District of Portalegre will be activated.</p> <p>Extremadura</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the first instance, the Special Plan for the Risk of Forest Fires in Extremadura (INFOCAEX) will be activated in its Operational Situation 2 and the Military Emergency Unit will be activated. • Subsequently and due to the bus accident, the Extremadura Territorial Civil Protection Plan (PLATERCAEX) will be activated. <p>Portalegre</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the District of Portalegre, the Operations Management System (SGO) will be activated at level IV, as the activation of numerous operational resources will be required. • Subsequently, due to the accident and the fire, the District Emergency and Civil Protection Plan of Portalegre will be activated.
Military Aid to the Civil Authority	<p>The military forces join the emergency plan.</p>
Recovery Management	<p>Recovery management falls to the affected boroughs. They nominate a manager to coordination the recovery based on the recovery protocol.</p>
Warning, Informing and Communications	<p>Each Local Authority is required to put in place arrangements to make information available to the public about civil protection matters and maintain arrangements to warn, inform and advise the public in the event of an emergency.</p>
Other groups and organisations	<p>There is a range of other groups and organisation that support the response to incident, which includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Protection • Red Cross Portugal/Spain • Volunteers (e.g., citizens) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Help and collaborate in the evacuation and transfer victims to the Sanitary Assistance Zone (SAZ) • Other Public Health Services • Politic representators • Municipalities or humanitarian aid organisations

Table 12 - UC#1 CONOPS

The management and coordination structures in Spain and Portugal are presented below. It is important to highlight that both structures were planned by the Emergency and Civil Protection National Authority from both countries.

Spain

The table below presents the plans activated at different levels (Municipal, A.C. of Extremadura Level and National Level) and the management and coordination structure. To make this **Territorial Civil Protection Plan (PLATERCAEX)** fully operational, it is indispensable to establish the operational, management and coordination structure, as well as the groups that will intervene in each emergency. At the same time, establish the composition and specific functions of the different authorities that constitute it.

The organisational chart has the following structure and it is organized in terms of **Management and Coordination Structure - CECOP/CECOPI**. On the other side, the **Operational Structure** is composed of various groups (**Advanced Command Post (ACP)**, **Sectorial Advanced Command Post (CGIF)**, **Advanced Medical Post (AMP)**, **Municipal Operational Coordination Centre (CECOPAL)**, **resources coordination and action groups**).

Directorate General for Civil Protection and Emergencies of the Ministry of Home Affairs	
Activated CP Plans	Management and coordination structure
Municipal Level:	PLATERCAEX DIRECTOR
PEMU (Sit. Grav.3)	DIRECTION COMITEE
A.C. of Extremadura Level:	TECHNICAL ADVISORY COMMITTEE
INFOEX (GIF Nivel 2)	INFORMATION OFFICE
INFOCAEX (Sit Grav. 2)	CECOPI (INTEGRATED OPERATIONAL COORDINATION CENTRE)
PLATERCAEX (Sit Grav2)	CAUE 1.1.2 EXTREMADURA (It is established in CECOP)
National Level:	CAUE 1.1.2 DIRECTOR (DIRECTOR OF OPERATIONS)
PLEGEM (FASE	COR (REGIONAL OPERATIONAL CENTRE PLAN INFOEX)
PREEMERGENCY SIT.OP.2)	

Table 13 - Directorate General for Civil Protection and Emergencies of the Ministry of Home Affairs

On the other hand, it is mentioned the Forest Fire Fighting Plan of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura (INFOEX). This plan establishes the organisation and operating procedures of the resources and services owned by the Regional Government of Extremadura and those assigned by other public administrations and public or private entities or bodies, to tackle forest fires occurring in the territory of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura.

The superior management and organisation of the INFOEX Plan corresponds to the Head of the Regional Ministry with competence in forest fire prevention and extinction and, without prejudice to this, the management of the Plan corresponds, in general, to the Management Committee.

Portugal

The table below presents the Civil Protection structure planned by the Emergency and Civil Protection National Authority from Portugal for VALKYRIES pilot.

Sistema de Proteção Civil

Level	Emergency Plans	Management and Coordination Structure Coordination		Operational Structure	
		Policy Direction	Policy Coordination	Institutional Coordination	Operational Command
Regional	-	-	-	-	Alentejo Regional Command for Emergency and Civil Protection
Distrital	Portalegre District Civil Protection Emergency Plan	Government Member	Portalegre District Civil Protection Commission	District Operational Coordination Centre	Alentejo Sub-regional Command for Emergency and Civil Protection
Municipal	Municipal Civil Protection Emergency Plans of the affected municipalities	President of the Chamber	Municipal Civil Protection Committees of the affected municipalities	Municipal Operational Coordination Centres of the affected municipalities	Commander of the Fire Brigade
Operations Theatre	-	-	-	-	Commander of Rescue Operations

Table 14 – Civil Protection System

Organisation - Operations Management System

Effective maximum deployed	Organisation of the Theatre of Operations	Command		Means of support for the Command Post	Command Post Organisation
648 Operational	Command Post Command Post Operational 2 fronts 6 Sectors per front	Commander of Rescue Operations (COS)	COREPC, 2º COREPC, CODIS, 2º CODIS	VC 3 / CETAC	Coordinator PCO Operations Officer Logistics Officer Planning Officer Security Officer Liaison Officer Public Relations Officer
		Front Commander	Commander	VCOC	
		Sector Commander	Commander / 2º Commander	VCOT	

Table 15 – Civil Protection System

7.2. UC#2 CONOPs

UC#2 CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE & RECOVERY	
Response mobilisation and sustainability	<p>Each authority has in place:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Unit Commander <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to deal with a range of scenarios, assess the incident, and escalate it to ensure a suitable mobilisation to deal with it. (ii) Unit members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident response. <p>To support the ability for to response to a prolonged emergency, each authority maintains sufficient resources and expertise to maintain its response for 48 hours.</p>
Cross-Border Authority emergency response staff	<p>Emergency response roles</p> <p>The roles more commonly found to exist as a dedicated emergency response roles include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (iv) First Level (C2) – IRS (v) Second Level – Incident Commander (vi) Third Level – Unit Commander
Cross-Border Authority Command and Control	<p>The command-and-control structure is composed by the following entities. Each Local Unit has a Commander who is in charge of organising the work of all responders within its unit.</p> <p>Variations in Command and Control (C2) may occur, depending on the severity of the incident and the availability of certain units on the field.</p> <p>Communication between agencies should be continuous through the Incident Commander.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (iv) First Level (Command & Control) - IRS – Integration Rescue System, operator of the 112 (v) Second Level - Incident Commander (vi) Third level - Unit Commander

Figure 3 - Command and Control (C2)

<p>Cross-Border Authority strategic command</p>	<p>The Incident Commander has overall responsibility for the Local Authorities' response to the emergency. This Commander establishes the incident response strategy and is responsible for the Unit Commanders Group (UCG).</p>
<p>Cross-Border Authority tactical command</p>	<p>The affected Local Authority nominates a Unit Commander to act as their Tactical Commander, who has overall responsibility for the Local Authority's response to the emergency. These commanders determine the best way to achieve the strategic priorities as determined by the Incident Commander.</p> <p>There shall be one Unit Commander for each of the following entities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FRS - Basic Unit and HAZMAT Unit • Ambulances • Police - Common unit and CBRN unit • Civil Protection (CP) - Control Chemical Laboratory (CChL) • Military <p>Unit Commanders Group (UCG)</p> <p>The purpose of a UCG is to provide strategic coordination of resources at a Local Level. It is chaired by the Incident Commander.</p>

Function-specific capabilities	<p>IRS (C2, 112):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Get as much information as possible (How many victims, what are the symptoms, what is the exact place of incident, the dimensions, etc.).• Command and Control Authority. <p>FRS – basic unit (1st on site). The primary objectives of FRS are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Recognize the threat – presence of hazardous materials (“5S” or similar).• Remember to prioritise personal own personal safety.• Report on the situation immediately (e.g., “METHANE”).• Respond – Using “steps 1 2 3 plus” principles (in this case consider: Evacuation, Communication & advise, Disrobe, Decontaminate).• Remove the people from the hazard. <p>Ambulance (2nd on site)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Transport of patients to hospitals depending on the occupancy of the hospitals and the patient status.• Taken into consideration (limited capacities of the hospitals in such a case).• Navigation – Optimizing the road. <p>FRS – HAZMAT (3rd on site)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Location and status of the victims.• Number of victims and identification.• Access to “health records”. <p>Police (4th on site)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inputs from the present units.• Gather the evidence (as it is possible crime).• To use all the data taken by the previous steps for possible next criminal investigation. <p>Police - CBRN unit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Gather the evidence.• Detect and identify the threat in more detail (What is the substance, what are its properties and effects).• To support HAZAMT team in specific actions.• To put their measurements to the MC2A. <p>CP – CChL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Detailed analysis of the chemicals and updating of the results in the MC2A. This step is important for other units and stakeholders. Confirm the completion of specific steps (decontamination line ready, measurements done, zones established, etc.).
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Mutual Aid	Participating authorities shall provide, wherever possible, assistance to another participating authorities in the form of provision of personnel and/or equipment in the event of, or in the reasonable anticipation of, an emergency or other disruptive or rising incident when asked to do so.
Military Aid to the Civil Authority	Its role in the field is the same as the CP – CChL, but only in case that the chemical substance is considered a Chemical Warfare Agent.
Recovery Management	Recovery management falls to the affected boroughs. They nominate a manager to coordination the recovery based on the recovery protocol.
Warning, Informing and Communications	Each Local Authority is required to put in place arrangements to make information available to the public about civil protection matters and maintain arrangements to warn, inform and advise the public in the event of an emergency.
Other groups and organisations	There is a range of other groups and organisation that support the authorities' response to the incident.

Table 16 - UC#2 CONOPS

7.3. UC#3 CONOPs

UC#3 CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE & RECOVERY	
Response mobilisation and sustainability	<p>Mobilisation of the response involves the following steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial call to 112. • Bulgarian Civil Protection. • Hellenic Ministry of Foreign Affairs. • EUCPM notification for the incident (just in case further assistance is needed). <p>The authorities that will be in the area are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) The Bulgarian Red Cross and Hellenic Rescue Team (ii) The Bulgarian Fire Brigade (iii) The Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service (iv) Local authorities from Bulgaria (v) State civil protection authorities <p>In addition to the Bulgarian stakeholders, the respective first responders from Greece might be present at the site of the Use Case, as they would, should their assistance be needed in a real-life event. The following stakeholders will participate, either physically or remotely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Experts from the Civil Protection Agency of the Region of Central Macedonia. (ii) The Hellenic Fire Brigade (iii) The Supportive Team for CBRNE of the Hellenic Police <p>It has to be mentioned here that the above Agencies will participate in the context of the Use Case but are not the only ones that operate in a real-life event. Military CBRNE units as well as the State General Chemistry and the Hellenic Earthquake Planning and Protection Organisation (EPPO) would be activated at least for the assessment of the impact on the Greek side.</p> <p>To support the ability to respond to a prolonged emergency, each authority maintains sufficient resources and expertise to sustain operations for 48 hours.</p>
Cross-Border Authority emergency response staff	<p>After being notified, the Hellenic Ministry of Foreign Affairs, notifies the Hellenic Ministry of Climate Crisis and Civil Protection, in order to be aware of potential impacts to the Greek-Bulgarian borderline and the provision of resources.</p> <p>The main involved Greek stakeholders may be divided into three sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil protection agencies (locally, regionally, or nationally stationed). • Professional first responders' agencies The fire service, the ambulance service, the military, the police

	<p>, Hellenic Earthquake Planning and Protection Organization, regional services, , weather forecast service.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and private utility infrastructures power service, telecommunication service, water supplier service, natural gas supplier service • Other State services The Hellenic Earthquake Planning and Protection Organization (EPPO), the Hellenic National Meteorological Service (HNMS), the Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy • Volunteering organizations (under the umbrella of the GSCP)
<p>Cross-Border Authority command and control</p>	<p>The disaster response action is coordinated by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Ministry of Interior (Moi) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Close cooperation with the Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service the local authorities, police, military unit, and the Greek counterparts.
<p>Cross-Border Authority strategic command</p>	<p>The command-and-control structure is composed by the following entities. Variations in Command and Control (C2) may occur, depending on the severity of the incident and the availability of certain units on the field.</p> <p>Cross-sector aspects are addressed mainly since different disaster vectors are described in the scenario, and therefore, different types of First Responders (FRs) need to be foreseen. Communication between agencies should be continuous.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) First Level (Command & Control) – Moi (ii) Second Level – The Bulgarian General Directorate (GD) "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" (iii) The Hellenic Ministry of Foreign Affairs (iv) The Hellenic General Secretariat of Civil Protection (GSCP) (v) Third level – First Responders (FRs)
<p>Cross-Border Authority tactical command</p>	<p>The affected Local Authority nominates a Unit Commander to act as their Tactical Commander, who has overall responsibility for the Local Authority's response to the emergency.</p> <p>There shall be one Unit Commander for each of the following entities:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bulgarian Red Cross • Hellenic Rescue Team • Bulgarian Fire Brigade • Hellenic Fire Brigade (for the Greek side) • Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service • Military
<p style="text-align: center;">Function-specific capabilities</p>	<p>The Bulgarian Red Cross and Hellenic Rescue Team</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide assistance to affected population in the cross-border area, humanitarian aid and restoring family links. <p>The Bulgarian Fire Brigade and Hellenic Fire Brigade</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responders implementing emergency rescue and emergency recovery activities (independent operations to the two affected countries and joint operations in the context of the cross-border assistance). <p>The Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency medical aid. <p>Local authorities from Bulgaria and Greece</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistical support and coordination. <p>State civil protection authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for management and coordination
<p style="text-align: center;">Mutual Aid</p>	<p>Participating authorities shall provide, wherever possible, assistance to another participating authorities in the form of provision of personnel and/or equipment in the event of, or in the reasonable anticipation of, an emergency or other disruptive or rising incident when asked to do so.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Military Aid to the Civil Authority</p>	<p>Military units – CBRN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile and therefore specialised expertise is needed. • Universities and institutes in Blagoevgrad, Sofia, as well as Greek partners – Chemical related faculties/departments, respectively their laboratories might be used for analysis if requested.

	<p>Bulgarian Military Medical Academy – Specialised search and rescue team.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Save lives and minimize damage to health. • Mobile command-staff vehicle of the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy equipped with communication technology, PCs, connection to the internet.
<p>Recovery Management</p>	<p>The Bulgarian Fire Brigade and Hellenic Fire Brigade.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responders implementing emergency rescue and emergency recovery activities (independent operations to the two affected countries and joint operations in the context of the cross-border assistance).
<p>Warning, Informing and Communications</p>	<p>Each Local Authority is required to put in place arrangements to make information available to the public about civil protection matters and maintain arrangements to warn, inform and advise the public in the event of an emergency. Regarding Greece early warnings can be sent by the 112-emergency number.</p>
<p>Other groups and organisations</p>	<p>There is a range of other groups and organisation that support the authorities' response to the incident.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volunteering organizations (under the umbrella of the Hellenic General Secretary of Civil Protection - GSCP)

Table 17 - UC#3 CONOPs

7.4. UC#4 CONOPs

UC#4 CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE & RECOVERY	
Response mobilisation and sustainability	<p>Authorities on the scenario:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Norwegian Coastal Administration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinator of communication between vessels. (ii) Norwegian Coast Guard <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scene Commander. (iii) SAR Units <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident response. <p>To support the ability for to response to the emergency, each authority maintains sufficient resources and expertise to maintain its response for prolonged time.</p>
Cross-Border Authority emergency response staff	<p>Emergency response roles</p> <p>The roles more commonly found to exist as a dedicated emergency response roles include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Norwegian Coastal Administration, DSB (ii) Norwegian Coast Guard (iii) SAR Units
Cross-Border Authority command and control	<p>The command-and-control is performed by the Rescue Coordination Centre (RCC). They will take the role, identify risks and plan how to best apply the SAR resources available. This may involve units from different nations, and it can change during the emergency dutarion.</p> <p>They are responsible for communicating with ships near the area, so they can assist, providing them with geolocation and an initial assessment of the incident.</p> <p>Variations in Command and Control (C2) may occur, depending on the severity of the incident and the availability of certain units on the field.</p> <p>Communication between agencies should be continuous through the Rescue Coordination Centre (RCC).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Command & Control – Rescue Coordination Centre (RCC) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Norwegian Coastal Administration (ii) Norwegian Coast Guard – Scene Commander. (iii) SAR Units

<p>Cross-Border Authority strategic command</p>	<p>The Rescue Coordination Centre (RCC) has the best ability to perform coordination and will take the role. They will establish the incident response strategy, applying the SAR resources available.</p>
<p>Cross-Border Authority tactical command</p>	<p>Norwegian Coast Guard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several other vessels in the vicinity available to assist, including one Coast Guard vessel, this will take the role of scene commander. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Receive initial notification of the incident. ○ Assess the incident and activate the response.
<p>Function-specific capabilities</p>	<p>Norwegian Coastal Administration, DSB</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio communication broadcasted to the ships close to the area, so they can assist, providing them with geolocation and an initial assessment of the incident. <p>Norwegian Coast Guard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coast Guard vessel will assist and will take the role of scene commander. • Bring casualties on shore to hospitals. <p>SAR Units</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control and care of all personnel involved. • Extinguish the fire. • Drone Units <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ New capabilities with autonomous SAR units should be listed as resources similarly as regular SAR units and should be activated based on needed services (search for man overboard, make heatmap, find contaminated area etc.). ○ Drones with chemical sample instrumentation for the ships near the incident to provide casualties information and toxic spill. ○ • Rescue ships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Advanced care to the victims involved in the crash. • Toxic control ships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Control of the spill. ○ Monitoring toxic spill spread.

Mutual Aid	Participating authorities shall provide, wherever possible, assistance to another participating authorities in the form of provision of personnel and/or equipment in the event of, or in the reasonable anticipation of, an emergency or other disruptive or rising incident when asked to do so.
Military Aid to the Civil Authority	N/A
Recovery Management	After the initial SAR, there will be a clean-up of oil or chemicals in the sea drifting towards the shores. Toxic spill is controlled, and first responders' resources are demobilized.
Warning, Informing and Communications	Each Local Authority is required to put in place arrangements to make information available to the public about civil protection matters and maintain arrangements to warn, inform and advise the public in the event of an emergency.
Other groups and organisations	There is a range of other groups and organisation that support the authorities' response to the incident.

Table 18 - UC#4 CONOPs

8. Annex B – Use Case #1

8.1. Scenario description

Identifier	UC-VALKYRIES-01
<p>Overview description of VALKYRIES usage</p>	<p>Cross-Border emergency intervention (Forest fire) Spain-Portugal</p> <p>VALKYRIES provide a common framework to address solutions that might improve cross-border cooperation between Spain and Portugal for first responders to identify forest fire sources, assess forest fire impact on area and population. Victims' identification and health assistance of the potential casualties might be better supervised and managed across the different first responders and medical services reducing the impact on citizens. Data exchanged and shared across different emergency actors, harmonized protocols, and tools standardisation reduce the time-to-response, with a more accurate and efficient coordinated actuations.</p>
<p>Actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens/Volunteers Some citizens and groups of volunteers collaborate with humanitarian aid. Some of these groups are trained and prepared to carry out rescue aid and health aid work. • Firefighters, Emergency Medical Services: SUMMA 112 (Emergency Medical Service of Madrid 112)/FIIBAP (Salud Madrid, 2021) • Emergency Operations Centers (EOC): 112 Extremadura (Centro de Coordinación Operativa (CECOP/I), 112 Portuga (Centro de Coordenação Operacional Distrital - CCOD). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Disaster management political authority ○ Incident Manager ○ Incident management support team ○ Crisis management team • Advanced Command Post <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Incident Commander ○ Command staff <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>Logistics</u> ▪ <u>Operations (fire fighting, search & rescue...)</u> ▪ <u>Medical care, evacuation</u> ▪ <u>Safety</u> ▪ <u>Others:</u> Planning, Technical assistance, liason, etc. • Action groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Safety:</u> Police, Civil Guard, Portuguese National Guard. ○ <u>Operations:</u> Firefighters, search and rescue

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Medical</u>: EMS and ambulances ○ <u>Logistic</u> ○ <u>Psychological first aid</u> ○ <u>Technical assistance</u> ○ <u>Public information</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hospitals: Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora and potentially other hospitals in Extremadura. ● Victims ● Other actors: Civil Protection, Red Cross Portugal/Spain, Volunteers, Public Health Services, Politic representators
<p>Potential related tools</p>	<p>In both Spain and Portugal, the Emergency System is operated through the unique number 112.</p> <p>Fortunately, there is a cross-border agreement for the management of Mass Casualties Incident (MCI) in the areas near the border between the two countries. This agreement has allowed collaborations in previous incidents between neighbouring countries and drills on a biannual basis (Agencia Estatal Boletín Oficial del Estado, 2019)</p> <p>Potential related tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mobile comms ● Radio comms ● GNSS / GALILEO information ● iSafety as Mobile Command and Control (C2) app ● SIGRUNAWARE ● MONITOR ● TASSICA MCI ● KystInfo ● Blockchain
<p>Potential data sources</p>	<p>The initial data will be provided by the alerts to the two 112 cross-border coordinating centres, which will activate their resources according to usual protocols. In a second phase, the first responders will collect the initial data according to the Minimum Data Set (CMD) of the Valkyries Project.</p> <p>Potential data sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Weather information ● Geographical information ● GNSS location from vehicles, mobile devices. ● Drone information ● First responder's database ● Electronic Health Records (EHR) ● Victims' health data

Table 19 - Scenario description UC1

8.2. Emergency support activation planning information

<p>Background</p>	<p>Due to the high temperatures of the summer period, the orography, the wind, the climate change, and the previous forest fires, have left a terrain susceptible to new fires of difficult control.</p> <p>Due to a dry thunderstorm with significant electrical discharges in the areas of Valencia de Alcántara and the District of Portalegre, several outbreaks of fires will be caused on both sides of the Raya because of lightning strikes in the area.</p> <p>To establish exactly the area where the forest fire that affects both sides of the Raya will be simulated, a study of the history of forest fires in this area will be carried out.</p> <p>In addition, near the border there is an accident involving a bus, with numerous victims.</p> <p>The affected area is of high ecological value, and it is very close to different population centres of difficult access and far from hospitals of high complexity. Forest fire brigade personnel stationed at strategic points are responsible for guard duty. There are not many health resources in the area as it is rather unpopulated. There are citizens who are working in the fields (cleaning farms), walking pets, and playing sports. Subsequently, they will be the first to see the smoke.</p>
<p>Strategical and Operational Vignettes</p>	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Parque Natural da Serra de São Mamede</p> <p>District of Portalegre</p> <p>Municipalities: Castelo de Vide Marvão Portalegre Arronches</p> </div> <div style="width: 45%; text-align: right;"> </div> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 4 - Fire starts and advance zone</i></p>

Figure 5 - Health operational deployment

Advanced Medical Post (AMP): module whose tasks are: 1) Perform patient profiling (triage) on the site of the disaster. 2) Stabilise the condition of and prepare the patient for transport to the most suitable health facility for final treatment.

Advanced Command Post (ACP): module deployed close to the disaster location on early stages of the incident management, where the primary functions of command and control are performed.

Figure 6- Health operational deployment

Current
situation**Overall Description**

A cross-border forest fire, with multiple fire sources localized in the border area between Spain and Portugal. There are several urbanized areas with limited access due to the mountainous terrain, high forest density and an underdeveloped road system are affected. Due to climate change, the orography and the meteorological situation, this area presents a high risk of fire with difficult control as demonstrated in previous incidents. There are potential casualties that require triage, first aid and potential transportation to Hospital Do Espírito Santo de Évora (HESE) and potentially other hospitals in Extremadura. Due to the large scale of the fire, the number of victims requiring hospitalisation is high, and additional First Aid vehicles (Ambulances) are requested to transport the victims to the available hospitals. Fire resulted from of the fall of lightning threatens several built-up areas in the middle of the mountains and a large forest area. They warn of the presence of several deaths as well as cars trapped by the advance of the flames. These events are like those that occurred in 2017 on the "road of death" linking the Portuguese municipalities of Figueiró dos Vinhos and Castanheira de Pera, in the district of Leiria.

In these circumstances, the coordination between different actors is crucial to minimize human and material damage. The fire's trajectory was directed towards the villages of Marvão and Castelo de Vide causing great material and human damages. Preventive evictions and a large movement of this population to safe areas.

In its advance through the sierra, the dense woodland, and the dry environment favors the rapid advance of the flames and dangerously approaches inhabited areas difficult access and evacuation. Valkyries displays this alert at the Command-and-Control Centre, preventing the population from being trapped by the flames by taking early action.

Own Operatives

- **Firefighters** and means to extinguishing both land and air fires are deployed cross-border.
- **Ambulances** of basic and advanced life support of the Emergency Medical SystemS, Red Cross and Civil Protection of both Spain and Portugal are activated.
- **Security forces** from both countries are activated.
- **HESE Hospital** is activated and remains ready to respond to the medical emergencies assigned.
- **Other Spanish health care institutions** might be included to plan and support assistance resources and decisions.

- **Advanced Command Post:** Organisation close to the emergency scenario that allows decision making and coordination close to the first responders on terrain.
 - Coordinate and direct the actions of all the action groups involved in the emergency in the affected area "in situ" in accordance with the instructions of the Plan Steering Committee, for which they will send it exhaustive information on the evolution of the risk.
 - Be in permanent contact with the EOC.
 - Inform the Incident Manager of the proposed measures and the evolution of the emergency.
 - Delimit the areas in the scene: Rescue, Relief and Base areas.
 - Request from the EOC the means that are necessary in the disaster zone.

Co-operating and neutral actors

Many citizens (volunteers) come with the intention of helping, collaborate in the evacuation and transfer victims to the Relief area.

Public and private institutions, such as municipalities or humanitarian aid organisations, provide logistical supplies (water, blankets, makeshift shelters)

Finally, the military forces join the emergency plan.

Coordinator's Assumptions

- The intra-organisational coordination of each organism involved is carried out according to its own procedures complemented by the information of VALKYRIES. In addition, there are collaboration protocols in case of MCI (Mass Casualty Incident) in cross-border areas.
- The CECOP is an EOC installed in the Emergency and Urgent Care Centre 1.1.2. of Extremadura, in Mérida, where the necessary means and resources are available to exercise the functions of coordination, control, monitoring, communication and centralization of the information necessary for the management of the emergency. (PLATERCAEX2019)

Limitations and constraints

Despite of protocols of joint action in MCI between Spain and Portugal, each country has a different operation systems that hinders communication and effective collaboration.

The first responders don't always have all the information.

The EOC has no real-time information.

The infrastructure of the **Emergency Operations Centre (EOC)** shall be appropriate for the following functions to be exercised there:

- Execute the actions entrusted by the Incident Manager and coordinate, control and monitor all actions for the attention of the emergency.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive notification of the emergency and, if applicable, always with the agreement of the INcident Manager, make the activation notices of the Plan. • To be the centre of the communications network that allows the functions of information, command and control. • Coordinate between plans at different levels. • Manage means and resources during the emergency. • According to the Public Information Office, transmit information to the various administrations and authorities. • Ensure that notification is made, as soon as possible, to the city council or affected municipalities, both in case of accidents and other events with perceptible effects capable of causing alarm in the field and coordinating with them the actions in their own municipality maintaining or contact with the people who hold the Municipal EOC of the affected municipalities. • Liaise with the Advanced Command Post (ACP) and Municipal EOC • There are different communication systems between the different commands and interveners that hinder effective communication and collaboration. <p>Local times are different between Spanish and Portuguese actors. The lack of communication with the interveners forces us to limit the capabilities of the communications network.</p>
	<p>Tactical end-states and objectives</p> <p>The end-state is achieved, when all the victims have been transferred to the reference hospitals and the fire has been temporary controlled to protect critical population centres. The tactical objective is to identify, provide initial care (first aid) and transfer victims to an optimal facility in the shortest possible time.</p>
<p>Emergency Support Activation Planning Description</p>	<p>VALKYRIES framework is applied to this forest fire emergency by identifying requirements, gaps, and actor's needs.</p> <p>Actors are trained on VALKYRIES framework and technological solutions to ensure their correct understanding and use.</p> <p>Virtual rehearsals have been carried out with each stakeholder separately.</p> <p>Regional/Local administrations are engaged and supportive to enable Localisations and allowed use for final the demo scenario.</p> <p>Dissemination tasks to cover all the preparation and execution process are identified to create interest in the social media and other means.</p>
<p>Execution</p>	<p>The characteristics of the fire require maximizing precautions in the intervention due to multiple factors . The indications of the firemen must be considered so as not to put at risk the safety of the interveners.</p> <p>Start time Time +0</p> <p>The first calls enter through the 112 alerting of several fires in the vicinity of San Vicente de Alcántara.</p>

The first responders are the firefighters of this town who warn of several victims of various considerations and 2 possible dead. They begin to collect basic incident information.

The Spanish coordinating centre 112 activates several health resources (3 basic ambulances and 2 advanced life support vehicles) that after arriving at the scene confirm multiple victims and initiate data collection..

According to information from the Guardia Civil, apparently a dry thunderstorm has caused several fires near the town of San Vicente de Alcántara.

Means of extinguishing fires are deployed both ground and air to stop the advance of the flames. Health and civil protection mean approach the points where there are victims to be treated. Security forces guarantee the arrival and rapid and safe evacuation of these points.

The rush to get out of the area affected by the fire, as well as the burning flora on the road, caused the accident of a bus traveling to Portalegre.

Time +0:30

As expected, Community resources are not sufficient for the scale of the incident and other means of neighbouring communities make their resources available to the Community. Portugal alerted to the danger deploys means of extinction, security, and health to stop the advance towards the place of the Sierra de San Mamede.

Time +0:45

The fires progress rapidly due to wind of 40 km / hour towards the natural park of Serra de S. Mamede, sweeping away everything in its path and endangering all nearby populations. These are evacuated preventively to safe areas until the danger passes.

The characteristics of the incident force the Spanish and Portuguese authorities to activate their respective emergency plans.

Time +1:00

The Portuguese cEOC 112 receives multiple calls alerting of 2 foci of fire in the area near the town of Marvão. The firefighters of this town are the first to intervene and like the Spanish case warn of multiple victims and 3 possible dead. They begin to collect essential information.

The Portuguese EOC 112 activates its own resources that, once at the scene, confirm multiple victims and begin to collect data.

The data provided shows the virulence of the fire and the difficulties in controlling it. There are also data of the number of victims in the **two Spanish foci** a total of 51 victims of various considerations (30 green (minimal); 9 yellow(delayed); 10 red (immediate) and 2 black (deceased) and in the two Portuguese **foci and** site a total of 49 victims of various considerations (20 green (minimal); 16 yellow

	<p>(delayed); 10 red (immediate) and 3 black (deceased). (Arcos González, y otros, 2016).</p> <p>Thanks to the location of the victims, the location of the advanced medical post is considered for the different fire sources. More resources are requested and hospitals in the area are alerted requesting the availability of beds in intensive care units.</p> <p><u>Time +1:30</u></p> <p>With the new data from both medical outposts, the triage counting, and Categorisation is updated. Transfer of the injured is requested according to the availability of hospitals, beds in intensive care units and fleet management.</p> <p><u>Time +2:00</u></p> <p>The victims are being transported according to its priority to the hospitals with the response capability available. (<i>SEE PROXIMITY HOSPITALS AND CARE LEVELS ACCORDING TO PATHOLOGIES</i>).</p> <p>During the transportation, victim health condition has been recorded and transmitted to the destination Hospital. Due to the capacity of the available hospitals, and the medical specialties required, a Spanish ambulance transports a Spanish victim to HESE, while a Portuguese ambulance transports a Portuguese victim to a Spanish hospital.</p> <p>The First Responders provide Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) to the destination hospital. (HOW IS THE HOSPITAL ALERT PERFORMED FOR CRITICAL PATIENTS? WEIGH AIR TRANSFER BY RESPONSE TIME, HOSPITALS WITH HELISURFACE INFRASTRUCTURE).</p> <p><u>Time +2:30</u></p> <p>The Spanish emergency coordination centre 112 receives several calls alerting of a new fire outbreak. Firefighters in the area confirm a small fire outbreak with no casualties. They collect data on the focus.</p>
<p>Tasks and business processes</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reception and management of the call to 112. 2. Mass Incident Declared 3. Exact location identification 4. Type of incident classification 5. Number of Casualties & Severity estimation 6. Hazard present identification and awareness 7. Access assessment 8. Activation of local resources according to their own protocols. 9. Establish Advanced Command Post 10. Arrival of the first resources that confirm the incident and initiate the collection of information.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Detection and activation of the units. 12. Enabling more resources and data collection. 13. Activation of the respective emergency plans. 14. Activation of the protocols of action in cross-border MCI. 15. Collection of information supplemented with SIGRUN solution information. 16. Supranational management of the incident with the activation of mobile resources, hospitals, etc. 17. Management of evacuation of wounded to optimal health centres. 18. Egress.
Coordination instructions	<p>Initially, the local protocols for the management of MCI will be applied until the activation of the joint protocols in the collaborative framework signed for the management of cross-border MCI. It is expected that the drill between Spain and Portugal will be carried out according to the drills scheduled biannually between both countries.</p>
Integrated support systems	<p>The services in charge of emergency management will use the usual communication devices such as TETRA, mobile telephony, and Tablet. Cross-border coordination will be facilitated with VALKYRIES.</p> <p>It would be desirable to use drones to provide more information on the geolocation of the fire sources.</p> <p>First aid vehicles data is shared through SIGRUN System, providing its location, response state, ETA to hospital, victims data.</p>
Services and Assets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical services information exchange • Fire control information exchange • Resources geolocation service • Emergency event log merging Spanish and Portuguese data • Common Operational Picture real time updated
VALKYRIES opportunities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication: SIGRUN will help to minimize the communications by classic methods such as TETRA or telephony. 2. Traceability of information: SIGRUN solution ensures maximum traceability of the data collected by each user. 3. Security: the SIGRUN multilayer system maximizes data security according to the access profile of each user. 4. Integration of multidisciplinary information: all the information collected is integrated in real time to nourish horizontally all those involved. 5. The standardisation and harmonisation of data will provide a unique opportunity for each user to manage their tasks regardless of the place of action and in a multilingual way.

Table 20 - Emergency support activation planning information UC1

8.3. Threat scenario

Threat	<p>Terrain level threat</p> <p>Loss of communication due to coverage problems. Different communication systems between the first responders. Procedures, protocols, taxonomies, and references although similar, may have different interpretations and responses, which can lead to confusion or erroneous decision making. Difficulties with the languages. The intelligent communications network must support the communications of all the participants and be modified as needed. Victims' wearables may fail and there must be a contingency plan to move the information to the new device The information can be retrieved due to the order of recording communications from different devices, which allow the puzzle to be mounted.</p>
	<p>Planning level threat</p> <p>Scattered information for the detection of risks due to the orographic characteristics of the fire in high mountains. Difficult cross-border coordination due to multiple factors such as language, legislative and operational barriers.</p>
Effect	<p>Terrain-level Effect</p> <p>SIGRUN with its multiple levels of operation, according to the technological characteristics and harmonisation, can solve this type of problems that in case of counter could put at risk the optimal management of the MCI if it is not solved.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Effect</p> <p>SIGRUN will provide cross-sectional information to all users according to their user profile, maximizing cross-border coordination and eliminating language, legislative and operational barriers.</p>
Impact	<p>Terrain-level Impact</p> <p>It will improve communications between the participants, reduce the time-to-response, increase the accuracy of the actions, decrease impact on people and other assets.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Impact</p> <p>Coordination for cross-border MCI management will be improved. Avoid time for validations since there is common and harmonized information, reduce decision making timing and increase visibility on resources availability.</p>

Table 21 - Threat scenario UC1

8.4. Mishap's response and risk mitigation plans, objectives and countermeasures

<p>CoA (Course of Action) - Terrain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey of forest fire area • Identification of victims • Alert area hospitals • Mobilize medical responders to terrain. • Contact off-duty personnel for possible recall. • Alert outlying hospitals. • Establish command post • Set up incident operations area (Security perimeter, staging area, transport corridor, treatment area) • Set up triage teams, collation teams, treatment teams according to META. • Victims' health data exchange • Transport casualties to health centres • Fire fighters' protection of specific are • Contact traffic authority for secondary transport options. • Civil traffic deviation • Alert administration authorities Mayor and or Governor offices • Restricted area delimitation • Communication to civil citizens & media • Evacuation • Fire extinguish action • Demobilisation of resources
<p>CoA-Planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responders resource availability analysis • First responders resource ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) analysis • First responders' awareness • Risk analysis • Comms network coverage and capabilities assessment and contingency plans analysis • Review of communication processes and availability across the different hierarchy levels during the MCI and different countries involved. • CoA Impact assessment • What If scenarios
<p>Mishap's response and risk mitigation objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimisation of number of victims • Reduction of casualties' severity • Minimize ETA

CoA level of automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control civil panic impact • Increase first responders' safety • Better situational awareness <p>Decisions to make are always monitored and not automated. The tool suggests changes or decision making. The tool displays the relevant data for decision making Comms integrated across first responder's actors.</p>
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Table 22 - Mishap's response and risk mitigation plans, objectives, and countermeasures UC1

8.5. Traceability and observability

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimal incident management minimizing telecommunications failures on MCI with forest fire emergencies on mountainous terrain. - Standardisation and harmonisation of MCD when collaborating on triage and transportation on different countries. - Minimize data loss across the planning and execution with different actors involved. - Effective work with wearables distributed to victims and 1st Interveners - Communication between wearables and the Management app - Incident takeover created by 112 - Creation of Communications Network for First Responders. - (recommended) Effective work with wearables distributed to victims and 1st Responders. - Potential Communication between the wearables and the SIGRUN solution. - Collection and use of the MCD for VALKYRIES solution - Potential use of SIGRUN solution with its different work profiles, such as triage, casualty stabilisation, resources, SCUE (Emergency and Urgency Coordination Service), and command and control. - Decrease time in decision making such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Priority of care classification on terrain o Evacuation decision from forest fire area o Assignment of transfer hospital in Spain and Portugal - Traceability of the injured across the different actors involved either in Portugal or Spain. - (recommended) Information obtained through wearables
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REQ_COM_T3.4_3 Minimum Common Data (MCD)VALKYRIES solution availability - REQ_BASE_T4.2_1 Trusted communication of end-user terminals with the infrastructure

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REQ_COM_T4.2_1 Sufficient communication capabilities between devices - REQ_COM_T4.2_2 Integration with existing communication technologies - REQ_COM_T4.2_3 Optimal network technology selection - REQ_COM_T4.2_4 Communication availability between devices - REQ_COM_T4.3_8 Agile intercommunication between wearables and C&C - REQ_COM_T4.5_2 Data transmission to SIGRUN - REQ_BASE_T6.2_1 Education and Training for first aid response
<p style="text-align: center;">Observable Effects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SIGRUN obtains information from the incident generated by 112 - SIGRUN is nourished by information from the distributed wearables - SIGRUN offers the crossing of operational data and incorporates data into the system from its collaborative capacity for information sharing - Elimination of language and procedural barriers - Real-time information for decision making - Decision making with more valuable information - Full traceability of the incident - Digitisation of clinical data and the course of the incident - Effective real-time communication between Command Post, Intervention Point and Hospitals involved in victim treatments - The information recorded on the wearables is reflected in the SIGRUN solution as it is incorporated into the app. - The information is recorded throughout the triage, treatment, and transfer decision. - SIGRUN provides cross-referencing of data from the operation and incorporates data into the system from its collaborative information sharing capabilities. It occurs throughout the entire exercise - Relevant data from other agencies or services are incorporated as incident data to be considered. Example, security forces cut off several access roads, etc. - This data is generated externally throughout the exercise for the verification of this service. - Elimination of language and procedural barriers - SIGRUN will have a common and international language (English) and the official language of the country if it can be incorporated. - More information, faster, better, and safer for decision making. - Information on victims, number, priority, location, etc., are reflected from the first communications between first responders and command post. - Information on deployed resources, types of resources, manning, functions in the field, their operational movements, times in each status, fatigue control for relays, etc.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Information on scene security through coordination with security forces. This information is captured in the form of information layers and alerts.- Alerts are created to warn of adequate sizing between victims and deployment of resources, crew fatigue, transfer of territories, lack of communication with different middle management,- Better incident traceability- SIGRUN offers traceability data by patient, resource, intervention point, victim priority, transfers to hospital, execution times of all resources, etc.- Digitisation of clinical data and the course of the incident on a consultation platform, creating an indelible record of the incident.- Effective real-time communication between Command Post, Intervention Point and Hospitals involved, through the VALKYRIES app and conventional radio media. Verified through computer feedback using timestamp-based communications.
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Table 23 - Traceability and observability UC1

9. Annex C – Use Case #2

9.1. Scenario description

Identifier	UC-VALKYRIES-02
Overview description of VALKYRIES usage	<p>Cross-Border emergency intervention (toxic leakage) Slovakia-Italy</p> <p>VALKYRIES provide a common framework to address solutions that might improve cross-border and cross-sectorial cooperation between Italy and Slovakia for first responders to manage a toxic plume leak that reach a near Morava River due to a technological incident caused by industrial fire. Victims' identification and health assistance of the potential casualties might be better supervised and managed across the different first responders and medical services reducing the impact on citizens. Data exchanged and shared across different emergency actors, harmonized protocols, and tools standardisation reduce the time-to-response, with a more accurate and efficient coordinated actuations.</p> <p>Number of people have serious symptoms and need immediate treatment. Toxic plum is heading to the densely populated part of town as well as to close village in Italy a, right on the second side of the river. Due to the weather conditions, it is highly probable that toxicity will be serious even after at least 10 kilometres.</p> <p>For the purpose of the project the extinguishing of the fire will not be subject of the use-case. It is expected that fire is not spreading and Fire and Rescue Service (FRS) will manage it base on their Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) without any additional needs/requirements.</p>
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens • ISEMI together with Moi SR (FRS – Fire&Rescue Service, Police, CP – Civil Protection) • IRS – (Integrated Rescue System) • Italian Civil Protection • Italian Fire Brigades • Emergency Medical Service (AREU)
Potential related tools	<p>On the Slovak side and for such a case it is a system of Integrated Rescue System which is used (based on 112 number). FRS and ambulances are deployed as well as police and civil protection.</p> <p>Unfortunately, there is no official bilateral agreement between SK and IT on cooperation (excluding UCPM – Union Civil Protection Mechanism). Cooperation is based on personal relations of related units and its representatives, these exists, it means that certain level of cooperation will be ensured.</p>

	<p>(To better identify capacities of Austria it would be good to involve Austrian FRS units – on region, Notruf144 and/or Austrian Red Cross).</p> <p>Potential related tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile comms • Radio comms • GNSS information • SIGRUN
<p>Potential data sources</p>	<p>It is expected that phone call to the number 112 is received, together with basic (standardized) information gathered by call-officer. Next data will come from responders arriving at the spot as first (FRS). And subsequently after arriving of special units. Weather conditions are available directly from Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute.</p> <p>Potential data sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather information • Geographical information • GNSS location from vehicles, mobile devices. • Drone information • First responder’s database • Electronic Health Records (EHR) • Victims’ health data • First Aid Vehicles (FAV) data

Table 24 - Scenario description UC2

9.2. Emergency support activation planning information

<p>Background</p>	<p>The geographical scenario is located at Stupava, Zohor and north-western part of Bratislava - Devínska Nová Ves. Close to Morava River and the borders with Italy. This industrial area with different non-active materials and hazard ones required for manufacturing. Workers and citizens on surroundings are actively present since early in the mornings till close of business.</p> <p>Industrial accidents might include different dangers: architecture damage, fire, hazard material exposure on air or even leaked to water resources close to the location.</p> <p>Unstable weather is usual and might be an obstacle for first responder activities and evolution of disaster might be worse.</p> <p>Effective coordination for first responders assessing the situation and acting at early stages may limit the impact of the disaster in the industrial area and surroundings.</p>
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Especial first responder's units for dealing with hazard materials are usually engaged on industrial areas with this specificness.

Strategical
and
Operational
Vignettes

Figure 7 - Incident location UC2

Figure 8 - Industrial explosion disaster

Current
situation

Overall Description

Toxic plumb containing isocyanates is spreading by wind to Bratislava (SK) and Lombardy (IT). It is Monday morning, people are travelling to work, children to school. Emergency calls are coming to the Integrated Rescue System (IRS) reporting more-less the same problems. Situation needs activation of ambulances on national level as well as special units. Capacities of close hospitals started to be full.

	<p>Own Operatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambulances from Bratislava and Trnava region will be mobilized. • Other special units: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Police (CBRN unit) ○ FRS (FR team as well as HAZMAT unit) ○ Control Chemical Laboratory
	<p>Co-operating and neutral actors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Military forces – CBRN ones might be considered if the chemical substance will be confirmed as possible warfare agent. • Universities and institutes – Chemical related faculties/departments, respectively their laboratories might be used for analysis if requested...
	<p>Coordinator's Assumptions</p> <p>Response action is coordinated by FRS and using procedures, forces, and resources of IRS.</p>
	<p>Limitations and constraints.</p> <p>Coordination with Italy is not possible immediately. Bilateral agreement is missing. Suitable channels for information exchange are missing as well.</p>
	<p>Tactical end-states and objectives</p> <p>The end-state is achieved, when leakage of chemical is located, toxicity of the cloud is below life threatening level and all reported injuries are managed (threatened or hospitalized).</p>
<p>Emergency Support Activation Planning Description</p> <p>From the point of view of software support it is the CoordCom which is used for coordination and planning. It contains GIS with different map layers, it is possible to measure distances as well as draw/specify areas. However, this has to be done manually. Subsequently it is possible to display which units of Integrated Rescue System (IRS) are assigned for area, what forces and resources is available and take related decisions. For FRS units (only for them) there is also GINA system which is an extension of CoordCom. MATRA system represents personal units for use during the rescue action. These units are using digital network. SITNO is digital communication network. Connection to this network is managed by Mol of SR and is a subject of strict rules.</p> <p>VALKYRIES framework is applied to this forest fire emergency by identifying requirements, gaps and actor's needs.</p> <p>Actors are trained on VALKYRIES framework and technological solutions to ensure their correct understanding and use.</p> <p>Virtual rehearsals have been carried out with each stakeholder separately.</p> <p>Regional/Local administrations are engaged and supportive to enable Localisations and allowed use for final the demo scenario.</p> <p>Dissemination tasks to cover all the preparation and execution process are identified to create interest in the social media and other means.</p>	
<p>Execution</p> <p>First Aid is provided by responders coming as first on the place (FRS) to save lives and minimize damage to health. Subsequently and immediately after arrival of</p>	

ambulances and paramedics specialized care will be provided (triage, treatment, transport to hospital if necessary and related admission of patients).

As this is chemical incident, zoning have to be carried out, based on first measurements, detection, and threat identification. "CBRN incident SOP" will be applied.

Most probably responders will have to work in PPE (personal protective equipment).

Contamination of victims have to be taken into consideration (treatment, transport, hospitalisation, etc.)

Chronology of events:

Time of emergency call: Monday, 6:30 AM.

Explosion/fire in the private company storing different materials – waste dump storing also dangerous materials – has been reported to emergency number 112. Number of people have serious symptoms (vomiting, burning eyes, nose and throat, also respiratory problems) as well as mortal victims are possible.

Company is situated between Stupava, Zohor and north-western part of Bratislava - Devínska Nová Ves. Close to Morava River and the borders with Italy.

Time after the first intervention of FRS: 6:50 AM.

Fire in the landfill has extended to the part where plastic waste is stored, mainly the products containing polyurethane foams, paints, and coatings (company is approved to store such a materials). Total quantity is estimated about 50 tons at least. Due to the presence and explosions of highly flammable substances, the fire spreads very quickly and reaches a temperature of up to 600 degrees Celsius.

3 dead persons have been identified so far together with number of injured. They are complaining of vision loss, burning eyes, nose and throat, difficulty to breath – this looks to be main cause of death.

It is cold weather, soft northeast wind (1 to 2 degree of Beaufort scale, direction 25°). It is highly probable that similar symptoms will occur in Devínska Nová Ves and in border area of Italy. Area of 50 km² have to be immediately secured and monitored.

Responders have to use personal protective equipment (PPE). Contamination of persons have to be taken into consideration. Special (specific) units – HAZMAT Teams and other related forces have to be deployed immediately.

In meantime, number of emergency calls have been received from this area. People have serious problems and need medical treatment. Number of ambulances have been deployed. It is necessary to manage removal of the wounded because some hospitals reports admitting patient issues.

Fire and Rescue Service (FRS) of Slovakia is in contact with counterparts in Austria. Situation is similar there. This is not official way of contact (only personal-based). European Union Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) has not been activated so far.

	<p>Police (CBRN unit) is coming to the spot as well. There is a well-founded fear that a crime has taken place. They are also providing measurements, detection, and identification of chemicals in the area.</p> <p><i>NOTICE: for the needs of the project the premises of Mol SR will be used for demonstration. It is in the same area.</i></p>
<p>Tasks and business processes</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reception and management of the call to 112 2. Mass Incident Declared 3. Exact location identification 4. Type of incident classification 5. Number of Casualties & Severity estimation 6. Hazard present identification and awareness 7. Access assessment 8. Activation of local resources according to their own protocols. (Activation of forces, deployment of first unit(s) – FRS) 9. Establish Command Post 10. Arrival of the first resources that confirm the incident and initiate the collection of information according to MCD. (Evaluation of situation by FRS on site and reporting to the C2 (command and control – IRS), application of related SOP) 11. Detection and activation of the multi-victim incident protocol. 12. Enabling more resources and data collection (In this case it is obvious that this is MCI (multi-casualty incident) – so it means activation of more forces and resources (ambulances/choppers, specialized HAZMAT/CBRN teams – civil protection, police, army...) 13. Activation of the respective emergency plans. (Preparation for admission of injuries in hospitals) 14. Activation of the protocols of action in cross-border MCI. (Prepared for multi-regional response actions (activation of forces and recourses on national level, considering request for international help – firstly based on bilateral agreements with bordering countries (in this case CZ), theoretically on EU level (EUCPM). 15. Collection of information supplemented with SIGRUN solution information. 16. Supranational management of the incident with the activation of mobile resources, hospitals, etc. 17. Management of evacuation of wounded to optimal health centres. 18. Egress
<p>Coordination instructions</p>	<p>Coordination is provided by IRS. Actions on side are managed by commander of FRS unit.</p>
<p>Integrated support systems</p>	<p>It is the radio-stations and mobile phones which are used for communication and information exchange.</p>

	<p>There are tablets available on the board of FRS vehicles, but their use is limited mainly to navigation, respectively as database of SOPs, library of for example chemical substances and their properties, etc.</p> <p>In this case also, drones would be used for reconnaissance and monitoring, but this is not fully ready (drones are more in the initial phase of implementation).</p> <p>Furthermore, for major incident (like also this one), there is available mobile command-staff vehicle equipped with communication technology, PCs, connection to the internet.</p> <p>In specific case like this, it is also possible to use long distance detector – spectrometer SIGIS II, which can detect hazardous chemicals in the air at up to 5 km.</p> <p>First aid vehicles data is shared through the VALKYRIES System, providing its location, response state, ETA to hospital, victims data.</p>
<p>Services and Assets</p>	<p>In Slovakia, it is the civil protection whose role is to ensure whole logistic of the transfer of larger population (evacuation). From this point of view, it is therefore important to know the potentially endangered area so that they can activate the cadastral relevant components. National Civil Protection Authority is Mol SR – Section of Crisis Management. They are part of IRS, of course.</p> <p>In case of already injured persons, it is the Emergency service (pre - hospital emergency health care). This subject manages whole logistic related to injuries based on their own trauma plans. It is under Ministry of Health of SR, and it is also part of IRS.</p> <p>In case of need of decontamination of larger number of persons, it is the FRS who dispose with mobile decontamination line (capacity about 60 persons/hour). The closest one is in Malacky (about 30 km from the incident place) and preparation needs about 2 hours.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical services information exchange - Fire control information exchange - Resources geolocation service - Emergency event log merging Slovak and Austria data - Hazard material sample tracking management and data exchange - Drone services and data exchange <p>Common Operational Picture real time updated</p>
<p>VALKYRIES opportunities</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication: Between different responders' units (FRS, ambulances, police, hospitals) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Improved both way information exchange between responders and C2 o Between C2s of the neighbouring countries in case of incident affecting more than one country. 2. Traceability of information: SIGRUN solution ensures maximum traceability of the data collected by each actor (important facts (for police investigation, for evaluation...)).

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Security: the SIGRUN multilayer system maximizes data security according to the access profile of each user. 4. Integration of multidisciplinary information: all the information collected is integrated in real time to nourish horizontally all those involved (effectively deploy the forces and resources). 5. The standardisation and harmonisation of data will provide a unique opportunity for each user to manage their tasks regardless of the place of action and in a multilingual way. 6. Current status is, that almost whole communication is provided F2F (verbally / personally). All the parts (units) of IRS communicate on digital network SITNO. In principle, all the responders can communicate together also. Mostly responders within one unit communicate with own operator and the operators communicate with each other, just it is not used in practice. For larger events (like this one), the individual units communicate through the C2 staffs and their liaison officers.
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Table 25 - Emergency support activation planning information UC2

9.3. Threat scenario

Threat	<p>Terrain level threat</p> <p>Different communication systems between the first responders and countries.</p> <p>Identification of hazard materials and toxic leakage at early stage and safely.</p> <p>Use of drones on cross borders areas might be affected by unmanned vehicles regulations.</p> <p>Procedures, protocols, taxonomies, and references although similar, may have different interpretations and responses, which can lead to confusion or erroneous decision making.</p> <p>Difficulties with the languages.</p> <p>The intelligent communications network must support the communications of all the participants and be modified as needed.</p> <p>The information can be retrieved due to the order of recording communications from different devices, which allow the puzzle to be mounted. In case of request for help from Italy, there will be complication to cross the border river. This would be ensured by using close cycle bridge.</p> <p>Planning-level Threat</p> <p>Quick and accurate identification of chemical threat (substances and its effects and subsequently the optimal means to localize and minimize damage) – there is room for improvements.</p>
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	<p>Unmanned vehicles regulation might affect the drone deployment and use.</p> <p>Also, with determining the affected area, its Visualisation and sharing with related persons.</p> <p>Difficult cross-border coordination due to multiple factors such as language, legislative and operational barriers.</p>
Effect	<p>Terrain-level Effect</p> <p>It is expected, that are is easily accessible by common means (it is business organisation). So, no effects are expected.</p> <p>SIGRUN with its multiple levels of operation, according to the technological characteristics and harmonisation, can solve this type of problems that in case of counter could put at risk the optimal management of the MCI if it is not solved.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Effect</p> <p>Improved tools can make intervention more effective.</p> <p>VALKYRIES framework to harmonize cross border regulation on MCI and SIGRUN solution will provide cross-sectional information to all users according to their user profile, maximizing cross-border coordination and eliminating language, legislative and operational barriers.</p>
Impact	<p>Terrain-level Impact</p> <p>It will improve communications between the participants, reduce the time-to-response, increase the accuracy of the actions, decrease impact on people, environment, and other assets. Finally, as a consequence, the effectiveness and quick response on toxic leakage will reduce the impact on casualties and natural resources.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Impact</p> <p>If responders know exactly what and where is the threat, they can take appropriate means (not to waste forces and resources where it is not necessary)</p> <p>Avoid time for validations since there is common and harmonized information, reduce decision making timing and increase visibility on resources availability.</p>

Table 26 - Threat scenario UC2

9.4. Mishap’s response and risk mitigation plans, objectives, and countermeasures

<p>CoA (Course of Action) - Terrain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ambulances and other responders will come by cars (there are existing roads) – no special need and action is expected. - Helicopters are not expected. - Survey of toxic and leakage area - Identification of victims - Mobilize medical responders to terrain. - Alert area hospitals - Alert outlying hospitals. - Establish command post - Set up incident operations area (Security perimeter, staging area, transport corridor, treatment area) - Set up triage teams, collection teams, treatment teams. - Victims’ health data gathering and control - Contact off-duty personnel for possible recall. - Transport casualties to health centres - Fire fighters/HAZMAT team protection of specific area - Drone deployment - Toxic sample collection and analysis - Contact traffic authority for secondary transport options. - Civil traffic deviation - Restricted area delimitation - Communication to civil citizens & media - Evacuation - Fire extinguish action - Toxic samples extraction and analysis - Civil traffic deviation - Alert administration authorities Mayor and or Governor offices - Evacuation - Fire extinguish action - Demobilisation of resources
<p>CoA-Planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First responders resource availability analysis - First responders resource ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) analysis - First responders’ awareness - Risk analysis (HAZMAT scenarios) - Comms network coverage and capabilities assessment and contingency plans analysis

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Review of communication processes and availability across the different hierarchy levels during the MCI and different countries involved.- CoA Impact assessment- What If scenarios
Mishap's response and risk mitigation objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Minimisation of number of victims- Minimisation of toxic leakage impact- Better situational awareness- Reduction of casualties' severity- Minimize ETA- Control civil panic impact- Increase first responders' safety
CoA level of automation	Decisions to make are always monitored and not automated. Real time information for decision making. The tool displays the relevant data for decision making.

Table 27 - Mishap's response and risk mitigation plans, objectives and countermeasures UC2

9.5. Traceability and observability

<p style="text-align: center;">Objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardisation and harmonisation of MCD when collaborating on triage and transportation on different countries. - Minimize data loss across the planning and execution with different actors involved. - Collection and use of the MCD for VALKYRIES solution - Potential use of SGRUN solution with its different work profiles, such as triage, casualty stabilisation, resources, SCUE (Emergency and Urgency Coordination Service), and command and control. - Decrease time in decision making such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Priority of care classification on terrain o Evacuation decision from toxic area o Assignment of transfer hospital in Slovakia and/or Italy - Traceability of the injured across the different actors involved either in Slovakia or Italy. - Integrate drone information in SGRUM to get more complete situational awareness
<p style="text-align: center;">Requirements</p>	<p>Involving of experts/representatives from different actors (different sectors), including ones from related bordering country. Namely FRS, IRS, police, ambulances, civil protection. Some other are under consideration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REQ_COM_T3.4_3 Minimum Common Data (MCD)VALKYRIES solution availability - REQ_BASE_T4.1_2 Self-driving and unmanned vehicles - REQ_BASE_T4.2_1 Trusted communication of end-user terminals with the infrastructure - REQ_COM_T4.2_1 Sufficient communication capabilities between devices - REQ_COM_T4.2_2 Integration with existing communication technologies - REQ_COM_T4.2_3 Optimal network technology selection - REQ_COM_T4.2_4 Communication availability between devices - REQ_COM_T4.5_2 Data transmission to SGRUN - REQ_BASE_T6.2_1 Education and Training for first aid response

Observable Effects	EMCD available across the different systems <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integration of unmanned vehicles information on SIGRUN• Real time information availability across the different devices (Data delay minimum of X seconds)• VALKYRIES framework awareness (Number of people applying VALKYRIES framework)
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Table 28 - Traceability and observability UC2

10. Annex D – Use Case #3

10.1. Scenario description

Identifier	UC-VALKYRIES-03
Overview description of VALKYRIES usage	<p>Cross-Border emergency intervention (Earthquake) Bulgaria and Greece</p> <p>VALKYRIES provide a common framework to address solutions that might improve cross-border cooperation between Bulgaria and Greece for first responders to manage earthquake casualties, assess earthquake impact on area and population. Victims' identification and health assistance of the potential casualties might be better supervised and managed across the different first responders and medical services reducing the impact on citizens. Data exchanged and shared across different emergency actors, harmonized protocols, and tools standardisation reduce the time-to-response, with a more accurate and efficient coordinated actuations.</p>
Actors	<p>The participants in this use case are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Bulgarian Red Cross and the Hellenic Rescue Team providing assistance to affected population in the cross-border area, humanitarian aid and restoring family links • The Bulgarian Fire Brigade and Hellenic Fire Brigade – first responders implementing emergency rescue and emergency recovery activities (observers) • The Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service and the Hellenic National Centre for Emergency Assistance providing emergency medical aid (one ambulance team from the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy will be deployed on the spot) • Local authorities from Bulgaria and Greece providing logistical support and coordination (observers) • State civil protection authorities responsible for management and coordination (observers) • The Hellenic Earthquake Planning and Protection Organisation (EPPO) (observers)
Potential related tools	<p>On the Bulgarian side there is an integrated Rescue System based on 112 number. Fire brigade, police and ambulances are deployed in case of disasters.</p> <p>Similarly, a Greek 112 is in place that is supposed to deliver appropriate messages to relevant stakeholders and, when necessary, the general public. There is no official bilateral agreement between Bulgaria and Greece on cooperation, excluding EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM). The cooperation is based on the</p>

	<p>established personal relations of related units on both sides of the border which means that certain level of mutual aid will be ensured. The transborder cooperation in case of crisis is also supported by few relevant initiatives, such as the <i>Cross Border Cooperation Network of Greece, Bulgaria, and Turkey Prefectures</i>, which, even though it is official, has no constitutional role.</p> <p>To improve the capabilities for reaction in such kind of cross-border multi-victims' disasters, it would be needed to involve Specialised CBRN unit from the Bulgarian Armed Forces as first responders in case of CBRN, emergency rescue and emergency recovery activities. In addition, it would be useful to involve as observers the Bulgarian Police and the Hellenic Police – law enforcement agencies responsible for maintenance of public order.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile comms • Radio comms • GNSS / GALILEO information • SIGRUN
<p>Potential data sources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather information • Seismic information • Traffic information • Critical infrastructure information on area • Geographical information • GNSS location from vehicles, mobile devices. • Drone information • First responder's database • Electronic Health Records (EHR) • Victims' health data

Table 29 - Scenario description UC3

10.2. Emergency support activation planning information

<p>Background</p>	<p>Cross-border crisis as an earthquake result in the border area between Bulgaria and Greece.</p> <p>A strong earthquake caused a series of humanitarian crises and industrial accidents threatening the lives of the population in the Bulgarian-Greek border area.</p> <p>Location: Southwestern Bulgaria, Bulgarian-Greek border area. The town of Petrich and the Logodazh Dam on the Bulgarian territory.</p>
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Strategical and Operational Vignettes

Figure 9 - Incident location UC3

Current situation

Overall Description

As a result of an earthquake with a magnitude of 6.5 on the Richter scale with an epicentre around the town of Petrich (Bulgaria), there is a great number of affected people with several victims in the worst affected municipalities. Hundreds of families lost their homes, there is a severely damaged infrastructure, destroyed residential buildings, farm buildings and warehouses in the Blagoevgrad district (Bulgaria).

The earthquake caused the failure of a reservoir and the leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile at a polymer plant in the town of Petrich. In addition, the integrity of the refrigeration system in vegetable refrigerated warehouses has been disrupted, due to large amounts of ammonia continue to leak.

At the same time, as a result of heavy rainfall during the last 10 days, there have been significant spills and partial floods along the Struma and Mesta rivers within the Bulgarian territory. Almost all settlements in the regions along the two rivers are affected. There is unconfirmed information regarding the presence of a crack in the wall of Logodzh Dam, and its size and the degree of risk of its failure have not been specified yet.

The telephone connection, including the connection of the mobile operators, has been disrupted, which makes communication in the area and request for support from neighbouring countries (incl. Greece) and

EUCPM difficult. A large part of the water supply network around the epicentre of the earthquake was destroyed.

The resulting panic among the population of the larger affected settlements such as the towns of Kresna, Sandanski and Melnik has led to the concentration of cars and trucks on their entry and exit roads and hinders the traffic. Extremely busy traffic is observed on the main road E-79 in the direction to the border checkpoint with Greece "Kulata-Promachonas" and the national road III-106 in the direction to the border checkpoint-with Northern Macedonia "Logodazh" (Former "Stanke Lisichkovo"). This is a result of the hundreds of citizens of the Hellenic Republic and the Republic of Northern Macedonia leaving the affected area, vacationing in Sandanski, Melnik and other resorts in the southwestern part of the Republic of Bulgaria.

Own Operatives

Ambulances from the towns of Blagoevgrad, Sandanski, Petrich and the city of Sofia have been mobilized. The regional units of the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population", the regional directorate of the Bulgarian Police in Blagoevgrad, Sandanski and Petrich, as well as the Military CBRN unit in Blagoevgrad has been activated.

The Bulgarian mayors of the towns of Blagoevgrad, Sandanski, Petrich and the Regional Governors of Blagoevgrad and Sofia District are activated, and they implement the plans of the Regional Disaster Risk Reduction Councils.

The Voluntary formations, established at municipal level that are under the direct authority of the mayors of the affected municipalities, and which are an integral part of the unified rescue system are activated.

It is expected representatives of the Hellenic National Centre for Emergency Assistance and units of Hellenic Fire Brigade to provide support to the Bulgarian authorities.

The Disaster Risk Reduction Council at the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria is informed about the emerging disaster situation and assistance at national level is requested by the local authorities.

A specialised emergency medical team from the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy is also deployed.

Co-operating and neutral actors

Military unit – CBRN one has to be considered. There is a leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile and therefore specialised expertise is needed.

Universities and institutes in Blagoevgrad, Sofia, as well as Greek partners – chemical related faculties/departments, respectively their laboratories might be used for analysis if requested.

	<p>Coordinator's Assumptions</p> <p>The disaster response action is coordinated by the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Ministry of Interior (Mol) in close cooperation with the Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service (towns of Blagoevgrad, Sandanski and Petrich), the local authorities, police, military unit, and the Greek counterparts.</p> <p>Limitations and constraints.</p> <p>Coordination with Greek counterparts is not possible immediately. Bilateral agreement is not in place. Suitable channels for information exchange are missing, as well. A Common Alerting Protocol, as also mentioned above, needs to be in place.</p> <p>Tactical end-states and objectives</p> <p>The end-state is achieved, when the destruction of the Logodazh Dam is prevented, the results from the floods are under control, the leakage of chemicals is identified, the toxicity of the cloud is below -threatening level and all reported injuries are managed (threatened or hospitalized).</p>
<p>Emergency Support Activation Planning Description</p>	<p>From the point of view of software support, it is the CSAM CoordCom (previously Carmenta CoordCom) which is a fully integrated platform for 112 and emergency response, including call-taking, communication, case handling and dispatching can be used. TappingCoordCom, 112 operators and dispatchers can control and coordinate the entire chain of emergency or incident events, from receiving and identifying an incoming emergency call or sensor alarm to dispatching the correct resources to the incident location, quickly and with maximum efficiency. VALKYRIES framework is applied to this earthquake emergency by identifying requirements, gaps, and actor's needs.</p> <p>Actors are trained on VALKYRIES framework and technological solutions to ensure their correct understanding and use.</p> <p>Virtual rehearsals have been carried out with each stakeholder separately.</p> <p>Regional/Local administrations are engaged and supportive to enable localisations and allowed use for final the demo scenario.</p> <p>Dissemination tasks to cover all the preparation and execution process are identified to create interest in the social media and other means.</p>
<p>Execution</p>	<p>First Aid is provided by responders coming first on the place from the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Mol, the Bulgarian Emergency ambulance services in the towns of Blagoevgrad, Sandanski and Petrich, as well the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy to save lives and minimize damage to health. Subsequently and immediately after arrival of ambulances and paramedics specialized care will be provided (triage, treatment, transport to hospital if necessary and related admission of patients) in</p>

the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy and regional hospitals in Blagoevgrad, Sandanski and Petrich.

As this is a disaster including chemicals linkage incident, zoning have to be carried out, based on first measurements, detection, and threat identification. "CBRN incident SOP" will be applied.

Most probably the first responders will have to work in PPE (Personal Protective Equipment).

Potential contamination of victims needs to be taken into consideration (treatment, transport, hospitalisation, etc.)

Chronological events:

Time of emergency call: Sunday, 5:43 AM.

The National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Science identified an earthquake with a magnitude of 6.5 on the Richter scale with an epicentre around the town of Petrich (Bulgaria). There is a great number of affected people with several victims in the worst affected municipalities. The earthquake caused the failure of a reservoir and the leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile at a polymer plant in the town of Petrich which has been reported to emergency number 112.

At the same time, because of heavy rainfall during the last 10 days, there have been significant spills and partial floods along the Struma and Mesta rivers within the Bulgarian territory.

There is unconfirmed information regarding the presence of a crack on the body of Logodazh Dam, and its size and the degree of risk of its failure have not been specified yet.

Time after the intervention of the first aid responders: 06:00 AM.

The General Directorate (GD) "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Ministry of Interior of the Republic of Bulgaria is deployed.

The Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service is also deployed, as well as regional units from the Bulgarian Police. It is expected a Military CBRN unit to arrive soon.

The Bulgarian authorities are in contact with the counterparts in Greece. This is not an official way of contact, yet only personal-based. EUCPM has not been activated so far. Upon notification of the Greek authorities (even through personal contact), Greek forces are in alert to act when asked and the Greek 112 issues mass alerts to citizens that are close the borders (on the Greek side).

	<p>The telephone connection, including the connection of the mobile operators, has been disrupted, which makes communication in the area difficult. A large part of the water supply network in the area of the epicentre of the earthquake was destroyed.</p>
<p>Tasks and business processes</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reception and management of the call to 112. 2. Mass Incident Declared 3. Exact location identification 4. Type of incident classification 5. Number of Casualties & Severity estimation 6. Hazard present identification and awareness 7. Access assessment 8. Activation of local resources according to their own protocols. (In this case it is obvious that this is MCI (Multi-Casualty Incident) – so it means activation of more forces and resources (ambulances/choppers, specialized CBRN teams – civil protection, police, army units, etc.) 9. Establish Command Post 10. Arrival of the first resources that confirm the incident and initiate the collection of information according to MCD. (Evaluation of situation by the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian MoI on site and reporting through the national C2 (Command and Control) system, application of related SOPs. 11. Detection and activation of the multi-victim incident protocol. 12. Enabling more resources and data collection (In this case it is obvious that this is MCI (multi-casualty incident) – so it means activation of more forces and resources (ambulances/choppers, specialized CBRN team – civil protection, police, etc.) 13. Activation of the respective emergency plans. (Preparation for admission of injuries in hospitals) 14. Activation of the protocols of action in cross-border MCI. (Preparing for multi-regional response actions (activation of forces and recourses on national level, considering request for international help from Greece and theoretically on EU level (EUCPM). 15. Collection of information supplemented with SIGRUN solution information. 16. Supranational management of the incident with the activation of mobile resources, hospitals, etc. (Preparing for multi-regional response actions (Activation of forces and recourses on national level, considering request for help from Greek counterparts and other bordering countries, as well as on EU level based on the EUCPM).

	<p>17. Management of evacuation of wounded to optimal health centres.</p>
<p>Coordination instructions</p>	<p>Coordination on site is provided GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Mol. Actions are coordinated with the local and medical authorities, police, and the military unit.</p> <p>In this scenario, all three types of cross-cutting aspects in response to a crisis are addressed, i.e., cross-sector, cross-hierarchy, and cross-border. Cross-sector aspects are addressed mainly due to the fact that different disaster vectors are described in the scenario, and therefore, different types of First Responders (FRs) need to be foreseen (i.e., fire brigade, police, civil protection authorities, army unit, local authorities, etc.). Cross-hierarchy aspects are also addressed, since FRs from different administrative levels (e.g., local, regional, national, and transnational) need to smoothly and efficiently cooperate as an emergency response teams to such a disaster.</p> <p>Both the cross-sector response and cross-hierarchy response in each country are typically specified, at least to a certain extent, in the national legal framework (e.g., in Greece these issues are addressed in the National General Plan for Civil Protection, named "Xenokratis", correspondingly in Bulgaria in the Disaster protection law).</p> <p>Cross-border aspects are addressed since the scenario takes place at the borders between Greece and Bulgaria. It is well known that cross-border issues in case of a disaster among the EU countries are typically addressed by the EU Civil Protection Mechanism¹.</p>
<p>Integrated support systems</p>	<p>It is the radio-stations and mobile phones which are used for communication and information exchange.</p> <p>There are tablets available on the board of Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service vehicles, but their use is limited mainly to navigation. In this particular use case also, drones would be used for reconnaissance and monitoring, but this is not fully ready (drones are more in the initial phase of implementation). We envisage to use two types of drones: (1) DeltaQuad VTOL; (2) DJI Mavic Zoom, Enterprise Advanced. The drones are equipped with: IR camera, daylight camera, t C, sensors for air pollution and Toxicity, Geiger counter, moisture module, concentrated gas detection module CO, module for detecting concentrated dust particles and gas analyser.</p> <p>Besides, we envisage to use Digital Elevation model (DEM), GIS for simulation of the flood, dam damages and precipitation model.</p>

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/mechanism_en, accessed on 24.08.2020.

	<p>Furthermore, for major incident, like this one, there is available mobile command-staff vehicle of the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy equipped with communication technology, PCs, connection to the internet.</p> <p>Finally, as far as the scenario of the UC3 includes problems with the GSM communication due to the earthquake, we envisage using it as an alternative Mobile Deployable Broadband Cellular System, developed by BDI.</p>
Services and Assets	<p>In Bulgaria, it is the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian MoI whose role is to ensure the whole logistic of the transfer of larger population (evacuation). From this point of view, it is therefore important to know the potentially endangered area so that they can activate the cadastral relevant components.</p> <p>In case of already injured persons, it is the Emergency service (pre - hospital emergency health care). This subject manages whole logistic related to injuries based on their own trauma plans. It is under control of the Ministry of Health Protection of the Republic of Bulgaria.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Medical services information exchange- Flood control information exchange- Mobile coverage- Power supply availability- Critical infrastructure status information- Resources geolocation service- Emergency event log merging Slovak and Austria data- Hazard material sample tracking management and data exchange- Drone services and data exchange- Common Operational Picture real time updated

VALKYRIES opportunities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication: Between different responders' units (FRS, ambulances, police, hospitals) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved both way information exchange between responders and C2 • Between C2s of the neighbouring countries in case of incident affecting more than one country. 2. Traceability of information: SIGRUN solution ensures maximum traceability of the data collected by each actor (important facts (for police investigation, for evaluation...)). 3. Security: the SIGRUN multilayer system maximizes data security according to the access profile of each user. 4. Integration and interoperability of multidisciplinary information: all the information collected is integrated in real time to nourish horizontally all those involved (effectively deploy the forces and resources). 5. The standardisation and harmonisation of data will provide a unique opportunity for each user to manage their tasks regardless of the place of action and in a multilingual way.
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Table 30 - Emergency support activation planning information UC3

10.3. Threat scenario

Threat	<p>Terrain-level Threat. Lack of mobile network coverage and power outages on earthquake and flood scenarios might limit SIGRUN data exchange.</p> <p>Loss of communication due to coverage problems.</p> <p>Different communication systems between the first responders.</p> <p>Procedures, protocols, taxonomies, and references although similar, may have different interpretations and responses, which can lead to confusion or erroneous decision making.</p> <p>Difficulties with the languages.</p> <p>The intelligent communications network must support the communications of all the participants and be modified as needed.</p> <p>The information can be retrieved due to the order of recording communications from different devices, which allow the puzzle to be mounted.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Threat</p> <p>Quick and accurate identification of the damage of the Logodazh Dam, effective control of the floods and the leakage of chemicals and the corresponding chemical threat (substances and its effects and subsequently the optimal means to localize and minimize damage).</p>

	<p>Unmanned vehicles regulation might affect the drone deployment and use.</p> <p>Also, with determining the affected area, its Visualisation and sharing with related persons.</p> <p>Difficult cross-border coordination due to multiple factors such as language, legislative and operational barriers.</p>
Effect	<p>Terrain-level Effect</p> <p>SIGRUN with its multiple levels of operation, according to the interoperability on comms alternatives (radio, satellite, TETRA, mobile, etc.) and harmonisation can solve this type of problems that in case of counter could put at risk the optimal management of the MCI if it is not solved.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Effect.</p> <p>Improved communication tools can make disaster response activities more effective.</p> <p>VALKYRIES framework to harmonize cross border regulation on MCI and SIGRUN solution will provide cross-sectional information to all users according to their user profile, maximizing cross-border coordination and eliminating language, legislative and operational barriers</p>
Impact	<p>Terrain-level Impact.</p> <p>It will improve communications between the participants, reduce the time-to-response, increase the accuracy of the actions, decrease impact on people, environment, and other assets. Finally, as a consequence, the effectiveness and quick response on toxic leakage and floods will reduce the impact on casualties and natural resources.</p>
	<p>Planning-level Impact. If the first responders know exactly what and where is the threat, they can take appropriate means (not to waste forces and resources where it is not necessary).</p> <p>Avoid time for validations since there is common and harmonized information, reduce decision making timing and increase visibility on resources availability.</p>

Table 31 - Threat scenario UC3

10.4. Mishap’s response and risk mitigation plans, objectives and countermeasures

<p>CoA (Course of Action) - Terrain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Ambulances and other first responders will come by cars (there are existing roads) – no special need and action is expected.- Helicopters are not expected.- Survey of toxic and leakage area- Survey of flood area- Survey of urban and critical infrastructure on earthquake areas- Monitor weather conditions- Identification of victims- Mobilize medical responders to terrain.- Alert area hospitals- Alert outlying hospitals.- Establish command post- Set up emergency power supplies- Set up comms radio and/or satellite comms- Set up incident operations area (Security perimeter, staging area, transport corridor, treatment area)- Set up triage teams, collection teams, treatment teams.- Victims’ health data gathering and control- Identify potable water availability for population- Identify safe areas for population according to the weather conditions and transportation availability.- Contact off-duty personnel for possible recall.- Transport casualties to health centres- Fire fighters/CBRN/Civil protection team protection of specific area- Drone deployment- Toxic sample collection and analysis- Contact traffic authority for secondary transport options.- Civil traffic deviation- Restricted area delimitation- Communication to civil citizens & media- Evacuation- Toxic samples extraction and analysis- Civil traffic deviation- Alert administration authorities Mayor and or Governor offices- Evacuation
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demobilisation of resources
<p style="text-align: center;">CoA-Planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responders resource availability analysis • First responders resource ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) analysis • First responders' awareness • Access to incident zone planning • Assessment of mobile, radio, satellite coverage on disaster area • Assessment of power supply on disaster area • Identification of critical infrastructures • Identification of refuge areas availability • Risk analysis (CBRN scenarios, massive population impact) • Comms network coverage and capabilities assessment and contingency plans analysis • Review of communication processes and availability across the different hierarchy levels during the MCI and different countries involved. • CoA Impact assessment • What If scenarios
<p style="text-align: center;">Mishap's response and risk mitigation objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimisation of number of victims - Minimisation of toxic leakage impact - Reduction of casualties' severity - Minimize ETA - Control civil panic impact - Increase first responders' safety - Better situational awareness
<p style="text-align: center;">CoA level of automation</p>	<p>Decisions to make are always monitored and not automated. Real time information for decision making. The tool displays the relevant data for decision making</p>

Table 32 - Mishap's response and risk mitigation plans, objectives and countermeasures UC3

10.5. Traceability and observability

<p style="text-align: center;">Objectives</p>	<p>Standardisation and harmonisation of MCD when collaborating on triage and transportation on different countries.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimize data loss across the planning and execution with different actors involved. - Collection and use of the MCD for VALKYRIES solution - Potential use of SIGRUN solution with its different work profiles, such as triage, casualty stabilisation, resources, SCUE (Emergency and Urgency Coordination Service), and command and control. - Decrease time in decision making such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Priority of care classification on terrain o Evacuation decision from toxic area o Assignment of transfer hospital in Bulgaria and/or Greece. - Traceability of the injured across the different actors involved either in Bulgaria or Greece. - Integrate drone information in SIGRUM to get more complete situational awareness
<p style="text-align: center;">Requirements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REQ_COM_T3.4_3 Minimum Common Data (MCD)VALKYRIES solution availability - REQ_BASE_T4.1_2 Self-driving and unmanned vehicles - REQ_BASE_T4.2_1 Trusted communication of end-user terminals with the infrastructure - REQ_COM_T4.2_1 Sufficient communication capabilities between devices - REQ_COM_T4.2_2 Integration with existing communication technologies - REQ_COM_T4.2_3 Optimal network technology selection - REQ_COM_T4.2_4 Communication availability between devices - REQ_COM_T4.5_2 Data transmission to SIGRUN - REQ_BASE_T6.2_1 Education and Training for first aid response

<p>Observable Effects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• MCD available across the different systems• Integration of unmanned vehicles information on SIGRUN• Real time information availability across the different devices (Data delay minimum of X seconds)• VALKYRIES framework awareness (Number of people applying VALKYRIES framework)
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Table 33 - Traceability and observability UC3

11. Annex E – Use Case #4

11.1. Scenario description

Identifier	UC-VALKYRIES-#UC4
Overview description of VALKYRIES usage	<p>Sea rescue on a cross-border operation close Norway, Denmark, and Sweden</p> <p>VALKYRIES provide a common framework to address solutions that might improve cross-border cooperation in Norway and its country neighbours involving two vessels with several passengers involved. After the initial SAR there will be a clean-up of oil or chemicals in the sea drifting towards the shores.</p> <p>First responders to manage toxic spill on large water areas, sea rescue casualties, and several ships.</p> <p>Victims' identification and health assistance of the potential casualties, as long as toxic spills, might be better supervised and managed across the different first responders and medical services reducing the impact on citizens. Data exchanged and shared across different emergency actors, harmonized protocols, and tools standardisation reduce the time-to-response, with a more accurate and efficient coordinated actuations.</p>
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration coordinator: University of Southeastern Norway-USN • Overall exercise coordinator: Norwegian Coastal Administration, DSB • Key stakeholders of first responders: Norwegian Coast guard • Norwegian Coastal Administration
Potential related tools	<p>A variety of drones possible to deploy to vessels belonging to the Coast Guard and the Coastal Administration. This to demonstrate the transfer of relevant information and data to a decision support system (SIGRUN).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile comms • Maritim Broadband radio (MBR) • Radio comms (VHF) • GNSS / GALILEO information • SIGRUN

Potential data sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from instrumentation in drones, helicopters, and aircrafts. - Data from the Costal Administration preparedness and response portal (map over resources, AIS data, incidents, response plans for vulnerable areas, sightings, etc.) https://beredskap.kystverket.no/scope?lng=en - Relevant data can also be retrieved from https://kart.kystverket.no/ . Similar data are available from other North Sea countries - Information from communication with coastguard, airplanes, helicopters, sea rescue vessels and other vessels. - Weather information - Ship Traffic information - Geographical information - GNSS location from vehicles, mobile devices. - First responder's database - Electronic Health Records (EHR) - Victims' health data
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Table 34 - Scenario description UC4

11.2. Emergency support activation planning information

Background	<p>Around Europe and in northern part there are a heavy traffic of larger vessels carrying people, cargo, chemicals, and oil. There are also several military vessels in transit in the same area and some of them may carry nuclear power supply systems. A collision involving two or more of these vessels may create a huge disaster including considerable number of human casualties, heavy pollution, and risk of fire.</p>
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Strategical and Operational Vignettes

Figure 10 - Illustration from Marine Traffic (AIS) showing larger vessels in the North Sea and Baltic area

Figure 11 - Picture of a military vessel after collision with an oil tanker on The Norwegian coast some few years ago

Figure 12 - Example of scenario of a collision

Current situation

Overall Description.

Two vessels, one passenger ship and one chemical tanker, has collided in the waters between Denmark and Norway. This has resulted in some injuries on crew and passenger and a small fire on the tanker. It is urgent need to attend to passengers and to get control of the fire. The content of toxicity in the smoke is unknown but assumed poisonous.

Own Operatives.

Firefighting is difficult without special equipment; the number of firefighters is limited on board the affected vessels. The number of people in the water after the collision is unknown but need to be prioritized initially to prevent drowning/freezing to death.

The vessels involved in the collision will need to start the rescue operation of any people in water or in immediate danger.

The crew on the affected vessels will take actions to save lives and limit the consequence of the collision and any environmental impact but will need assistance from air and sea SAR capable resources and oil/chemical spill cleaning resources.

Co-operating and neutral actors.

Several other vessels in the vicinity available to assist, including one Coast Guard vessel, this will take the role as on scene commander. All the assets will be part of the exercise, no actors outside this will be needed.

	<p>Coordinator’s Assumptions. The exercise will be run by the Norwegian Coastal administration, and the Valkyrie User Case will be run as a part of this exercise.</p> <p>Limitations and constraints. The user case is part of an annual joint exercise between Norway, Denmark, and Sweden. The demonstration must be held within this exercise's frames.</p> <p>Tactical end-states and objectives. The first phase of the user-case is over when the first responders have control of all personnel involved and has extinguished the fire. The second phase ends when the details about the oil/chemical spill is known, regarding size, content and predicted drifting route.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Emergency Support Activation Planning Description</p>	<p>The initial emergency response and planning will be done onboard the vessels affected by the collision, but capacity for these activities might be severely hindered or impossible depending on the severity of the incident. Distress message will be sent out via the Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS) to all surrounding vessels and to shore with ship identification and position information.</p> <p>The Rescue Coordination Centre (RCC) that has the best ability to perform coordination will take the role and identify and plan how to best apply the SAR resources available.</p> <p>This can very well involve units from different nations, and it can change during the duration of the emergency.</p> <p>New capabilities with autonomous SAR units should be listed as resources similarly as regular SAR units and should be activated based on needed services (search for man overboard, make heatmap, find contaminated area etc.)</p> <p>VALKYRIES framework is applied to this sea incident by identifying requirements, gaps, and actor's needs.</p> <p>Actors are trained on VALKYRIES framework and technological solutions to ensure their correct understanding and use.</p> <p>Virtual rehearsals have been carried out with each stakeholder separately.</p> <p>Regional/Local administrations are engaged and supportive to enable Localisations and allowed use for final the demo scenario.</p> <p>Dissemination tasks to cover all the preparation and execution process are identified to create interest in the social media and other means.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Execution</p>	<p>Chronological events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TO: 2 vessels crash on the Norway coast with several passengers involved. A mayday alert is received by Norwegian Coastal Administration.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - T0+X min: Radio communication from Norwegian Coastal Administration is broadcasted to the ships close to the area to provide support by providing geolocation and incident initial evaluation. Vessel toxic payload is identified in the crash. First responders on/near shore are alerted to provide availability and readiness details. - T0+ 30: Drones with chemical sample instrumentation is set up. - T0+1h: Ships near the crash start providing casualties information and toxic spill. Drone departs to incident area on sea. - T0+1,5h: Drone starts transmitting video from sea incident area. Toxic spill is spreading along a broader area than expected. - T0+1,75h: Drone takes a sample of the toxic spill and provide first data about spill. - T0+2,25h: Drone is back on shore/mother ship with toxic sample. Next drone departs to sea incident area to monitor spill progress. <p>This will be repeated several times to monitor the different activities in the area and taking several samples to understand progress and concentration on the toxic spill.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - T0+3h: Rescue ships and toxic control ships arrive to sea incident area and start controlling the spill and provide advanced care to the victims involved in the crash. Toxic spill spread is monitored. - T0+6h: Casualties are brought on shore to hospitals. - T0+12h: After the initial SAR there will be a clean-up of oil or chemicals in the sea drifting towards the shores. Toxic spill is controlled. First responder resources are demobilized.
Tasks and business processes	<p>Decisions to involve autonomous agents in the SAR operation is taken by the RCC and during the clean-up phase by the Coastal Administration command centre. The procedure can be as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reserve autonomous unit 2. Accept or reject reservation

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. If accepted, then activate autonomous unit 4. Self-check and communication check 5. Deploy autonomous unit 6. Monitor and assign duties to the autonomous unit 7. Process data from the autonomous unit 8. Present data to the correct consumers 9. Return to home position 10. Post-mission check, charge/refuel and decommission
Coordination instructions	<p>Each mission with then autonomous units will create a set of data that can be of interest for different parts of the emergency response organisation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual imagery of scene: All - Man overboard: the closest SAR Rescue unit - Location of fire and structural damage: SAR Coordinators and firefighters - Chemical composition of water: SAR Coordinators and clean-up command centre.
Integrated support systems	<p>The aim is to deploy drones to conduct surveillance to assist in picture compilation and situational awareness to make correct decisions.</p>
Services and Assets	<p>The user case demonstration must have seagoing platforms has mother ship for the deployment of drones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical services information exchange - Mobile coverage - Chemical information and databases look ups - Resources geolocation service - Emergency event log merging Slovak and Austria data - Drone services and data exchange - Common Operational Picture real time updated
VALKYRIES opportunities	<p>To demonstrate and evaluate how information flow between drones-control centres and first responders is concerning the use of SIGRUN platform.</p>

Table 35 - Emergency support activation planning information UC4

11.3. Threat scenario

Threat	Terrain-level Threat. Toxic spill extension and impact on sea. Vessel status and situational awareness around the incident area.
	Planning-level Threat. Identify number of casualties, severity and resource availability and proximity Drone information exchange with SIGRUN must harmonized.
Effect	Terrain-level Effect. Situational awareness by providing images and sharing data to the different first responders on real-time to make more informed decisions.
	Planning-level Effect. Situational awareness of resources availability, readiness and proximity.
Impact	Terrain-level Impact. Realtime information exchanged across first responders to make more accurate decisions about casualties and spill characteristics. Reduced impact on affected sea area. Potential less severity of casualties.
	Planning-level Impact. More efficient number of resources deployed and less ETA for first responders.

Table 36 - Threat scenario UC4

11.4. Mishap's response and risk mitigation plans, objectives and countermeasures

CoA-Terrain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drone booking - Drone instrumentation set up - Drone flight plan authorisation - Drone deployment - Survey of toxic and leakage area - Monitor weather conditions - Identification of victims - Mobilize medical responders to terrain. - Alert area hospitals - Alert outlying hospitals. - Establish command post
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set up comms radio and/or satellite comms - Toxic sample collection and analysis - Communication to civil citizens & media - Evacuation - Toxic samples extraction and analysis - Alert administration authorities Mayor and or Governor offices - Evacuation - Demobilisation of resources
<p style="text-align: center;">CoA-Planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responders' awareness • Access to incident zone planning • Assessment of mobile, radio, satellite coverage on disaster area • Identification of critical infrastructures • Risk analysis (HAZMAT scenarios, massive population impact) • Comms network coverage and capabilities assessment and contingency plans analysis • Review of communication processes and availability across the different hierarchy levels during the MCI and different countries involved. • CoA Impact assessment What If scenarios
<p style="text-align: center;">Mishap's response and risk mitigation objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimisation of number of victims - Minimisation of toxic leakage impact - Reduction of casualties' severity - Minimize ETA - Control civil panic impact - Increase first responders' safety - Better situational awareness
<p style="text-align: center;">CoA level of automation</p>	<p>Decisions to make are always monitored and not automated. Real time information for decision making. The tool displays the relevant data for decision making</p>

Table 37 - Mishap's response and risk mitigation plans, objectives and countermeasures UC4

11.5. Traceability and observability

Objectives	<p>Study how autonomous units can be of assistance and contribute to Localisation of victims, fires, structural damages, and chemical spills.</p> <p>How can data from the autonomous units be presented and used by the response organisation.</p>
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REQ_COM_T3.4_3 Minimum Common Data (MCD) VALKYRIES solution availability - REQ_BASE_T4.1_2 Self-driving and unmanned vehicles - REQ_BASE_T4.2_1 Trusted communication of end-user terminals with the infrastructure - REQ_COM_T4.2_1 Sufficient communication capabilities between devices - REQ_COM_T4.2_2 Integration with existing communication technologies - REQ_COM_T4.2_3 Optimal network technology selection - REQ_COM_T4.2_4 Communication availability between devices - REQ_COM_T4.5_2 Data transmission to SIGRUN - REQ_BASE_T6.2_1 Education and Training for first aid response
Observable Effects	<p>Recorded timeline from the autonomous systems point of view compared with the response coordinators timeline (when is data/pictures/video available from the autonomous systems compared with availability from other rescue units). To what extent is the data from the autonomous systems useful for the situational awareness / situational understanding for the rescue units and coordinators.</p>

Table 38 - Traceability and observability UC4

12. Annex E – Traceability matrix

** The matrix is included in D2.1 A/1 and will be used in the deliverables from this point onwards to ensure requirements' compliance. No additions have been made to this deliverable D2.7 A/1 to avoid increasing pages.

13. Annex F – VALKYRIES Objectives

Objective	Description
VALK-OBJ-1	<u>(Map of growing commercial and R&D opportunities)</u> : Analyse the existing/ongoing technological, procedural, education and collaborative opportunities of the first aid response supplier markets and related signs of progress beyond the state-of-the-art able to improve the EU disaster resiliency
VALK-OBJ-2	<u>(Sustainable Regulation and ethical compliance)</u> : Analyse the first aid response cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy regulatory and ethical principles, identifying minimum standard requirements, lacunae, and hurdles, and developing recommendations to policymakers and stakeholders to facilitate their enforcement through the consolidation of a harmonized regulatory framework and the implementation of new strategic schemes.
VALK-OBJ-3	<u>(Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation)</u> : Research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines, and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardisation actions.
VALK-OBJ-4	<u>(Sustainable certification and conformity assessment criteria)</u> : Analyse the accreditation and certification opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, including the enforced conformity assessment criteria, evaluation procedures and facilities; resulting in recommendations, guidelines, and strategies to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation, and homogeneity assessment.
VALK-OBJ-5	<u>(Sustainable Harmonisation framework)</u> : Development of a holistic framework for supporting the standardisation/harmonisation of first aid response enablers assuming their cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy hybrid dimensions, bearing in mind the vertical/horizontal propagation of consequences of the decisions made between technical, procedural, and collaborative domains.
VALK-OBJ-6	<u>(Harmonisation of vehicular first aid technologies, procedures, and collaboration)</u> : Research, analyse and apply the VALKYRIES' recommendations, guidelines and harmonisation tactics on reference equipment, technologies, procedures, preparedness, raise awareness and related collaborative solutions.

Objective	Description
VALK-OBJ-7	<i>(Cross-sectorial collaboration, civilian protection, volunteering and military assistance)</i> : Research, analyse and expand the harmonisation framework towards facilitating, guiding, and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors, among them firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection, military, or heterogeneous volunteering.
VALK-OBJ-8	<i>(Reference integration and interoperation)</i> : Reference integration and interoperation of the harmonised technological, procedural, and collaborative solutions based on the common requirements and gap mitigations prioritised by the committed end-users and practitioners.
VALK-OBJ-9	<i>(Large EU scale cross-border demonstrations)</i> : Evaluation and demonstration of the interoperability and enhancements derived from harmonising vehicular first aid related enablers at four cross-border and cross-sectorial scenarios: Spain-Portugal, Slovakia-Austria, Bulgaria-Greece, and Norway-Netherlands.

Table 39 - VALKYRIES Objectives

14. Annex G – Call Challenges

(Horizon 2020 - Work Programme 2018-2020 Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens)

SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020: pre-normative research and demonstration for disaster-resilient societies

Call Challenge	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
VALK-CHAL-1	Innovation action on “First aids vehicles deployment, training, maintenance, logistic and remote centralized coordination means.”	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
VALK-CHAL-2	“A reason for the difficult interaction among practitioners, and for the low levels of interoperability of equipment and procedures implemented by first responders, lies in there being insufficient harmonisation and standardisation, which pre-normative research and demonstrations may address effectively.”	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
VALK-CHAL-3	“The security market in Europe is an institutional market that is highly fragmented (because of the lack of standardisation and harmonised certification), and with a strong societal dimension (it directly affects in many ways the citizens).”	VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6
VALK-CHAL-4	“The Mandate M/487 to Establish Security Standards coordinated by the European Committee for Standardisation has clearly recognized the whole field of “crisis management and civil protection” as one of the three priorities for establishing standards in the security sector. It has identified the need for crisis management and civil protection standardisation activities to facilitate response, effectiveness, efficiency and cooperation as top priorities, especially in what regards to natural hazard emergencies).”	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Call Challenge	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives
VALK-CHAL-5	“Improved standards and common communication data exchange mechanisms are required for an effective deployment of resources during the run-up to a major crisis related to any kind of disaster either natural (including resulting from climate-related extremes) or man-made, and immediately after the event, for example in case of a mass evacuation from an urban area.”	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
VALK-CHAL-6	“Proposals should target in particular events where there are strong cross-sector, cross-border, cross-hierarchy coordination activities ongoing, and therefore the issue of interoperability.”	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9
VALK-CHAL-7	“The aim is to pave the way to improved standards, including voluntary Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and/or ISO or EN standards.”	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5
VALK-CHAL-8	“The centre of gravity for technology development with actions funded under this topic is expected to be up to TRL 6 to 7 – see General Annex G of the Horizon 2020 Work Programme.”	Main Objective

Table 40 - Call Challenges

15. Annex H – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AAS	Área Apoio e Servicos
ACM	Advanced Command Post
AIS Marine Traffic	Automatic Identification Systems
APIs	Applications interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
C&C	Command and Control
C3ISR	Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR)
C4	C4 (Main Command and Control Centre Operation).
CBRN	Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear defence
CCOD	Contact Centre On Demand / Centro de Coordenação Operacional Distrital
CECOPI	Centro de Coordinación Operativa Integrado
CETAC	Centro Tático de Comando
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
CIMIC	Civil-Military Cooperation
CIS	Clinical Information System
CODIS	Comandante Distrital
2º CODIS	2º Comandante Distrital
CoP	Conference of the Parties
COP	Common operational picture

Acronym	Description
COR	Centro Operativo Regional Plan INFOEX
COREPC	Comandante Regional
2º COREPC	2º Comandante Regional
COS	Comandante das Operacoes de Socorro
CSAM	CoordCom
DMMP	Disaster Medical Management Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoW	Description of Work
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster risk reduction
DTA	Digital Twins Aggregated
DTI	Digital Twin Instance
E&T	Education and Training
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EDT	Portable Digital Twins
EHR	Electronic Health Records
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EOC	Emergency Operations Centres
EPPO	Earthquake Planning and Protection Organisation
ER	Emergency Response
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival

Acronym	Description
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
F2F	Face-to-Face
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
FIIBAP	Fundación para la Investigación e Innovación Biosanitaria de Atención Primaria
FR	Funding Requirement
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	The General Directorate
GIS	Geographic Information System
GMDSS	Global Maritime Distress and Safety System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HAZMAT	Hazard Material
IOA	Incident Operations Area
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ICU	Intensive Care Units
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IM	Innovation & IPR Manager (IM).
INFOCAEX	Plan Especial de Protección Civil ante incendios forestales
INFOEX	Plan de Lucha contra los Incendios Forestales de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

Acronym	Description
IRS	Integrated Rescue System
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KPPs	Key Performance Parameters
LRT	Local Reforco Tático
META	Modelo Extrahospitalario de Triage Avanzado (Advanced Triage Model) (Arcos González, y otros, 2016)
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MCDT1	MCD Primary Triage
MCDT2	MCD Secondary Triage
MCI	Mass Casualty Incident
MDC	Minimum Data Collection
MIDS	Minimum Incident Data Set
MoI SR	Ministry of Interior Section of Crisis Management
NB	Narrowband
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NHS	National Health Service
OA	Overarching Architecture
OASIS	Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
OMS	Operations Management System
OODA	Observe, Orient, Decide, Act
PC	Personal Computer
PCO	Posto de Comando Operacional

Acronym	Description
PEMU	Plan Territorial de Protección Civil de ámbito local
PIM	Platform Independent Model
PLATERCAEX	Plan Territorial de Protección Civil de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura
PLEGEM	Plan General de Emergencias del Estado
PMA	Advanced Command Post
PND	Personal Navigation Devices
PPE	Personal protective equipment
PSA	Puesto Sanitario Avanzado – Treatment Area in Incident Operations Area
PSM	Platform Specific Model
QRM	Quality Assurance & Risk Manager
RBT	Área Reabastecimientos
RCC	Rescue Coordination Centre
SAR	Search and Rescue
SAZ	Sanitary Assistance Zone
SELP	Safety, ethical, legal and privacy rules
SCU	Special Care Units
SCUE	Emergency and Urgency Coordination Service
SOP	Standard operating procedure
SOPs	Standard Operative Procedures
SSO	Single Sign-On
TETRA	Terrestrial Trunked Radio
TTP	Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures

Acronym	Description
UC	Use Case
VCMS	Victim Case Management System
VCOC	Veiculo de Comando e Comunicações
VCOT	Veiculo de Comando Tático
ZA	Zona de Apoio
ZCR	Zona de Concentracao e Reserva
ZRR	Zona de Rececao de Reforcoss
ZS	Zona de Sinistro

Table 41 – Glossary

16. Annex I – References and bibliography

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